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Vol. I, Issue 01

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Dr. H. H. A. Karunarathna

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Editorial Note

It is a great pleasure to launch the Nagananda International Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences (NIJHSS) as a peer-reviewed journal in Sri Lanka. Many scholars have suggested the need for an internationally dedicated platform where researchers can have a great opportunity to present their research findings and views. It provides really an exciting opportunity to consider the truly interdisciplinary nature which will further create a research community that would deal with the Archaeology, Anthropology, History, Ethnography, Indigenous Medicine, Sociology and Criminology, English Language / Teaching and Literature, Geography, Buddhist Studies and Pali Language, Computer Science, Mass Communication, Heritage Studies, Tourism Management and Economy of Sri Lanka and South Asia in particular.

The objective of Nagananda International Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences is to publish up-to-date, high-quality, and original research studies full of relevant and insightful reviews. As such, the journal aspires to be vibrant, engaging and accessible, and at the same time integrative and challenging. Each issue of the journal consists of three types of papers. The first, provides a short contemporary and provocative ‘opinion piece’ on an issue or synthesis of issues pertinent to Archaeology, Anthropology, Art, Architecture, Numismatics, Iconography, Ethnography, and various other scientific aspects. The second, Critical reviews, provides a critical and concise yet comprehensive and contemporary review of a particular theme specific to research being conducted in areas that are not often well published such as the North of Sri Lanka. The third type of paper includes Research Papers that are more traditional in form and demonstrates a sound theoretical and/or methodological underpinning and a clear contribution to knowledge in the field. NIJHSS also aims to bring almost cutting edge research in other related scientific, technical and methodological fields to the focus area of current society. Needless to say, any papers that you wish to submit, either individually or collaboratively, are much appreciated and will make a substantial contribution to the early development and success of the journal.

Best wishes and thank you in advance for your contribution to the Nagananda International Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences (NIJHSS). I would like to shower upon you my profuse thanks for your great contribution in making this journal a complete success. I would also like to extend my gratitude to Ven. Professor Bodagama Chandima Thera, the Vice-Chancellor of Nagananda International Institute for Buddhist Studies, for his immense and valuable advice in this regard.

Moreover, I extended gratitude to Professor Ratne Wijetunge, former Dean of the Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences, Ven. Professor Induragare Dhammarathana Thera, Acting Dean of the Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences, the scholars contributed in reviewing the articles in the journal, and all the Heads of the relevant departments.

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Contents

Management and Communication in Buddhist Context.....	1-17
Professor Sumanapala Galmangoda	
Determinants of Internship Satisfaction: Study of the Management Undergraduate of a Leading State University in Sri Lanka.....	18-44
L.P.J.R.Samendra and T.D Weerasinghe	
Cascading Systems fed by the ancient Yodha ela canal of Anuradhapura in Sri Lanka.....	45-71
Dr. H. H. Ashoka Karunaratna	
The Hindu-Buddhist religious and social reconciliation reflected from pre-Buddhist time to the 3rd Century AC period in Sri Lanka.....	72-82
Dr. Dananjaya Gamalath and Dr. Nayomi Kekulawala	
Introduction to Comparative models for Innovation theory. (Review of Chapter 14: Introduction to Modern Economic Growth by daron Acemoglu, 2008).....	83-89
Kasun D.Ramanayaka	
Anthropological analysis on the new trends and changes of Catholic system of belief and rituals (With Special references to Chilaw, Sri Lanka)..	90-101
W.K.M.Wijerathna	
An Archaeological Comparison of Late Medieval Non-Religious Architecture between Kerala and Sri Lanka.....	102-119
Buddhisha Jayashan Weerasuriya	

Management and Communication in Buddhist Context

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Abstract:

This article examines the fundamental aims and the objective of Buddhism depending on its world view. For instance, the vision of Buddhist order is to realize nibbana, the cessation of suffering. Its mission is to propagate the Buddha's message throughout the world for the sake of all beings. The order of monks and nuns has rendered its service over two thousand and five hundred years in order to fulfil the above vision and mission. While observing the evolution of this process related to the order of sangha the article compares the main concepts of modern management system with those of the sangha society. Further, it introduces some unique concepts of Buddhist management system which can be considered as a contribution to the modern concept of management. Communication is an essential part of management and verbal communication has been the main medium of communication in the propagation of Buddhism throughout the world. So, the Buddhist sources include a wealth of information regarding the nature of language and its usage in the context of verbal communication. The important facts relevant to the subject have been elucidated with reference to the doctrinal and historical explanations in the early Buddhist sources.

Keywords: *Communication, Management, verbal Communication, Buddhist sources*

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Introduction:

Management and communication are two areas of Buddhism which have not been adequately examined in the modern researches in this field. I have taken an attempt to clarify some important facts related to this field which I think, will provide a positive contribution to the existing knowledge of the subject in the modern world.

Result and Discussion:

Though the two subject's management and communication are studied in a wider context still the modern world faces a number of problems in addition to their positive contribution to solve many problems in the modern society. Therefore the new facts revealed in this article will provide a good context to revive the modern methods of these two subjects in order to bring them to a more profitable level.

Management is a most useful system of government and a highly developed subject of education in the modern world. Its usefulness is being felt more and more with the growth and complexity of the society. There are a number of species of beings in the world. Among these various kinds of beings the man is different from others because he has the ability to thinking, ability to communicate perfectly and is endowed with awareness of moral behaviour. In ancient times the human society was not complexed and its needs were simple in connection with simple way of life it was accustomed to. So it could maintain its life-style without much effort. With the development of modern science and technology and the related increase of human thinking the man's needs became very complexed. In order to meet with these unlimited needs he had to manage the limited resources of the world. He understood that he cannot fulfil these needs without a proper management of the limited resources. As a result there arose various organizations of production, distribution and management of goods in the society. Meanwhile there arose a necessity of a system of management in order to maintain these organizations successfully. As these organizations are interconnected worldwide their system of management also seems very similar in content. Such a plan of management which is universally accepted is called management. According to the modern view this process of management consists of the following themes:

1. Planning
2. Organization
3. Staffing
4. Direction
 - i. Leadership
 - j. Motivation
 - k. Communication
 - l. Co-ordination
5. Control

Buddhist teachings consist of not only the facts related to management but also important views regarding politics, economics, law, health, aesthetics and sociology. They are mostly available in conceptual form and need clarifications in accordance with the modern social context. Through such clarifications no doubt, we can surely make a positive contribution to those fields of study.

Before we go into the details of the concept of management it is worthwhile to consider in brief the Buddhist analysis of the individual and the related world. All Buddhist teachings are based on this world view.

According to Buddhism the world in reality is an unsatisfactory abode although we experience temporary feelings of satisfaction.

“Na kahāpanavassena titti kāmesu vijjati”¹

“The human beings are not satisfied even with a rain of gold”

The main reason for this dissatisfaction is the changing nature of the phenomena. The beings having created an unchanging world of concepts out of the constantly changing world try to experience an eternal satisfaction in it. In reality we attach to the concepts but not to the real world.

“Saṅkapparāgo purisassa kāmo”²

“Desire of the person means attachment to concepts”

The person who is attached to concepts sees suffering as happiness. “Dukkhaṃ sukhaṃ rūpeṇa”. All leave this world with some kind of a feeling of wanting. “Ūno loko atitto taṇhādāso”³ This is the reality of the world. Some people think that they can achieve success in life if they chase after pleasures having discarded the reality. The sciences such as economics, medicine, chemistry and management are being studied and practised in order to help the people in their unsuccessful attempt to achieve satisfactoriness. In reality, there has been no one in the past, will not be in the future and is not at present who has experienced full satisfaction in life.

“Na cāhu na ca bhavissati na cetaṛahi vijjati”⁴

Therefore, Buddhism after realistic analysis of the world of experience presents a true way of attaining full satisfaction in this very life. This way is completely different from the path recommended by the modern sciences. If the modern way of life is compared to a river flowing downward, the Buddhist path is equal to a river flowing upward.

“Paṭisoṭagāmiṃ nipuṇaṃ”⁵

Instead of following the path leading to sensual pleasures with blind beliefs, Buddhism shows the way to reduce desires. Modern sciences mostly recommend treatments to the effect but not to the cause. Let us take for example the treatments

recommended for birth control. The Buddhist recommendation for this is not controlling birth but controlling one's desires. Buddhism explains with facts that full satisfaction is not a dream if the life is planned on the above mentioned right view of the world.

“Victory brings enmity. Defeat brings suffering. Those who give up both are always satisfied”

“Jayam veram pasavati dukkham seti parajito
upasanto sukham seti hitva jayaparajayam”⁶

The concept of management becomes essential to plan the behaviour according to the reality of existence. Buddhist teachings point out that a proper management should be applied to all aspects of life: economic, political, religious and social.

I have shown above that there are several fundamental characteristics in the modern concept of management.

At the very outset it is important to clarify how these fundamental characteristics are applied in Buddhist teachings. Next we can clarify the Buddhist contribution that could be made in regard to the modern concept of management.

The concept of management is applied to a certain institution which generally constitutes of a group of people working together towards a common objective. The Buddhist community of sangha is an institution which has an unbroken history of about 2500 years. Its glorious history and success is mainly due to the principles of management on which it was established in the 6th century B.C. It will take several volumes to discuss its structure and aims in detail. Here our attention is focussed only to point out few facts in brief with regard to the organization of the order of sangha.

The sangha society was established on a firm ground with minor objectives and a direct goal. Its goal was to attain nibbana as a solution to the mass of suffering that human beings have to face in their wonderings in the existence.(7) The behaviour of the monk who treads upon this path contributes to the development of morality and peaceful environment in the society. These are considered as minor objectives of the sangha society. (8) The noble eightfold path is included within the threefold training system viz, morality, concentration and wisdom. (9) It should be emphasized that this path is recommended not only for the monks but also for the lay people who lead a worldly life. Planning includes aims and the objective of an institution and the determination of the means to achieve them. The above mentioned objectives, the goal and the path leading to achieve them with regard to the organization of the sangha can be compared with the aspect of planning.

The next aspect of management is termed as organization. This includes activities such as departmentation, authority, delegation of authority etc. The activities of the sangha also has been divided in to divisions and sub-divisions and the authority of those divisions are ascribed to suitable members of the order. Mainly the disciplinary rules are divided into two groups as Ubhatovibhanga and Khandaka.(10) Ubhatovibhanga consists of the

rules pertaining to the individual life of a monk. They are the four great offences *pārājikā*, thirteen *saṅghādhisesas*, offences which can be decided only by a formal *saṅgha-kamma*, two *aniyatas*, uncertain rules etc. *Khandaka* includes rules and regulations pertaining to the social life of a monk. They are related to activities such as ordination (*pabbajjā*), higher ordination (*upasampadā*), ecclesiastical activities (*uposatha*), giving punishments (*daṇḍakamma*)¹¹, observing rainy season (*vassūpanāyika*) etc. Further eminent monks had been appointed as authorities in order to put these rules and appointments. Ven. Upāli as the authority on *Vinaya* and Ven. Ānanda as the treasurer of *dhamma* can be cited as examples. In addition, some monks have been appointed as advisors and the reciters of the rules and regulations at the regular meetings of the *saṅgha*.¹² It should be noted here that the third aspect of management, staffing, is also included in the above activities. Appointments as authorities on various tasks and training provided for the monks under the distinguished teachers etc. are closely connected with the activities related to staffing.

The fourth aspect of management namely, direction means to lead the authorities properly, to act successfully in relation to their individual services. There are several things that should be completed so as to fulfil the purpose of direction. Leadership, motivation, communication and co-ordination are most important among them. As to the leadership Buddhism emphasizes that the leader should speak what he performs and should perform what he speaks (**yathāvādī tathākārī yathākārī tathāvādī**)¹³ There should not be any difference between his thoughts, speech and functions. Further he should be a talented, skilful, active and wise person (*vyatta*, *paṭibala*, *paṇḍita*, *sakka*)¹⁴ Through our Buddhist teachings one can notice that the Buddha and his leading disciples have motivated other followers by their exemplary characters as well as by various methods of teaching the *dhamma*. The communication among the members of the order was properly maintained through the regular meetings held twice a month.¹⁵ In these meetings the members had the opportunity to communicate with their elders and friends. It was helpful to maintain mutual respect. Confidence and friendship among the members. This is called the act of co-ordination in management.

The *Vinayapiṭaka* records a number of cases in which some Buddhist monks and nuns have transgressed the rules and regulations.¹⁶ There are a large number of supplementary rules and punishments recommended in the *Vinaya* for the rehabilitation of such monks and nuns. It was the practice that wrong behaviour of the members was directly informed to the Buddha or leading disciples and the accused was summoned to settle the case by giving proper advice and thereby laying down new or supplementary rules and regulations. Further the monks had the opportunity to settle their problems pertaining to moral behaviour in the meetings held twice a month. Such activities in the order come under the fifth aspect of management called control.

Thus it is clear that almost all the fundamental aspects of the modern concept of management could be seen in the organization of the *saṅgha* society.

Now attention should be focussed on the above mentioned activities of the order in detail. No doubt it will be a task which needs volumes and a long-term endeavour to study all the aspects of the structure and the nature of disciplinary rules. Such a study will reveal many facts which can be adopted in order to revive the modern concept of management. Here our attempt is to point out in brief the evolution of the concept of ordination (pabbajjā) in the Theravada tradition as a guide to those who wish to further their studies in this regard.

Here our intention is to clarify the evolution of the order of sangha in the light of the Vinayaṭīka which is not only collection of vinaya rules but a historical record of the Buddhist order as a whole. It represents the history of order at least up to the time of the second Buddhist council, held one hundred years after the Buddha's passing away. The Cullavaggapāli includes details of the second council¹⁸ and the Parivārapāli includes even the names of monks who visited Sri Lanka at the time of King Asoka,¹⁹ in the third century B.C. Thus we can consider the Vinayaṭīka as representing the middle phase of the evolution of the concept of ordination although it consists of details relevant to the early phase of the order.

At the very outset it is extremely important to mention that the four conditions stated in the Pārājikāpāli regarding the deterioration of the order.

- i. long existence of the order
- ii. expansion and growth of its membership
- iii. receiving an abundance of requisites
- iv. intellectual progress of the members²⁰

A close observation of the Vinayaṭīka reveals that the above conditions came into being in the order in the course of time. Due to this reason the Buddha had to formulate a large number of disciplinary rules regarding the behaviour of monks and nuns. This occurred, according to the tradition, about twenty years after the Buddha's enlightenment. By that time the membership of the order had increased up to thousand when comparing with Anāthapiṇḍika and Visākā had gathered around the Buddha and his disciples with the intention of supporting and promoting its healthy existence. They made monasteries and supplied daily requisites in abundance.⁽²¹⁾ Meanwhile some disciples like Sāti held different views regarding the teachings of the Buddha. All these conditions, according to the above mentioned statement, tend to create deterioration of the order. Therefore, the Buddha being concerned about the stability of the order in the future laid down disciplinary rules on different occasions with the following objectives:

- i. restraintment of the saṅgha society
- ii. well-being of the saṅgha society
- iii. restraintment of the untamed persons
- iv. well-being of the members who wish to be trained

- v. to safeguard oneself from the defilements pertaining to this world
- vi. to safeguard oneself from the defilements pertaining to the next existence
- vii. to rouse confidence among those who are not converted to Buddha's teachings.
- viii. To increase confidence of those who are already converted
- ix. for the long existence of the doctrine
- x. to encourage monks and nuns in their restraintment ²²

These can be considered as the objectives of the order introduced in the course of its evolution. The Vinayaṭaka includes two hundred and sixteen disciplinary rules for the monks which are classified under six categories:

i.	pārājika	-	04
ii.	saṅghādisesa	-	13
iii.	aniyata	-	02
iv.	nissaggiyapācittiya	-	30
v.	pācittiya	-	92
vi.	sekhiyā	-	<u>75</u>
			216

Pārājika refers to grave transgression of the relevant rules for the monks and nuns and as a result one merits expulsion from the order. ²³ Saṅghādisesa means a class of offences which can be decided only by a formal saṅgha -kamma -ecclesiastical activities.²⁴ Aniyata refers to the offences which are uncertain and therefore should be concluded by a trial²⁵. The offences that should be settled by giving up are called nissaggiya.²⁶ The offences requiring expiation are termed as pācittiya.²⁷ The rules connected with training are called sekhiyā.²⁸ The entire concept of ordination depends on the main objectives of Buddhism. Vinaya or the disciplinary rules are considered as the life of the order²⁹ Samanthapāsādikā. As ven. Buddhaghosa explains in his Visuddhimagga, discipline leads for restraintment, restraintment creates non-delusion, non-delusion creates delight, delight produces zest, happiness brings pacification, pacification produces happiness, happiness is for concentration, concentration paves the way for insight resulting in disgust with worldly life, disgust with worldly life brings non-attachment, non-attachment directs one to freedom or emancipation.³⁰ The above statement clarifies the gradual progress expected through training in vinaya rules. It should not be overlooked here that these vinaya rules are meant for the spiritual progress of individual monks and nuns. There remains another aspect of ordination which covers the social life of the saṅgha. The relevant rules and regulations for this aspect are recorded in the vinaya texts called Cullavaggapāli³¹ and Mahāvaggapāli.³²

With the evolution of the order in the course of time, the social life of the saṅgha turned to be more important than the individual life. Certainly the social life happened to be the main cause of the long standing of the order. The unbroken history of the order going back to about two thousand five hundred years is the result of these rules regarding the social life of the saṅgha. The rules and regulations connected with the social activities are collectively called khandhakavinaya.³³ It includes a number of rules regarding every aspect of social life of the saṅgha. Some are connected with punishments given to certain offences which violate social harmony of the saṅgha. The Mahāvagga includes a large number of rules which are applicable to maintain a good relationship between teachers and pupils.³⁴ The observance of rainy season coupled with several important rules was an essential aspect of conduct for the unification of monks and laity. The robe especially prepared for the monks who have observed rainy season is called kaṭhina and there are certain rules applied to it.³⁵ It is a well known fact that the kaṭhina ceremony has created a great awareness among the faithful devotees up to date. Another important fact relevant to the social aspect is the recommendation given to the disciples to ordain individuals and confer on them the higher ordination. Rules have been laid down to prevent unsuitable persons entering the order.³⁶ Seven criteria are recommended for settlement of disputes among the saṅgha.³⁷ Further it is very important that the two councils held by the Theravādinas are recorded in the Cullavaggapāli.³⁸ This event indirectly suggests that the preservation of the saṅgha tradition also comes under the social aspect of monk's life.

By the foregoing observation on the vinaya rules, one can easily infer the objectives of ordination which were introduced into the order in the course of its evolution. It was emphasized that the spiritual progress of the individuals was more important at the initial stage. When the saṅgha grew in number the social aspect was given a prominent place among the religious activities. This was further emphasized after the passing away of the Buddha. The demise of the Buddha greatly necessitated the preservation of his teachings for the sake of future generation. There was no individual leader appointed to look after the order. The Dhamma vinaya was designated to play the role of the Teacher. The Buddha's teachings at the time were scattered and an attempt was taken to collect and classify them through the councils.³⁹ Further, in the course of time, the fundamentals of the teachings were abstracted and new discourse were composed consisting of only the doctrinal matters. They were re-defined with a language consisting of more technical terms. This process resulted in creation of a new set of discourses called Abhidhamma.⁴⁰ By the time of the third Buddhist council held two hundred and thirty six years after the Buddha's passing away, in the reign of King Asoka, the Abhidhammapīṭaka of the Theravada had already been completed.

After the second Buddhist council, held one hundred years after the Buddha's demise, there occurred the schism of the order. The sangha was split into two traditions as Theravāda and Mahāsaṅghika.⁴¹ They tried to make collections of the Buddha's teachings which differed in form and content, giving supportive evidence to prove their openings. Mahāsaṅghikas presented the theory of the transcendental nature of the Buddha.⁴² Other

schools of Buddhism sprang from the above mentioned two traditions, Personalist school (Puggalavāda) held that there exists a person in an absolute sense which transmigrates from one existence to the other.⁴³ Sarvāstivādins upheld the theory that the elements of existence possess their own nature which does not change in the three periods of time.⁴⁴ Theravādins emphasized that the elements of existence are real only in the present moment.⁴⁵ Sautrāntikas emphasized the idealistic nature of the world of experience depending more closely on the original discourses.⁴⁶ Thus it is clear that the role of the saṅgha after the demise of the Buddha was more connected with intellectual activities than with spiritual matters of individual life. Propagation of Dhamma was an essential task undertaken by the disciples and after the third Buddhist council on the instruction of ven. Moggalīputtatissa nine missionary groups were sent to different countries.⁴⁷ A group of monks and a lay person headed by ven. Mahinda came to Sri Lanka and introduced Buddhism.⁴⁸ From that day Sri Lanka has played a prominent role in the propagation of Theravāda tradition through out several countries in South Asia. Although Buddhism disappeared from its motherland it was preserved and developed well in Sri Lanka, Burma, Thailand, Laos and Cambodia. It is a historical fact that Sri Lanka played a prominent roll in the expansion of Buddhism in several countries.

Communication:

Although we do not find a systematic exposition of language, there are numerous references to the nature and usage of language in the early Buddhist discourses. In such references, terms such as sāmāñña, saṅkhā, vohāra, nirutti, sammuti, adhivacana and paññatti (49) are used in connection with the aspects of linguistic communication. A study on these terms and their contexts reveal some important insight into the Buddha's attitude toward the nature and usage of language which might have influenced the evolution of the conception of paññatti in the later Pāli commentarial literature. The term paññatti which is used in the discourses synonymously with osme other terms like nirutti and sammañña has been singled out in the post -cononical Theravada abhidhamma directly to refer to linguistic communication. Therefore, in our inquiry into the early Buddhist attitude toward the nature and usage of language, we should pay attention not only to the term paññatti but also to the other terms synonymous with it.

The Buddhist discourses include the facts regarding the nature of the world of experience. These facts are generally designated as dhamma. Dhamma has been explained in the discourses thorough language. The language, whatever is its form, is the primary means of communication. (50) The communicator is necessarily aware of the medium that he uses to communicate his message. This is true even in regard to the Buddha's teachings. In many discourses we find the Buddha expressing his ideas about the nature and usage of language to his disciples. Prof. D.J. Kalupahana summarizes the content of such expressions of the Buddha as follows:

“The Buddha, who perceived the world of human experience as being in flux, was not willing to recognize language as a permanent and eternal entity. Like everything else, language loka- sāmañña = generality of the world, loka- vohāra = usage of the world, loka- nirutti = convention of the world is in flux.”⁵¹

As far as the numerous references that occur in the discourses regarding the nature and usage of language are concerned, the following facts can be discerned which probably influenced the evolution of the conception of paññatti in the post-canonical Theravāda abhidhamma:

- i. two constituents of language: sound and meaning
- ii. conditional nature of language
- iii. contextual basis of the meaning of language
- iv. the existence of various methods of communication
- v. psychological basis of linguistic communication

Language is a system which relates sounds with meanings.⁵² Sounds and meanings are the two main constituents of language. Therefore, any explanation of the nature of language should be focussed on these two aspects. The Buddha who was well aware of the medium of communication, advised the disciples to preach the dhamma through a perfect style of language. According to him not only the meaning but also the sound of language (sātham sabyañjanam) should be perfect.⁵³ This clarifies the Buddha's attitude regarding the usefulness of a standard means of communication for the propagation of his message, He possessed a voice consisting of eight resonant qualities. The Buddha himself was gifted with polite address, distinct, not husky, suitable for conveying the relevant meaning.⁵⁴ Some of his disciples were experts in delivering attractive sermons.⁵⁵ Further, some of them have been declared as foremost among those who possess special qualities related to linguistic communication.

e.g.:

- Ven. Bhaddhiya for sweet voice
- Ven. Bhāradvāja for deep voice
- Ven. Puṇṇamantāniputta for teaching
- Ven. Mahākaccāyana for exposition
- Ven. Soṇakutikanna for clear utterance
- Ven. Kumārakāssapa for brilliant expression
- Ven. Mahākoṭṭhita for logical analysis
- Ven. Nandaka and Ven. Kappina for admonition⁵⁶

The proper understanding of Dhamma was of great importance on the part of the disciples because misunderstanding of it inevitably led to confusion among them.

Therefore, once the Buddha advised Ven. Cunda not to quarrel over the doctrines but to compare meaning with meaning and phrase with phrase so as to come to a right conclusion.⁵⁷ In this regard Prof. K.N. Jayatilleke observes that “the failure to understand the limitations of language. Which employs static concepts to describe dynamic processes” of the world is partly responsible for misunderstanding of the reality.⁵⁸ This was the reason for the Buddha's great emphasis on the nature and usage of language.

Language, though sometimes causes misunderstanding, is of great benefit if properly used with awareness of its true nature. The Buddha has stated this dual nature of language as follows:

“Just, Citta, as from a cow comes milk, and from the milk curds and from the curds butter, and from the butter ghee, and from the ghee junket; but when it is milk it is not called curds, or butter, or ghee, or junket; and when it is curds it is not called by any of the other names: and so on. Just so, Citta, when any one of the three modes of personality is going on, it is not called by the name of the other. For these, Citta, are merely names, expressions, turns of speech, designations in common use in the world. And of these a Thatagata (one who has won the truth) makes use indeed, but is not led astray by them.⁵⁹ Commenting on the above discourse K.N. Jayatilleke says that “the Buddha uses the term *attapatilābha* to describe these states but does not assume the existence of an entity or entities corresponding to the word “atta” within one's person or body”. And again he says: “At the stage when milk has turned into any of these states it cannot be called by any other name than the name appropriate to describe each state. To this extent one cannot overstep convention. Nor should one assume that each of these names signifies an entity within the changing process”.⁶⁰ In essence, though the terms such as curd, butter, ghee etc. refer to the same milk we cannot reject them when we deal with them in our day-to-day life. On the other hand we should not be attached to those terms thinking that they refer to separate things when we try to understand reality by means of language or convention. Referring to the same passage the translator describes the function of language in relation to reality as “There are a number of qualities that, when united, make up a personality always changing. When the change has reached a certain point, it is convenient to change the designation, the name by which the personality is known just as in the case of the products of the cow. But the abstract form is only a convenient form of expression.⁶¹ In the Pāli Nikāyas we find mostly such clarifications of the limitations of the various expressions of language. Once we understand its limitations we can use it cautiously. This becomes evident in the *Araṇavibhaṅgasutta*, where the Buddha advises the monks not to affect to affect the dialects of the country side and not to deviate from recognized parlance.

“When it is said; “One should not affect the dialect of the countryside, one should not deviate from recognized parlance”, in reference to what is it said? And what, monks, is affectation of the dialect of the countryside and what is departure from recognized parlance “ In this case, monks, in different districts they know the different words *pāti... pātta... vittha... sarāva... dhāropa... pona... piṣīla...* all the terms refer to the same object “bowl” . Thus as they know the word as this or that in these various districts so does a

person, obstinately clinging to it and adhering to it, explain: "This indeed is the truth, all else is falsehood'. Thus, monks, is affectation of the dialect of the country side and departure from recognized parlance. And what, monks, is non affectation if the dialect of the countryside and non departure from recognized parlance ? In this case, monks, in different districts they know the different words: pāti... yet although they know the word as this or that in these various districts a person does not cling to it but explains: These venerable ones definitely express it thus, This, monks, is non affectation of the dialect of the countryside and non departure from recognized parlance. When it is said. One should not affect the dialect of the countryside, one should not deviate from recognized parlance, it is said in reference to this." ⁶²

Prof. Kalupahana points out two important facts regarding language as revealed by the above passage.

- i. "recognition of the kinship of words, based on usage rather than on simple etymology adopted by the grammarians
- ii. language drift which is a repudiation of the absolute structures of language that are supposed to be revealed by linguistic analysis"⁶³

Commenting on the same passage further he says that the Buddha's attitude towards language focuses on a midway position between strict adherence (abhinivesa) to it and transgression of its common usage. Because of this liberal attitude of the Buddha towards language, his disciples concentrated more on hermeneutical problems.⁶⁴ The Buddha's permission for his disciples to use their own languages sakāyanirutti in dissemination the teachings⁶⁵ is also relevant to the above point.

Another important fact regarding the early Buddhist attitude to language was the emphasis on contextual interpretation rather than literary meaning. The conception of two kinds of discourses, (neyyattha) the discourses which need explanation and (nītattha)⁶⁶ which need no explanation points to the fact that a particular statement should be understood with reference to its context but not necessarily on etymology. The contextual interpretation of statements prohibits the innovations and refers to the current usage. This might have been one of the reasons for categorizing the Buddha's sermons according to various modes of expression. Some of them can be cited from the commentarial literature as follows:

- saṅkhittā dhammadesanā – concise sermon
- vitthāradhammadesanā -detailed sermon
- sāmuḅbhāsiḅkā dhammadesanā – exalted sermon
- ānupubbikadhammadesanā – graduated sermon
- nippariyāyadesanā -non discursive sermon
- pariyāyadesanā -discursive sermon ⁶⁷

As stated above, language, according to Buddhism is not an absolute phenomenon as recognized in the Brahmanical tradition. It had mainly a psychological basis ven.

Nanananda says that the term “papañcasaññasāṅkhā” in the Madhupiṇḍikasutta refers to language or convention⁶⁸ The discourse clarifies the arising of “papañcasaññasāṅkhā” as follows:

“Visual consciousness, brethren, arises because of eye and material shapes; the meeting of the three is sensory impingement; because of sensory impingement arises feeling; what one feels one perceives, one reasons about; what one reasons about, one turns into ‘papañca’ papañceti; what one turns into “papañca”, due to that “papañcasaññasāṅkhā” assail him in regard to material shapes cognizable by the eye, belonging to the past...⁶⁹

According to the above description conventions papañcasaññasāṅkhā come into being as a result of the psychological process caused by contact between senses and their respective objects. Concepts that arise in consciousness are communicated through words and sentences in a given language. So language necessarily represents thoughts which are considered as meanings.

With regard to the canonical background of the conception of paññatti, the term “sammuti” also is worthy of consideration. As Prof. Y. Karunadasa states both the terms “Sammuti” and “paññatti” are often used in the early Buddhist discourses more or less synonymously to mean things whose reality is based on conventions.⁷⁰ Conventions vary in nature owing to various causes and conditions. So the enlightened beings do not become attached to them but use them cautiously.⁷¹

Conclusion

Despite the fact that language has limitations in the process of the realization of truth, Buddhism further emphasizes its usefulness by including language as one of the four branches of logical analysis. They are as follows: Atthapaṭisambhidā–discrimination of meaning, Dhammapaṭisambhidā–discrimination of ideas, Niruttapaṭisambhidā–discrimination of language, Paṭibhānapaṭisambhidā–discrimination of perspicuity⁷², The forgoing observation reveals that the conception of language paññatti which evolved as a theory of language in the post canonical exegetical literature has a close relationship with the early Buddhist conception of communication.

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Determinants of Internship Satisfaction: Study of the Management Undergraduates of a Leading State University in Sri Lanka

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Abstract:

Internship training has become an integral part of management degree programs offered in state and private universities in Sri Lanka. Even though the academic world focuses on internship training, a little attention has been given to examine the internship satisfaction. However, the internship satisfaction considered a critical factor in creating the desired graduate. Therefore, the current study attempts to examine, the determinants of internship satisfaction of commerce and management undergraduates providing the evidence from a leading state university in Sri Lanka. In addition to that, this study intends to contribute to filling the literature gap by investigating the associations between the determinants: university support; job characteristics; working environment; and the contextual factors with the internship satisfaction. Hence, this was a quantitative, cross-sectional study in which primary data were collected through a standard questionnaire distributed as an online google form to a sample of 237 final year undergraduates of the University of Kelaniya, Sri Lanka selected via the simple random sampling technique. Correlation and simple regression analysis were used to test the advanced hypotheses with the aid of SPSS and Excel. Findings reveal a significant positive impact of university support, job characteristics, working environment, and contextual factors on internship satisfaction of management undergraduates in the context. Accordingly, it is concluded that, if there is satisfaction in any of these four factors (university support, job characteristics, working environment, and contextual factors) the interns will be retained in that organization. The study results underlined that, if the right and preferred methodologies are being adopted in internships, interns will be able to obtain a greater level of exposure from their internships. Furthermore, this study raises the need for stakeholders to look at the determinants of internship satisfaction in a more serious and holistic approach.

Keywords: *Contextual factors, Internship satisfaction, Job characteristics, University support, Working environment*

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Introduction

One of the goals of the Ministry of Higher Education, Sri Lanka is to improve the employability of graduates. However, currently the job market faces difficulty in absorbing the rising number of graduates who are seeking employment. One of the main reasons behind this issue includes the lack of working experience among university graduates and the misconception that these graduates have no enough capability to suit the market demand (Jean, Kawai, Rong, Chi & Yin, 2012). As a result of that, internship programs have been included in the curriculum of higher education providers and have been made a compulsory requirement for graduation in universities and many other higher education institutions in Sri Lanka.

Though the undergraduates possess a significant level of knowledge sometimes they are unable to apply that knowledge into practical problems and situations. Some graduates perceive that their education is not enough for them to enter into the corporate world (Maskooki, Rama & Raghunandan, 1998 as cited in Gupta, Burns & Schiferl, 2010). Hence, in most of the degree programs it is compulsory for the undergraduates to attend an internship before the completion of their course module as it adapts the undergraduates to the corporate world. The theory knowledge itself is not enough, so that, the experiential education becomes mandatory for undergraduates. One form of experiential education facilitated by the universities to fill this gap is the internship programs. Internships provide an adequate amount of practical knowledge on businesses for management undergraduates (Gupta, Burns & Schiferl, 2010).

On one hand, companies expect from the graduates, the ability to apply subject knowledge in the business world practically before they come into the corporate world (Arts, *et al*, 2006 as cited in Dabke, 2015). On the other hand, educational institutes face the challenge of developing the skills needed to prepare university students for employment. Undergraduate students are enriched with the knowledge gained from their degree programs. Nevertheless, students must have the soft skills to solve practical problems to meet the challenges of the modern business environment. An internship with academic knowledge facilitates the creation of the perfect graduate who can cope with the problems of the practical business world. An internship is defined as: "an opportunity to integrate the work-related experience into graduate education by participating in scheduled and supervised work" (Gault, *et al*, 2010 as cited in Dabke, 2015). Having an internship training is an advantage for undergraduates and it enriches their experience with the real business world.

However, the essence of a successful internship relies on the level of internship satisfaction. Internship satisfaction is defined as a set of psychological attitudes towards the work done by the intern. Satisfaction with the internship depends on the correspondence of the outcome of the work with the intern's internal needs (Staribratov, 2019).

Students who have had a satisfactory internship experience have a positive attitude towards the university in which they have studied and the future job search process

(Paulins, 2008). Increasing satisfaction among interns will improve the university student and benefit the host companies as well; working with a greater commitment to companies that give internship training, Decrease in absenteeism rate (Dabke, 2015).

The leading factors that the researcher-led to study this issue were: there are very few studies have been done on internship satisfaction until recently, as an undergraduate and intern it is very interesting to study about this area and, this is a timely issue and should study about this soon because the internship effectiveness and internship future career progress depends on the level of internship satisfaction (as cited in Dissanayaka, 2016). This is a problem that occurs frequently. So, the situation of this issue is not like a one-time occurring and disappearing problem. That is why this should be studied. For this research problem, there is no comprehensive solution, and the evidence available in existing literature is not consistent. This inconsistency in extant literature led to conduct this research and investigate further about this scenario.

There is a paucity of research on internship satisfaction; especially in developing countries (D'Abate, Youndt & Wenzel, 2009; Jean, *et al*, 2012). Since Sri Lanka is in the category of developing countries, it is expected that this study will fill the mentioned gap to a certain extent. To date, no studies have been conducted to elucidate individual satisfaction with their internship experiences in the Faculty of Commerce and Management Studies, University of Kelaniya. So, there is a contextual gap as well. Further, policy decisions and guidelines in state universities become a timely necessity for effective and satisfactory implementation of internships to achieve the desired results through internships (Dissanayaka, 2016).

Problem of the Study

The number of unemployed graduates in Sri Lanka is increasing day by day. The unemployment rate is high, especially among skilled young people. Lack of proper practical training or shortcomings in practical training is one of the main reasons of Sri Lankan unemployed graduates which hinders the access to the job market. Eradicating graduate unemployment has become a timely necessity by encouraging institutional participation in effective internship trainings. Successful solutions to this graduate unemployment problem cannot be achieved through unsatisfactory internship trainings. Considering all these factors it seems, it has become a timely necessity to find out what causes the internship satisfaction in internship training (Jean, *et al*, 2012). However, only a very few studies have been conducted in the domain of internship satisfaction (Jean, *et al*, 2012). Having considered the above reported background information the below research question is raised in the current study.

What are the significant determinants of internship satisfaction of the undergraduates of the Faculty of Commerce and Management Studies, University of Kelaniya, Sri Lanka?

Objectives of the Study

General Objective

The general objective of this study is to identify the significant determinants of internship satisfaction among the undergraduates in the Faculty of Commerce and Management Studies, University of Kelaniya. Further, the following specific objectives were established to be achieved in the current study.

Specific Objectives

- i. To assess the effect of university support on internship satisfaction of undergraduates.
- ii. To assess the effect of job characteristics on internship satisfaction of undergraduates.
- iii. To assess the effect of the working environment on internship satisfaction of undergraduates.
- iv. To assess the effect of contextual factors on internship satisfaction of undergraduates.

Significance of the Study

Internship satisfaction of commerce and management undergraduates of the University of Kelaniya has not been studied before in a scientific research study. So, on one hand, that is why this is a unique study. Content and the Context are also new. From that angle, this study is new. Bridging that gap in the content and the context of this study will provide valuable insights at the end. And upon which future researchers, consultants, trainers, business analysts, and policymakers can take respective decisions in the context.

Since the University of Kelaniya is one of the premier institutes of management education in Sri Lanka, this research is expected to be useful in enhancing the quality and satisfaction of future internships at the University of Kelaniya. Further, this study will be useful for other universities that have internships to effectively develop and maintain their internship programs. This will guide for universities to direct students to get the training from companies that have high internship satisfaction. The university will be able to establish relationships with top companies and further strengthen existing relationships by sending undergraduates to internship programs and providing an effective service to those companies. Moreover, this research will be useful for future researchers as a reference if they wish to do related research.

Furthermore, the results of this research will enable organizations to attract, recruit, and retain highly skilled interns. Companies can take steps to provide a satisfying learning experience for the interns and increase their productivity. Knowing how students' satisfaction with the internship they offer will be useful for the HRM professionals to

get an idea of how to redesign and improve their internship program structure to retain outstanding interns as permanent employees in the future. The study is expected to serve as a preliminary step towards a broader discourse on internship satisfaction.

Literature Review

Internship Satisfaction

According to Staribratov (2019), satisfaction with internship training is a set of psychological attitudes that the intern has in his/her mind about his or her activities. Labour activity motivation and labour satisfaction play a significant role in the profession's adaptation and self-identification process. The job satisfaction of the interns depends on the extent to which the results of the work correspond to the needs of the interns. There are various ideas in the scientific literature that describe the level of satisfaction with internship training among young and under-experienced newcomers. However, most of them have incorporated their ideas into the following trends:

As mentioned by Gupta, Burns, and Schiferl (2010) it is evident that students who have gained more work experience through internship training will benefit more when finding a job and building a career. They are more likely to stay in the same company where they interned. The opportunity to find employment within the internship training company itself plays a huge role in increasing student internship satisfaction (Staribratov, 2019). Citing evidence from Staribratov (2019) Freeston *et al.*, (2007) mentioned that students who were treated by their host companies as part-time workers showed lower internship satisfaction.

Seyitoglu and Yirik (2015) assessed internship satisfaction among a sample of medical / hospitality students. They used five dimensions to see which of them contributed to the success of their internship. Those five dimensions were; payment during internship training, payments for overtime work, lack of overtime, fair management behaviour, and provide internship training throughout the internship period. Stansbie (2012) mentioned that there are nine factors which affect internship satisfaction. Those nine dimensions are, skill variety, task identity, task significance, autonomy, feedback from job, feedback from agents, dealing with others, pay and benefits receive from the internship. Citing evidence from Sovilla and Varty's (2004), Stansbie (2012) mentioned that, in terms of literature much attention has been paid to the studies related to the internship process and its connection to HR practice. There is little attention paid in the literature on internship satisfaction (D'Abate, Youndt & Wenzel, 2009). Having demonstrated a significant gap in published research in this research area, the purpose of this study is to identify and assess factors that contribute to internship satisfaction; especially in Sri Lankan context.

Moreover, this study examines internship satisfaction focusing on four main factors: university support, job characteristics, organizational environment, and the contextual factors.

University Support

Gryski, Johnson, and O'Toole (1987) found that strong administration of internship training programs and clear identification will increase the likelihood of success. The key to a satisfying internship program is to maintain regular contact with site supervisors and university supervisors, have regular visits, and interns to regularly consult their internship consultants. Citing evidence from Fagan and Wise (2007), Hussien and Lopa (2018) stated that in the event of unexpected problems in the course of the internship the university supervisors need the assistance of the University for Consultation.

Job Characteristics

Citing evidence from Steers and Porter (1991), D'Abate, Youndt, and Wenzel (2009) stated that job characteristics are a set of variables about the duties and tasks the employee does while he or she is employed. In this research job characteristics covers areas such as skill variety, task identity, task significance, autonomy, and feedback.

As stated by Wubuli (2009) skill variety is defined as the number of skills and different activities included in the job. Task identity is the degree to which an employee completes a task from beginning to end. The degree to which the job has an impact on people concerned is defined as task significance. Autonomy refers to how much freedom, independence a worker has, and how much space the employee is allowed to work at his or her discretion when planning and executing tasks. Feedback is defined as the extent to which direct information is provided to the employee in evaluating their performance.

Working Environment

In this study organizational environment includes areas such as main supervisor support, co-worker support, task clarity, learning opportunities, professional growth, and organization satisfaction (D'Abate, Youndt & Wenzel, 2009). Main supervisor support means the degree to which the site supervisor is supportive of interns and motivates them to be supportive of one another. Co-worker support is the extent to which interns and co-workers are friendly and supportive to each other. Task clarity is the extent to which clear instruction is given to the intern on how to do various jobs. Practical and theoretical knowledge he/she acquire after completing the internship programme successfully is defined as learning opportunities. The degree to which internship programme prepare university students to enter the world of work after graduation is defined as professional growth. The extent to which site management is satisfied with the internship learning, communication and attitude during internship is defined as the organization satisfaction (Hussien & Lopa, 2018).

Contextual Factors

According to the National Science Foundation, context is defined as “*the specific setting a program occurs in. This includes social, political, cultural, historical, and*

personal factors" (Jean, *et al*, 2012). D'Abate, Youndt, and Wenzel (2009) have introduced a number of contextual factors that have a significant impact on internship satisfaction. Those are pay, work hours, commute, and location. Citing evidence from Jean *et al.* (2012), Nelson (1994) introduced measuring factors of satisfaction from an individuals' work which are job security, co-workers and peers, supervisory support, and pay.

Development of Hypotheses

Smits (2006) studied how satisfied the students were with the quality of university supervisors' supervision by using students who had completed their internship training. Smits (2006) revealed that interns who received adequate university support had higher commitment and higher levels of satisfaction and those who did not receive adequate university support relatively had the lower commitment and lower satisfaction.

Citing evidence from Moghaddam (2011), Jean *et al.* (2012) stated how the effectiveness of the internship office of the educational institute helps the students who receive internship training. As revealed by the author majority of the interns have responded that the internship office has shown an observable effect on students' job searching and other support processes. The support given from the internship office of the school in an organized and timely manner was the main reason which is caused the interns to be satisfied. Jean *et al.* (2012) have assessed the impact of university support on undergraduate internship satisfaction using two key components including, faculty site visits and good communication with the faculty supervisor.

Based on the above evidence the following hypotheses can be advanced:

Hypothesis 1a: There is a significant relationship between university support and internship satisfaction of undergraduates

Hypothesis 1b: There is a significant impact of university support on internship satisfaction of undergraduates.

The better the match between the competencies and the job characteristics of the students, the higher the probability that internship training will be satisfactory (Lord, Sumrall & Sambandam, 2011). Citing evidence from Hackman and Oldham (1980), Jean *et al.* (2012) further discussed the Job Characteristics Model (JCM). This model describes the relationship between job characteristics and employee satisfaction, motivation, and performance. That is not only job outcomes, job satisfaction as well can be reduced or increased by changes in job characteristics. Skill variety, task identity, task significance, autonomy, and feedback are the five job dimensions that come under this model.

Reiner and Zhao (1999) mentioned that job characteristics is one of the main determinants of internship satisfaction. Citing evidence from Brown and Peterson (1993), Lord, Sumrall, and Sambandam (2011) found and revealed that job characteristics is one of the key factors in measuring internship satisfaction.

Paulins (2008) studied students' perceptions of task characteristics included in the internship and the relationship between task characteristics and job satisfaction. The results of his research revealed that employers will get the benefit of increasing the satisfaction of internship because employee productivity and loyalty are linked to job satisfaction. This study shares similar views on internship satisfaction and job satisfaction. D'Abate, Youndt, and Wenzel (2009) stated that according to further investigations the job characteristics model applies to permanent employment and internship training.

Accordingly, the following hypotheses are advanced:

Hypothesis 2a: There is a significant relationship between job characteristics and internship satisfaction of undergraduates.

Hypothesis 2b: There is a significant impact of job characteristics on internship satisfaction of undergraduates.

One of the features of the work environment, the opportunity to learn is an important determinant of internship satisfaction (D'Abate, Youndt & Wenzel, 2009). Citing evidence from Rothman (2003), D'Abate, Youndt, and Wenzel (2009) have studied about most and least favoured aspects among a sample of business school interns, and according to his study, he reported that students' open responses indicated that they preferred an internship that would provide significant learning opportunities. Moreover, Glisson and Durik (1998) found that supervision is significantly associated with internship satisfaction.

Further, D'Abate, Youndt, and Wenzel (2009) revealed that all the following factors namely internal satisfaction, having learning opportunities in the work environment, receiving good support from the supervisor, giving professional development opportunities, receiving co-workers support were found to be correlated with internship satisfaction.

Moreover, Nelson (1994) studied the impact of job dimensions, organizational environment, and its supportive relationships on internship satisfaction. Tarquin and Truscott (2006), found that the supervisory relationship and the internship satisfaction are intertwined. Furthermore, Hurst (2007) mentioned that the extent to which the guidance, encouragement, and mentoring of employees is done by the supervisor is defined as supervisory support. Citing evidence from Jean *et al.* (2012), Klee (2011) mentioned that employees who receive high levels of support from site supervisors report high levels of satisfaction with their internship training experience. As mentioned by Phoebe (2010) according to research conducted by using 113 interns, the effectiveness of supervision and task role clarity are considered as two organizational environment factors that increase the success of an internship.

Further, Moghaddam (2011) mentioned that students who have undergone an internship or are currently receiving an internship were motivated by the availability of site supervisors and staff to answer the internship issues, helping their work and treating them as same as members of their group. Investigations have shown that the satisfaction

that university students receive from working as interns collaboratively with colleagues in companies is greater than the satisfaction they gain from academic work (Jean *et al*, 2012).

Based on the above-mentioned evidence the following hypotheses are advanced:

Hypothesis 3a: There is a significant relationship between the working environment and the internship satisfaction of undergraduates.

Hypothesis 3b: There is a significant impact of working environment on internship satisfaction of undergraduates.

It was revealed that flexible work hours lead to internship satisfaction and the need to travel a far distance to reach the workplace leads to internship dissatisfaction (Rothman, 2003 as cited in D'Abate, Youndt & Wenzel, 2009). The location of the internship training is also another contextual factor that may contribute to the internship satisfaction. As mentioned by Fisher and Show (1994) research on relocation and job attitudes has raised questions about location. Getting to work in a workplace with friends and family, get the opportunity to join a community, receiving a familiar place as the location are some of the examples for that (Fisher & Shaw, 1994).

Pay is another key factor that affects internship satisfaction. Elickson (2002) studied what happens to an internship satisfaction with the amount of pay if the payment is made during the internship. According to Gerhart (1987), there is a significant relationship between pay and satisfaction among young workers.

Beebe, Blaylock, and Sweetser (2009) were done an online survey using the Job Descriptive Index (JDI) and Job in General Scale (JIG) to analyse job satisfaction of internship students' experiences. The results showed that paid internships have higher internship satisfaction rates and unpaid internships have lower internship satisfaction rates than that. According to the above examples from the literature, it can be concluded that pay affects internship satisfaction. There is evidence from the literature that internship satisfaction was high among the interns who worked in the financially paid institutions (Beebe, Blaylock & Sweetser, 2009; Phoebe, 2010; Jean, *et al*, 2012). Klee (2011) stated that the financial allowance given to interns by their host companies plays a significant role in internship satisfaction (as cited in Jean *et al.*, 2012).

According to the above factors following hypotheses are advanced:

Hypothesis 4a: There is a significant relationship between contextual factors and internship satisfaction of undergraduates.

Hypothesis 4b: There is a significant impact of contextual factors on the internship satisfaction of undergraduates.

The above hypothesized relationships are depicted in figure 01; conceptual framework of the study.

Methodology

Research Design

In the current study hypothetico-deductive approach was adopted as it was a model-testing study. This study falls into the category of quantitative research. This type of research would be descriptive research because it examines the 'what' question. This is a field study and the level of researcher's interference is minimal in this research. A cross-sectional time frame is used in this study. There is no repetition of primary data collection. This study is conducted using the survey method. The unit of analysis in the current study is at the individual level.

Population and the Sample

The target population of the study is final year commerce and management undergraduates in the University of Kelaniya. Currently, there are five departments under the Faculty of Commerce and Management Studies. They are Accountancy, Commerce and Financial Management, Finance, Human Resource Management, and Marketing Management. The total population of Commerce and Management Undergraduates from the University of Kelaniya who had undergone an internship is 595 students. The sampling frame of this study is the list of final year undergraduates in the faculty of commerce and management studies in the University of Kelaniya who have undergone an internship up to date. According to the Morgan table, the sample size is determined as 234 observations.

Sampling Technique

As the total number of elements in the population is known to the researchers probability sampling is used in this study. As the population is known, the used sampling technique in this study was the simple random sampling.

Measurement Scales of Variables

Factors Affecting Internship Satisfaction

Adopting the measurement scale developed by Hussein & Lopa (2018) university support was assessed through three dimensions; university supervisor, internship coordinator, and the fair credit requirements. Job characteristics were assessed through five dimensions; skill variety, task identity, task significance, autonomy, and feedback. The working environment was assessed through six dimensions; main supervisor, co-workers, task clarity, learning opportunities, professional growth, and organization satisfaction. Contextual factors were assessed through four dimensions; pay, work hours, commute, and location. The data collection instrument for this study was a web-based survey which was adapted and revised from previous internship studies (Gupta, Burns & Schiferl, 2010; Hussein & Lopa, 2018; Jean *et al*, 2012). Interns were asked to rate their level of agreement for the 49 items in response to the question: to what extent interns agree or disagree with each statement? On a five-point Likert scale anchored at 1 = Strongly

Disagree and 5 = Strongly Agree. Items 1-11 assessed the university support, items 12-26 assessed the job characteristics, items 27-38 assessed the working environment, and items 39-45 assessed the contextual factors.

Internship Satisfaction (DV)

Internship satisfaction is a unidimensional variable and it was assessed using the adopted scales taken from Hussein and Lopa (2018). Four items were used to measure the construct asking participants about the extent to which they were satisfied with their internship as a whole. Five Point Likert scale format is used to measure the items ranging from 1= Strongly Disagree to 5= Strongly Agree as in the original scale. Sample items include: ‘Generally speaking, I was very satisfied with my internship’ (Internship Satisfaction).

Data Collection

Primary data were collected using a self-administered questionnaire through an online questionnaire survey designed as a google form. The questionnaire comprised of two sections. Section one includes four close-ended questions to capture the demographics of the respondents included: gender, age, monthly compensation, and internship duration. Section two of the questionnaire comprises the items taken from standard measurement scales to assess the independent variable and the dependent variable of the study and one open-ended question was given at the end to capture other opinions and suggestions of the respondents other than the things given in the standard measurement scale.

Data Analysis Techniques

To ensure the reliability of the study, reliability statistics were used. With the aim of ensuring the construct validity, validity statistics were applied to analyse the data.

Figure 01: Conceptual Framework of the Study
Source: Authors, 2021

Descriptive statistics were used in the study to explain the sample composition. Normality and linearity statistics were generated as well to analyse the primary data set of the study. With the aim of testing the hypotheses of the study correlation statistics and regression statistics were adopted. Correlation statistics were used to measure the strength of association between variables of the study and regression statistics were used to measure the impact or the coefficient of partial determination.

Data Analysis and Results

Response Rate

Out of 280 questionnaires distributed in online mode, 240 respondents were responded. But, out of those 240 respondents responded 3 responses were discarded because those 3 respondents had put the same rating for all the Likert scale items. Hence, the researcher considered and entered only those 237 fully completed responses into SPSS. The response rate was 85.7%. But, the effective rate of response after discarding ineligible respondents from the sample (Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill, 2009) was 84.6% which is also beyond the accepted margin of 33% in social research.

Sample Composition

The composition of the study sample is depicted in table 1.

Table 1: Sample Composition (N=237)

Gender	Male	81	34.2%
	Female	156	65.8%
Age	22 Years	3	1.3%
	23 Years	103	43.5%
	24 Years	81	34.2%
	25 Years	42	17.7%
	Above 25 Years	8	3.4%
Department of Study	Department of Human Resource Management	54	22.8%
	Department of Accountancy	54	22.8%
	Department of Commerce and Financial Management	73	30.8%
	Department of Finance	28	11.8%
	Department of Marketing Management	28	11.8%
Monthly Compensation	No Compensation	7	3.0%
	Less than Rs.5000	5	2.1%
	Rs.5000 - Rs.10000	84	35.4%
	Rs.10000 - Rs.15000	106	44.7%
	More than Rs.15000	35	14.8%

Duration of the Internship	Less than 3 months	5	2.1%
	3 – 6 months	46	19.4%
	6 – 9 months	101	42.6%
	9 – 12 months	54	22.8%
	More than 1 year	31	13.1%

Source: Analysed Data, 2021

Reliability Statistics

Internal consistency statistics were used to ensure the reliability of measurement scales. As recommended by Nunnally (1978) construct reliability and dimension reliability were assessed using the Cronbach's Alpha coefficient. Cronbach's Alpha values of all the variables are greater than 0.7 indicating that the multi-item scale is reliable. Cronbach's Alpha values of all the dimensions are greater than 0.5 as shown in table 2. TS3 (*Task Significance*) item is removed since it has a weak reliability coefficient. Except TS3 item, all the other items have played a significant role in conceptualizing the respective constructs.

Table 2: Reliability Statistics

Constructs	Dimension/s	No. of Items	Cronbach's Alpha
University Support (Cronbach's Alpha = 0.950)	University Supervisor	06	0.940
	Internship Coordinator	03	0.889
	Credit Requirements	02	0.910
Job Characteristics (Cronbach's Alpha = 0.927)	Skills Variety	03	0.637
	Task Identity	03	0.798
	Task Significance	02	0.916
	Autonomy	03	0.714
	Feedback	03	0.944
Working Environment (Cronbach's Alpha = 0.933)	Main Supervisor	02	0.883
	Co- workers	02	0.505
	Task Clarity	02	0.945
	Learning Opportunities	02	0.858
	Professional Growth	02	0.830
	Organization Satisfaction	02	0.954
Contextual Factors (Cronbach's Alpha = 0.912)	Pay	02	0.964
	Work Hours	02	0.898
	Location	02	0.918
	Commute	01	-
Internship Satisfaction	Internship Satisfaction	04	0.839

Source: Analysed Data, 2021

Validity Statistics

Sampling adequacy was ensured through the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) Measure and the sphericity was ensured through Bartlett's test respectively. As the KMO coefficient is greater than 0.7 for all the variables, and the Sig. value is less than 0.05, statistically it is claimed that the study sample of 237 observations is adequate enough to proceed with Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA). Sampling adequacy is significant in this study as results indicate that sufficient correlations exist among the variables to proceed. Results of the KMO and Bartlett's test are given in table 3.

Table 3: Results of the KMO and Bartlett's test

		University Support	Job Characteristics	Working Environment	Contextual Factors	Internship Satisfaction
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy		0.932	0.908	0.910	0.802	0.789
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	2442.652	3315.981	2597.379	1462.097	611.062
	df	55	91	66	21	6
	Sig.	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000

Source: Analysed Data, 2021

As recommended by Hair *et al.*, (2010) Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings (ESSL Cum %) of all the dimensions are greater than 50% and the item Factor Loading (FL) values are above the threshold limit of 0.5. Therefore, statistically the construct validity is ensured. Validity statistics of Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings and the item Factor Loading values are given in table 4.

Table 4: Validity Statistics [Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA)]

Construct/s	Dimension/s	No. of Items	Lowest FL	Highest FL	ESSL Cum %
University Support	University Supervisor	06	0.855	0.913	77.183
	Internship Coordinator	03	0.892	0.917	81.795
	Credit Requirements	02	0.959	0.959	92.038
Job Characteristics	Skills Variety	03	0.639	0.883	64.567
	Task Identity	03	0.668	0.931	71.328
	Task Significance	02	0.961	0.961	92.351
	Autonomy	03	0.587	0.944	70.053
	Feedback	03	0.935	0.957	89.936

Working Environment	Main Supervisor	02	0.946	0.946	89.490
	Co-workers	02	0.836	0.836	69.961
	Task Clarity	02	0.974	0.974	94.811
	Learning Opportunities	02	0.937	0.937	87.729
	Professional Growth	02	0.925	0.925	85.551
	Organization Satisfaction	02	0.978	0.978	95.604
Contextual Factors	Pay	02	0.983	0.983	96.549
	Work Hours	02	0.953	0.953	90.814
	Location	02	0.962	0.962	92.536
	Commute	01	-	-	-
Internship Satisfaction	Internship Satisfaction	04	0.581	0.932	71.689

Source: Analysed Data, 2021

Descriptive Statistics

Mean and Standard deviation (SD) are the two basic measures of descriptive statistics widely used in social science research. Statistically, Skewness and Kurtosis measure the relative size of the two tails of the distribution and the extent of probability in the tails respectively. The values are often compared to the Kurtosis of the normal distribution which is equal to 3. Mean, Standard deviation, Skewness and Kurtosis values of the constructs in the current research model are depicted in table 5.

Table 5: Descriptive Statistics

Construct/s	N	Mean	SD	Skewness	Kurtosis
University Support	237	4.0564	0.59859	-0.336	0.617
Job Characteristics	237	3.9759	0.63594	-0.467	0.459
Working Environment	237	3.9944	0.62354	-0.463	0.325
Contextual Factors	237	3.4461	0.83493	-0.002	-0.497
Internship Satisfaction	237	3.9357	0.76699	-0.710	0.253

Source: Analysed Data, 2021

Testing for Multivariate Assumptions

The primary data set was tested for multivariate assumptions including the test for normality, test for linearity, and the test for outliers before continuing with hypotheses testing.

Testing for Outliers

The dependent variable of the study; internship satisfaction was checked for

outliers using box plots. According to figure 02 - box plot, there are no outliers found in the dependent variable.

Figure 02: Box-plot
Source: Analysed Data, 2021

Testing for Normality

If the value of the Skewness and Kurtosis in the variables falls between -3 and +3, the distribution is said to be normally distributed. According to Skewness and Kurtosis values given in table 5 the dependent variable; internship satisfaction is said to be approximately normally distributed.

Figure 03: Histogram
Source: Analysed Data, 2021

Moreover, according to figure 3 - histogram with the normal curve, the dependent variable; Internship Satisfaction is said to be approximately normally distributed.

Testing for Linearity

According to the ANOVA output given in table 6, the value sig. of deviation from linearity in the constructs of university support and internship satisfaction is 0.671 which is greater than 0.05. Thus, it could be concluded that there is a linear relationship between the constructs of university support and internship satisfaction.

Table 6: Linearity Statistics - University support and internship satisfaction

			Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Internship Satisfaction * University Support	Between Groups	(Combined)	59.172	27	2.192	5.750	.000
		Linearity	50.695	1	50.695	133.007	.000
		Deviation from Linearity	8.477	26	.326	.855	.671
	Within Groups		79.659	209	.381		
	Total		138.831	236			

Source: Analysed Data, 2021

As shown in table 7 the value sig. of deviation from linearity in the ANOVA output in the constructs of job characteristics and internship satisfaction is 0.138 which is greater than 0.05. Thus, it appears there is a linear relationship between the constructs of job characteristics and internship satisfaction.

Table 7: Linearity Statistics - Job characteristics and internship satisfaction

			Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Internship Satisfaction * Job Characteristics	Between Groups	(Combined)	99.872	34	2.937	15.230	.000
		Linearity	91.575	1	91.575	474.814	.000
		Deviation from Linearity	8.297	33	.251	1.304	.138
	Within Groups		38.959	202	.193		
	Total		138.831	236			

Source: Analysed Data, 2021

The value sig. of deviation from linearity between the constructs of the working environment and internship satisfaction in the ANOVA output given in table 8 is 0.078 which is greater than 0.05. Thus, it could be stated that there is a linear relationship between the constructs of the working environment and internship satisfaction.

Table 8: Linearity Statistics - Working environment and internship satisfaction

			Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Internship Satisfaction * Working Environment	Between Groups	(Combined)	94.510	32	2.953	13.594	.000
		Linearity	84.913	1	84.913	390.835	.000
		Deviation from Linearity	9.597	31	.310	1.425	.078
	Within Groups		44.321	204	.217		
	Total		138.831	236			

Source: Analysed Data, 2021

According to table 9, the value sig. of deviation from linearity in the ANOVA output between the constructs of contextual factors and internship satisfaction is 0.137, which is greater than 0.05. Therefore, it could be concluded that there is a linear relationship between aforesaid constructs.

Table 9: Linearity Statistics - Contextual factors and internship satisfaction

			Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Internship Satisfaction * Contextual Factors	Between Groups	(Combined)	63.991	21	3.047	8.754	.000
		Linearity	54.423	1	54.423	156.345	.000
		Deviation from Linearity	9.567	20	.478	1.374	.137
	Within Groups		74.841	215	.348		
	Total		138.831	236			

Source: Analysed Data, 2021

Correlation Analysis

Building on the linear relationship found among the independent variables; university support, job characteristics, working environment, contextual factors, and the dependent variable; internship satisfaction, Pearson Correlation Coefficient was used to assess the strength of association among the constructs. Since the advanced hypotheses are non-directional, Sig. (2-tailed) the test was applied to test the significance of the correlation coefficient. Results of the correlation analysis are given in tables 10, 11, 12, and 13.

Table 10: Correlation Statistics - University support and internship satisfaction

		Internship Satisfaction	University Support
Internship Satisfaction	Pearson Correlation	1	.604**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	237	237

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Analysed Data, 2021

As shown in table 10, the Pearson correlation coefficient value between the above variables was calculated as 0.604. Since this value is positive and more than 0.5, it interprets that there is a strong positive correlation between university support and internship satisfaction. The correlation coefficient is significant at 0.01 level as Sig (2-tailed) is less than 0.01; which is 0.000. Hence, H1a is accepted.

Table 11: Correlation Statistics - Job characteristics and internship satisfaction

		Internship Satisfaction	Job Characteristics
Internship Satisfaction	Pearson Correlation	1	.812**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	237	237

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Analysed Data, 2021

As shown in table 11, a strong positive correlation is found between job characteristics and internship satisfaction ($r = 0.812$) which is statistically significant as Sig (2-tailed) (0.000) is less than the level of significance (0.01). Therefore, H₂a is accepted.

Table 12: Correlation Statistics - Working environment and internship satisfaction

		Internship Satisfaction	Working Environment
Internship Satisfaction	Pearson Correlation	1	.782**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	237	237

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Analysed Data, 2021

According to table 12, Pearson Correlation of 0.782 depicts a strong positive relationship between working environment and internship satisfaction. As the Sig

(2-tailed) value (0.000) is less than the significant value (0.01), the found correlation coefficient (0.782) is statistically significant. Therefore, H_3a is accepted.

Table 13: Correlation Statistics - Contextual factors and internship satisfaction

		Internship Satisfaction	Contextual Factors
Internship Satisfaction	Pearson Correlation	1	.626**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	237	237

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Analysed Data, 2021

According to the results of the Pearson correlation shown in table 13, there is a positive significant relationship between contextual factors and internship satisfaction of respondents. The Pearson correlation coefficient between the two variables is 0.626, which is positive. It shows that there is a strong positive correlation between contextual factors and internship satisfaction. Further, found relationship is statistically significant since Sig (2-tailed) value (0.000) is less than the significant value 0.01. Thus, there is statistical evidence to claim that contextual factors and internship satisfaction are significantly related. Hence, H_4a is accepted.

Regression Analysis

Linear regression analysis was done to test the hypotheses H_1b , H_2b , H_3b , and H_4b advanced to identify the impact of independent variables on the dependent variable. Results of the tests are given in table 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20, and 21.

Table 14: Regression Statistics - Effect of university support on internship satisfaction

R	0.604 ^a
R Square	0.365(36.5%)
Adjusted R Square	0.362
Standard Error	0.61241
Observations(N)	237
F	135.169
Sig.	0.000 ^b
Regression	Linear
Method	Enter

Source: Analysed Data, 2021

According to the results depicted in table 14, 36.5% (R Square = 0.365) of the variation of internship satisfaction could be significantly (Sig. = 0.000 which is less than 0.05) explained by the independent construct in the research model; university support. Further, as given in table 15, the marginal contribution of US (University Support) (0.774) in determining the effect on internship satisfaction is to be considered statistically significant (Sig. = 0.000) in the regression equation.

Table 15: Coefficients [Effect of university support on internship satisfaction]

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.795	.273		2.911	.004
	University Support	.774	.067	.604	11.626	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Internship Satisfaction

Source: Analysed Data, 2021

Thus, according to the regression results, H1b is accepted statistically claiming that there is a significant impact of university support on internship satisfaction.

Table 16: Regression Statistics - Effect of job characteristics on internship satisfaction

R	0.812 ^a
R Square	0.660(66%)
Adjusted R Square	0.658
Standard Error	0.44843
Observations(N)	237
F	455.393
Sig.	0.000 ^b
Regression	Linear
Method	Enter

Source: Analysed Data, 2021

According to table 16, R² equals 0.660 which means, when other factors remain constant; job characteristics have a 66% impact on internship satisfaction and the significant value of job characteristics is significant since the significant value of JC (Job Characteristics) is lower than the expected significant value of 0.05. When considering table 17, the marginal contribution of JC (0.980) in determining the effect on internship satisfaction is to be considered statistically significant (Sig. = 0.000) in the regression model.

Table 17: Coefficients [Effect of job characteristics on internship satisfaction]

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.041	.185		3	.22.824
	Job Characteristics	.980	.046	.812	21.340	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Internship Satisfaction

Source: Analysed Data, 2021

Thus, according to the regression results, H₂b is accepted statistically claiming that there is a significant impact of job characteristics on internship satisfaction.

Table 18: Regression Statistics - Effect of working environment on internship satisfaction

R	0.782 ^a
R Square	0.612(61.2%)
Adjusted R Square	0.610
Standard Error	0.47900
Observations(N)	237
F	370.089
Sig.	0.000 ^b
Regression	Linear
Method	Enter

Source: Analysed Data, 2021

According to the results depicted in table 18, 61.2% (R Square = 0.612) of the variation of internship satisfaction could be significantly (Sig. = 0.000 which is less than 0.05) explained by the independent construct in the research model, working environment. Further, as given in table 19, the marginal contribution of WE (Working Environment) (0.962) in determining the effect on internship satisfaction is to be considered statistically significant (Sig. = 0.000) in the regression equation.

Table 19: Coefficients [Effect of working environment on internship satisfaction]

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.093	.202		.461	.645
	Working Environment	.962	.050	.782	19.238	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Internship Satisfaction

Source: Analysed Data, 2021

Thus, according to the regression results, H₃b is accepted statistically claiming that there is a significant impact of working environment on internship satisfaction.

Table 20: Regression Statistics - Effect of contextual factors on internship satisfaction

R	0.626 ^a
R Square	0.392(39.2%)
Adjusted R Square	0.389
Standard Error	0.59932
Observations(N)	237
F	151.519
Sig.	0.000 ^b
Regression Method	Linear
	Enter

Source: Analysed Data, 2021

According to table 20, R^2 equals 0.392 which means, when other factors remain constant; contextual factors has a 39% impact on internship satisfaction and the significant value of contextual factors is significant since the significant value of CF (Contextual Factors) is lower than the expected significant value of 0.05. Further, when considering table 21, the marginal contribution of CF (0.575) in determining the effect on internship satisfaction is to be considered statistically significant (Sig. = 0.000) in the regression equation.

Table 21: Coefficients [Effect of contextual factors on internship satisfaction]

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.954	.166		11.793	.000
	Contextual Factors	.575	.047	.626	12.309	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Internship Satisfaction

Source: Analysed Data, 2021

Thus, according to the regression results, H4b is accepted statistically claiming that there is a significant impact of contextual factors on IS (Internship Satisfaction).

Discussion of Findings

According to the results of primary data analysis, all the hypotheses were accepted. There are some evidence from previous literature to prove that there is a significant impact of independent variables (US, JC, WE, CF) on the dependent variable (IS). The results of the study were intended to be used to acquire a better understanding of what are the determinants of internship satisfaction among Commerce and Management undergraduates. Through data analysis, it is found that there is a significant relationship

between independent variables; university support, job characteristics, working environment, contextual factors, and the dependent variable; internship satisfaction respectively. Further, it is found that there is a significant impact of independent variables; university support, job characteristics, working environment, contextual factors on dependent variable; internship satisfaction respectively. Analysis results showed that the biggest impact on internship satisfaction comes from job characteristics ($R^2 = 0.660$) and working environment factors ($R^2 = 0.612$). The results of the current study align with the previous studies which have done by various scholars.

Citing evidence from Jean *et al.* (2012), Klee (2011) found that, internship satisfaction is greatly influenced by the supportive relationship between the intern and the university supervisor. Further, Smits (2006) found that interns who did not receive adequate university support relatively had a lower commitment and lower satisfaction, and interns who received adequate university support had a higher commitment and higher levels of satisfaction. According to Jean *et al.* (2012), the support given from the university has a major impact on internship satisfaction.

According to the findings of, Lord, Sumrall and Sambandam (2011), the impact of job characteristics on internship satisfaction is high and a significant relationship is found between job characteristics and internship satisfaction. It is found that job characteristics is a main determinant of internship satisfaction (Reiner & Zhao, 1999 as cited by Jean *et al.*, 2012).

According to the study conducted by D'Abate, Youndt, and Wenzel (2009), working environment has identified as a key determinant which impacts on internship satisfaction. They have found a significant relationship between work environment characteristics and internship satisfaction as well. According to Gupta, Burns and Schiferl (2010), there are six factors that have an impact on internship satisfaction. They are a positive work environment, positive internship experience, new skills, communication skills, improved job prospects, and comfort of the work environment.

Citing evidence from D'Abate, Youndt and Wenzel (2009) Rothman (2003) found that there is a significant relationship between contextual factors and internship satisfaction. As mentioned by Gerhart (1987) there is a significant relationship between pay and satisfaction among young workers. According to a study done by Beebe, Blaylock, and Sweetser (2009), it is found that paid internships have higher internship satisfaction rates than unpaid internships.

Conclusion

Internship satisfaction is highly affected by job characteristics and working environment factors. Based on this finding it could be concluded that internship effectiveness is high in companies which have proper job characteristics (skill variety, task identity, task significance, autonomy, feedback) and more favourable working environment factors (main supervisor, co-workers, task clarity, learning opportunities,

professional growth, organization satisfaction) since internship satisfaction is high in those companies. If superiors share their personal experiences with interns, act as role models, and work collaboratively with their trainees, internship satisfaction will be high in such organizations. Having considered the findings reported in chapter four, the current study concludes by declaring that there is a tendency among interns to consider contextual factors. In companies with paid internships, interns work most preferentially than unpaid internship companies. Companies which are not providing compensation to their interns are unable to remain competitive in the market. Based on the findings reported in chapter four it could be concluded that, undergraduates are more likely to enter universities and institutes which offer high university support during their internship. If there is satisfaction in any of these four factors (university support, job characteristics, working environment, contextual factors) interns will be retained in that organization. If the right and preferred methodologies are being adopted in internships, interns will be able to obtain a greater level of satisfaction from their internship.

Recommendations

The university internship training coordinator and the university faculty office should make the information easily available and accessible to students. Moreover, they must ensure that they communicate this information clearly and systematically. So, it is recommended to hold internship orientation as a compulsory requirement in the internship process and hold it as frequently as needed to ensure standardization of information. It is recommended to assign more officers to handle students' grievances, inquiries, and paperwork processes. It is also important to have the support of university supervisors easily available for counselling as well as for resolving any issues that may arise while students are undergoing internships. There must be certain significance in the tasks assigned to them since the work they do has a direct impact on their internship satisfaction. Some employers do not give interns autonomy and freedom in doing their work. So, if possible, employers should give their trainees a certain degree of autonomy and freedom while doing their work. If superiors are willing to share their personal experiences with interns and if they act as role models to their interns, internship satisfaction and organizational commitment will be high in such organizations. So, it is recommended for employers to share their success stories with interns. They should share with interns an adequate explanation about the organization's core processes. Employers should reconsider the compensation and benefits they offer for their interns if they want to remain competitive in the market and it will avoid any forms of labour exploitation as well. It is recommended for employers to make their internship a structured one to make their trainees' internship experience a satisfactory one.

Limitations of the Study

The sample of the study is limited only to the Faculty of Commerce and Management Studies in the University of Kelaniya. Basically, in the research model researcher assumed that other factors remain constant. So, under assumptions researcher

checked the primary data set. So, that assumption itself is a limitation. It wasn't an easy task to collect the data during the Covid-19 pandemic situation in the country. The researcher used a Google Form to collect data from undergraduates since the university is closed during this period of time. Further, the researcher used approximation for normality and linearity as this is a quantitative study.

Directions for Future Research

If future researchers do research on the same theme, to overcome the limitations mentioned under 5.5 it is recommended to consider bigger samples including other national universities and private campuses without limiting to a particular university or institute. Future researchers better consider mediated and moderated effects and more longitudinal and qualitative inquiries to validate the findings of the current study. There are many more variables in extant literature which affect internship satisfaction. It is suggested to consider those factors as well in future research studies. Hopefully, this study would raise the levels of interest among scholars to conduct more studies regarding internship satisfaction. It is recommended for future researchers to focus their studies on how demographic factors affect internship satisfaction. Future researchers can focus their studies on whether an intern who has obtained satisfactory internship training at a company will become a satisfied permanent employee once he or she enters the real business world.

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Cascading systems fed by the an ancient Yodha Ela Canal in Anuradhapura

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Abstract:

The settlements existed before the creation of irrigation works, fulfilled their requirements of water through natural resources which were arranged according to the natural landscape settings. Anuradhapura old Yodha Ela coming under this study and well before its creation, the settlements spread in the Kala Oya Valley upper lands, fulfilled their water requirements through cascade systems right from the early historical period. According to the sloping of the terrain from the uppermost lands up to the lowermost lands, the cascade is a system made up of a network of village tanks. The problem of this research study is to establish as to why Yodha Ela was constructed later on through this zone although the *Kala Oya* valley uppermost lands received water from the cascade. The objective of the research study, is to examine the cascade which existed before the construction of the Yodha Ela, and the environmental and physiological factors that caused their structural changes. In order to justify the research objective, and during the data collection, GPS, study of aerial photographs, drawing up of plans, earth coring methods, and during data analysis the use of GIS, examination of soil profiles, calculation of the mean sea levels, and the like research methodologies were followed. As the result of this research, establishment of the spread of the village tanks in this zonal area before construction of the Yodha Ela, physical grouping of the cascade, establishment of the topographical landscape pattern of the cascade system, to build up the case that Yodha Ela is a facilitating component of the cascade systems, and the establishment of the functionality of the Yodha Ela and the cascade, was done. Even though in the previous researches, the originating water resources of the cascade system was done, their functionality, and classification of topographical patterns have not been done. But the manner in which the activities of the cascade changed with the early historic irrigation works have not been covered those previous studies. In this research, the structural pattern of cascade as an early water management methodology of the zonal area through which the Yodha Ela flowed and an understanding of the topographical landscape pattern accordingly, variations in the climatic factors, population density, agricultural works, and changes due to the variations in those factors, through the cascade and as a facilitating component the construction of the Yodha Ela during the early historic period, and parallel to those water management methodologies, migration of settlements from the uppermost to the lowermost zonal areas, which factors were established in this research study.

Keywords: *Water Management, cascade, Soil moisture, Groundwater, Topographical Pattern, Settlements*

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Introduction

According to the Sri Lanka district plan, bordering kekirawa and Anuradhapura districts which are within the North Central Province, Yodha Ela had been constructed. Its total linear elongation is 54 miles, and the width is 40 feet. Within the irrigation construction field, it can be cited as an exceptional quality creation. During the prehistoric period and the early historic period water management methods, and also the water management methods even after the construction of the Yodha Ela have together been networked from historical times, and with it functioning as such, altogether considered as a single Yodha Ela irrigation system. In this research, the cascade systems before the construction of the Yodha Ela, had to be introduced as a conceptual approach to the social background which was influential in the creation of Yodha Ela. As such, the water management methods used prior to the construction of Yodha Ela, and also the water requirements due to the complexities of issues in those contemporary settlements, leading to the factors in the construction of Yodha Ela, are the objectives of this research.

Applicable only to the Rajarata dry zone, and that can be identified only within one topographical environment, the concept of cascade system has been a subject of research receiving attention of both the local and foreign researchers. The conceptual research approach to the name 'cascade' has been received from following the functioning of the rapidly cascading streams in the rocky's mountain slope range of North America (Bandara, 1985). With a similar functionality found in the cascade system in the North Central Province of Sri Lanka, starting from the top of an undulating mountainous range, slowly but gradually growing in size flowing down a valley feeding the tank further downstream, and traversing a considerable distance, connecting a large pond or a tank or even smaller rivers in the lower elevations. In here, the functionality of the main waterfall is quite similar to the above mentioned cascading system, has been shown (Bandara, 1985). Dharmasena has tried to illustrate the cascade system from quite a different view point. "Based on a sustainable human intervention, water, soil, air, plant lives etc. in fulfilling the basic requirements of human and animal lives, become an organized biological resource base set within the dry zone geographical arena" (Dharmasenam, 2017: 01). What is apprehended from this approach is that the cascade has operated as a multi-faceted functionality.

Analysing of the human corporations from the systems theory point of view, the origination of sub-cultures like technology, societal culture, manufacturing processes, habits and rituals, the village tanks have been the basis for their formations. Centred on the tank, food security can be identified as one of the main production activities. This has been an activity paying due consideration on factors like the water, soil, technology, landscape, and agricultural products. After the prior historic period and as a result of man's entry into the agricultural period, an irrigation cultural society associated with a societal culture trend can be identified. The term "cascade" at academic level, first came into use in the book "**Small Tank and Food Security**" printed in the year 2000. In here,

the manner in which the village tank technology has influenced the water management in the food production process, traditional methodologies adopted in the agricultural works, present day village tank related issues and in order to control them, the sectors that also need to be developed, have been considered (Panabokke, 2000). The whole background formation in the development of the total irrigational culture centering the village tanks, has functioned as protecting the entire cascade system. The main purpose of these activities is food security. Since centring on the village tank is built up the entire cultural activities, they have human interventions both as tangible and intangible heritages. In later years, this term has been subjected to a much broader study in the book "Ellangavas for Environmentally based Development" (Tennakone, 2005). Also through the book "Urbanization in the Dry Zone of Sri Lanka", the Principles related to cascade have been analysed. In here, the topographical picture in the distribution of the cascade system, water flow, soil, and the influence of rainwater fall, have been analysed (Tennakone, 2005). Along with this principle of approach, within the eighties of the 20th century the functionality and the environmental friendliness of the cascade systems, a number of historic studies related to water management are cited among others (Ponnraja, 1982; Madduma Bandara, 1982, 1985; Abeysinghe 1982; Fernando, 1982; Karunanayake, 1983; Kariyawasam, 1984; Dharmasena, 1985; Tennakone, 1986; Alwis, 1986; Mendis, 1986 – 1989; Thilakasiri, 1986; Weerawardena, 1986) are important.

In the nineteen of the 20th Century, cascade with an international inclination has been studied, the International Water Management Institute has shown an interest in the scientific background of the tanks belonging to cascade for the development of the agricultural sector. Accordingly the establishment of the tanks, profile and nature of the tank, trends in their distribution have been studied at length (Panabokke, 1999). In this research on Rajarata, nine river clusters have been identified, and those water clusters have been grouped into 50 clusters, and have exposed 457 river valleys with cascades. Among these, the cascade belonging to river valleys, *Kala Oya*, *Moderagam Aaru*, *Malwathu Oya*, *Parangi Aaru*, *Maa Oya*, *Mii Oya*, *Yaan Oya*, *Koddikkaddu Aaru*, *Pankuulam Aaru* are important (Panabokke, 1999). Since the cascades between *Malwathu Oya* upper Valley and *Kala Oya* upper Valley have been exposed, and those facts have been included in this research study as a principle of approach. The said research study, although has drawn attention on the cascade, no attention has been paid on the sub-cascades. In this study however, sub-cascade between *kala Oya* and *Malwathu Oya* through which the Yodha Ela flows down, were exposed.

As the earliest period research on *Rajarata* cascades, research carried out on *Kadiragaama* and *Thoruwa* cascades are important. This study is a systematic research done on the tank systems that evolved parallel to the study on *Maaminiya Oya* and *Malwathu Oya* valley (Madduma Bandara, 1991). Cascade that originate from *Malwathu Oya* upper valley are bordering the *Kala Oya*, while cascades starting from the upper *Malwathu* valley are bordering the *Malwathu Oya* (Karunarathna, 2020). In here, the research approach is that when Yodha Ela is flowing through *Kala Oya* valley, construction of the

right embankment and when the same is flowing across *Malwathu Oya*, the construction of the left embankment. The two embankment's change of one and the same stream path when traversing through two valleys and the spread of the contour lines through revealing the pattern of the cascade profiles, the gradient of the terrain was established here.

Through the research paper titled "Scientific Background on some Traditional Methodologies of Lands and Water Management which were within the village tank system", the purpose and their functionality of built tanks/joined tanks or the associated tanks have been subjected to study (Bandara; Yatigamma; Paranavithana, 2010:1-10). The distribution of water in these cascades take place not only from across the upper lands to the lower lands, but take place also parallel to the associated tanks (Built tanks), has been shown by Brohier (Brohier, 1937). Cross or associated cascades are originated from a river or a tank or a hilltop. Much more has been subjected to study than the functionality of a cascade originated from a tank than the Yodha Ela cascade which is so special, since it is connected to a stream fed by a *mother tank* (first water). These cascade systems which were there even long before the Yodha Ela was created, although originated from a canal in the upper valley, construction of the Yodha Ela through this valley has been done in the ancient times as a step taken, in view of strengthening the functionality of the tanks in the system. Although the networking of a system of tanks has been introduced through a common concept of cascade, these village tanks at that times were considered as a show-piece that each of these tanks can be identified in a settlement zone. Dharmasena has illustrated this component as "*Tisbambe*" situated within the uppermost terrain of a tank with a higher gradient (Dharmasena, 2004:05).

In the settlements distribution where created irrigation works are functioning as a secondary system, some factors like the climate, water, and the environment are important (Bandaranayake, 2002:147-156). In the water management techniques associated with the water supply requirements of human settlements of the early historical period or that of the historical period prior to the construction of Yodha Ela, inefficiency of the water supply too may have been instrumental. For this, the climatic change, increase in the demand for land utilization, trends in the spread of settlements, and population density may have been instrumental. Through the research "Cascade Tank System and the Cultural Landscape of Sri Lanka", it has been shown that factors responsible in the spread of settlements in the topographical landscape pattern, and the related cultural landscape pattern, and human settlements around village tanks have been subjected to study (Bandaranayake, 2018:27). In here the scientific geographical landscape pattern that has been instrumental in the distribution of the tanks has been highlighted, and that the geo-pattern of the terrain where tanks in Sri Lanka have been constructed, is of crystalline granite, has been shown (*ibid*, 2018:27). This research which is drawing attention on the study of cascade cultural geo-landscape pattern, has classified the structural features into four categories. Viz. tanks constructed associating one stream path (single type), branched form stream paths (branch type), those connected with one or more connected in a linear way (linear type), single or cluster cascades (cluster type), those concentration around

a single epicentre (nucleous type) as cascades, could be identified (*ibid*, 2018:47). The spread of the cascade can be identified accordingly with the profile pattern of the water stream as a linear networking. The internal geophysical arrangement of those cascades built based on the Yodha Ela can be illustrated in two ways. That is, a linear networking distribution taking into consideration the horizontal spreading patterns, and the vertical spreading pattern according to the contours, epicentre, clusters, and linear cascades, can be established.

Attention has been paid to the steps that need to be taken in order to conserve the catchment areas among the cascade distribution zones and the feeder zones. Among them, the surface water flow control, evaporation control, ground water changes, agri water utilization methodologies are important (Dharmasena, 2002:10). As an important research in the study of cascades of the dry zone, Small Village Tank Systems of Sri Lanka: Their Evaluation Settings, Distribution and Essential Functions, is important (Panabokke, 2009). Village tank construction has started in the iron era (1500 - 500 BC), while in the historical period (500 - 300 BC) foundation for the large tank culture has been laid. Before the large tank culture, that the water management and settlements were in existence in the dry zone centred on village tanks, has been shown by Tennakone (Tennakone, 2005). Through the research paper "Small tank settlement in Sri Lanka" multipurpose activities which are the activities connected with the terrain variations and the like, and taking them into consideration, a classification as a village tank heritage, have been studied (Tennakone, 2000:03). The components of the activities connected to a village tank, and some factors in their utilization have been shown. Accordingly, the water catchment areas, *Kattakaduwa*, *Gasgommana*, canal pathways, human settlement terrain (*Tisbambe*), groundwater pathways, *Wev Pitiya*, tank forest, and the like are important (Tennakone, 2004:05). In studying the spread of the human settlements and their water requirement before the construction of the *Anuradhapura* Yodha Ela, this zone had been a human settlement ground and their water requirements had been fulfilled through cascades. The settlement spread of the downstream cascades which are fed by the Yodha Ela, and the upstream cascades which are separated from the primary activities, have been studied.

Nicholas shows that the human settlements first appeared in the B.C era in association with the village tanks in the dry zone areas (Nicholas, 1959: 75). During the 2nd century, increasing the water capacity of the existing village tanks centralizing on the household activities, they had to construct larger tanks sufficient for their agricultural works (Panabokke, 2004:22). In addition to this practice, the migration of settlements into lowland areas has occurred along with the distribution of water to different areas largely through the network of canal pathways of the agri technology. As a result of this, even though Yodha Ela up to the capital city was created due to the migration of human settlements existent during the early historic era in the inter zonal areas, and that in order to reveal this fact, inter-zonal settlements and intercity settlements, could be revealed, only through physical cultural factors.

Methodology

In order to reveal the cascades that are fed by the old Yodha Ela in Anuradhapura, the methodologies engaged primarily are; field visits, calculation of the contour lines, and obtaining of GPS data. In order to establish the distribution of cascades in the study area, maps showing the village tank distribution has been studied. Study areas were divided into two major categories. Viz. the zonal area through which Yodha Ela is flowing as the core area, and the middle area which is 45 km from each side of the river bank, that is in total about 90 km of ground area, was explored. In here, when dividing the ground areas, while a straight line distance measure was not done, but a measurement following the curvy nature of the Yodha Ela.

Since exploring the entire ground area was rather a difficult task, in the protected area portion of the Yodha Ela from *Kala Weva* to *Mahailluppalama* with 45 km on either side or covering a total area of 90 km was explored. The 2nd Portion from *Mahailluppalama* up to *Batuwatta*, and the 3rd portion from *Batuwatta* to *Thisaweve* following the earlier measurements, were explored. For the correction of the distances a Dhumpy leveller had to be utilized, while for the topographical positioning, GPS equipment has to be utilized. Because the survey maps and plans were used, the activities of the respective cascade could be revealed quite conveniently.

The activities of the tank systems in the study area as the Yodha Ela fed lower land and upper land cascade as separate notes, has been done in the zonal classification. Thereafter, in order to rectify the accuracy of those activities, and also to establish their connection with Yodha Ela, Tracing of the geographical positioning of those tanks on a contour map prepared using the ArcGIS software has been done. While naming of the tank systems was done based on the name of the largest tank in that location, and the study was carried out in cascade where at least 05 tanks were included.

In collecting the data associated with the tank systems fed by the ancient Anuradhapura Yodha Ela, an important aspect where attention was paid had been the settlement factors. While collecting data on the tanks in the systems, data collection on the settlements too has been done. In here, from the tanks in the uppermost systems to the lowermost systems in revealing the true activities of the tank system, tools such as GPS instruments, one inch maps, and compass had to be used in the explorations, while the irrigation components of the tanks in the zone were established through ground surface explorations. Accordingly for each and every tank the settlement ground of the relevant tank system distribution trend as to how they occurred, had to be established. All factors related to the settlements connected to the tanks have been recorded both in the written form and non-written methodologies.

In the study of the tank systems fed by the Yodha Ela and the sector exploration in collecting the data, one inch maps, survey plans, data collection issued by the agricultural department on the tank systems, and GPS scientific tools have been used. Revealing

through the sector exploration of the cascade tank system and using GPS location information, analysis of the data was done using the GIS Software. In here, the activities of the tank system in the study area, as to how it was instrumental in the distribution of the settlements was established through data analysis. As such in the establishment of data on the tank, how those tanks influenced the distribution of the settlements, attention was paid to reveal the methodologies engaged by the canal pathways and their connections with the tanks.

According to the ground arrangement pattern in the Yodha Ela Sector exploration, the site information of the cascade system tanks, with the help of the GIS software, the topographical plans of the relevant study zonal area, establishment of the information gathered during the site explorations and placing them onto a single map, was carried out. Thereafter, in order to establish the correctness and accuracy of the information, the complete data base on the entire rajarata tank system distribution, extracting the corresponding information as per the relevant zone, by tracing on the earlier map, correctness of the activities of the system tanks could be done. Then by tracing those cascade on the map where the corrected pathway of Yodha Ela was established, Yodha Ela upper cascade and the lower cascade system, and the establishment of their activities could be done. The originating tank of the cascade could be either be from a rain fed upper zone tank or a catchment area, most of the tank systems subjected to this study are distributed taking into consideration the tank connected to Yodha Ela, as the origin of tank in their distribution. By using GIS software, how much of those cascades are covering the feeder areas could be established.

The second factor is the establishment of the trends in human settlements in the related cascade of the zonal areas. In here, while basing on the field explorations data gathered connected to the cascade system has been important, incorporating such data in the topographical map prepared using GIS Software, a clear understanding on the trends in the settlements distribution could be obtained. Through this, the manner in which the human settlement trends have been associated with the cascade system could be comprehended by this methodology, during the data analysis. This is a fact that can be cleared from the organization of the Archaeological remains recovered from those settlement excavations.

Results

Cascade system can be identified as a water management medium identified in relation to the old Yodha Ela of Anuradhapura. Before the Yodha Ela was constructed (prehistoric or the megalithic culture) from the discovery of human settlements in this zone, it can be presumed that the origin of the village tanks would have happened here. Fed only by the rainwater, the village tanks are connected like the links of a chain starting from uppermost tank up to the lowermost tank according to the topographical pattern. 12 Cascades built in this manner have been identified from the Yodha Ela uppermost zones and lowermost zones, and confirmed. within the entire cultural geographical landscape,

irrigational construction features, and developed over different stages, could be identified. They are;

- Village tanks
- Cascade systems before the construction of Yodha Ela
- Activities of cascades after the construction of Yodha Ela

Under the 1st category which are the tanks that belong to the “*Mother tanks*” (*first water*) of the uppermost cascades that appeared, and concluded to have occurred with the Earliest distribution of the human settlements. It is quite clear that these tanks have been spreading over a distribution period from prehistoric (1000-500 BC) times, up to early historic (500-100 BC) times. Before the construction of the Yodha Ela, tanks that belong to the cascades have been fed only with rain water. Due to increase in complexities of the settlements, and the increase in demand for land and insufficiency of water requirements, Yodha Ela has been constructed through this province. Taking into consideration this increase in the social complexity, Yodha Ela has been constructed, and through this a further strengthening of the early irrigation system network, the Yodha Ela irrigation works have able to further improve their inter-relationship. Meanwhile, the cascade system is operating as two differentiated sections as the uppermost and the lowermost. The uppermost cascade fed only through rainwater or spring-water, while the lowermost cascade tanks are fed by the Yodha Ela. The spill-over water from the uppermost cascades are again directed to be collected at the Yodha Ela through arrangements in the ground pattern (Map No. 01).

Uppermost cascade Systems

From *Kalaweve* which belongs to the uppermost zone of the Yodha Ela, up to *MahaIlluppalama* was first explored, where five (05) cascade systems were revealed. The uppermost zone was studied. Those cascades systems are as given below.

Table 01: Uppermost cascade systems from *Kalaweve* up to *MahaIlluppalama*

Serial No.	Main tank	Sub-tank- i	Sub-tank- ii	Sub-tank- iii
01	<i>Mudaperumagama</i>	<i>Aluth Ihalagama Ihalawewa Maelaperumawa</i>	<i>Karabewa Gokarellagama</i>	<i>Mudaperumagama Radagama</i>
02	<i>Pallekagama</i>	<i>Halmillewa Karabewa</i>	<i>Ihalakagama</i>	<i>Pallekagama Hiripitiyagama</i>
03	<i>Aththikulama</i>	<i>Kelekarabewa Katuwellagama</i>	<i>Aththikulama</i>	<i>Nellikulama</i>
04	<i>Goonapathirawa</i>	<i>Ihalagama Machchagama Manewa</i>	<i>Kadiyangalla Lokgama</i>	<i>Goonapathirawa</i>
05	<i>Maradankadawala</i>	<i>Walagambahuwa Paankulama</i>	<i>Amane</i>	<i>Ihalagama Maradankadawala</i>

Source: From Sector Studies

Plan No. 02, *Pallekagama* Cascade

Among the cascade systems that belong to the uppermost zone of the Yodha Ela, *Gonapathirava* and *Pallekagama* cascades are important. The *Gonapathirava* cascade is connected to the *Ihalagamaveva* (1a) which originates from Cascade of *Maaneva Kanda*, upto *Machchagama*, and is also connected to *Maanawaveva* (1b). Water from Loggama (2b) and *Kadiyangalla* (2a) tank which are situated towards the left side of the feeder zone, and water from *Majjhagama* and *Maanewaveva* while connecting to the *Gonapathiraveva* (2), before the construction of the Yodha Ela, and though this cascade is spreading from *Gonapathirava weva* to lowermost zone, at present, due to construction technologies used in Yodha Ela, the lower zone area is functioning as a separate cascade. Since prehistoric human settlements could be discovered in this cascade uppermost zone, that this zone right from the early days had been subjected to human habitation, was confirmed.

The water catchment areas of some of the tanks originating from the uppermost zones of Yodha Ela, *Halmillewa* (bi) and *Karambawattaveva* (bii) are important as originating tanks based on natural scrub forests and natural water springs. Thereafter the “*Drainage water*” from those tanks join the tanks *Ihalakagamaveva* (1a) and *Pallekagamaveva* (1). Originating from the uppermost zone of the left side of this chain of tanks, water from the *Indunugalaveva* (1b), *Dampellessaveva* (1a) getting collected also to *Pallekagamaveva* (2), and thereafter join the tank *Hiripitiyagama* (3). Spreading in a horizontal manner from the left side of those tanks system, *Hiripitiyagama* is fed also from waters of (*Dampellessa* 3a), and *Kammalathpalliya* (3b). cascade system below the *Hiripitiyagama*, since they are divided by the Yodha Ela, could be identified as operating as a separate system.

Plan No. 03, *Aatthikulama* CascadePlan No. 04, *Maradankadawala* Cascade

Aatthikulama (C) cascade is originating from the Yodha Ela uppermost zone natural forest area, and the tank *Kelekarambewa* (1a) and *Katuwellagama* (1b) could be identified as the twin original tanks. The water from these tanks, join the main *Aatthikulama* (1) tanke, and thereafter join the *Nellikulamaweve* (2) and *Ganthiriyagamaweve* (3) tanks. The *Ganthiriyagama* lower cascade system, due to the construction of the Yodha Ela, is now separated.

Parallel to the *Aatthikulama* cascade, the origination of *Maradankadawala* Cascade has occurred from *Walagambahuwa* (1a) and *Paalankulama* (1b) tanks. *Walagambahuweve* is an active tank of the *Mahakanumulla* cascade, and with the "Drainage water" from lowermost area feeder zone are fed to the *Amanankattuaweweve*. Although the contour lines of the topographical area where this cascade is spread do not decline towards Yodha Ela, it is connected to the *Naachchaduaweweve* across the uppermost area of the Yodha Ela. Thereafter, has joined the tanks *Ihalagamaweve* (2) and *Maradankadawalaweve* (3), situated below the *Manewa wewa* (1).

Table No. 02, Uppermost system tanks from *MahaIlluppalama* up to *Batuwatta*

Serial No	Main tank	Sub-tank-i	Sub-tank-ii	Sub-tank-iii
01	In this Zone only Kulu-Lakes could be found.			

Source: through Sector Studies

Table No. 03, Uppermost settlements from *Batuwatta* up to *Thisaweve*

Serial No	Main tank	Sub-tank-i	Sub-tank-ii	Sub-tank-iii
01	In this zone village-tank could be found.			

Source: through Sector Studies

According to the information revealed during the sector study of Yodha Ela, from *Kalaweve* up to *MahaIlluppalama* of the uppermost zone, although the spread of the cascades can be identified, from *MahaIlluppalama* up to *battuwatta*, from *Batuwatta* up to *Thisaweve*, no any such spread of the cascade system in the uppermost zones could be identified. What was revealed in here is that the main water catchment areas of the uppermost zone from *Kalaweve* up to *MahaIlluppalama* could not be identified. But the agricultural activities in those zones have been carried out based on rain water and on tanks fed through natural spring water sources. According to the human settlement factors, the settlements which have spread associated with these tanks is a clear fact that from historic periods these irrigation works must have been on an active scale. But, from *MahaIlluppalama* up to *Thisaweve*, and within the uppermost zones of the main resources *Naachchaduwa*, *Thuruwila*, *Nuwara Weve*, due to the supply of water to the uppermost zones, the functionality of the cascades have been slowed down. Yet, during the historical periods, before the development of large irrigation works, centralizing on cascades in this zone, water supply activities had taken place, could be established through the distribution study of the marginalized tanks. As such, due to the development of the irrigation works, the water management methodologies before the construction of Yodha Ela, and over a period of time have made them obsolete. Due to this reason, even though human settlement factors within that zone could be identified, it is quite reasonable to think that some of the tanks in the cascade system have been rendered dormant, as a result of some later on activities.

Lowermost cascade system (from *Kalaweve* up to *MahaIlluppalama*)

Yodha Ela has been constructed not only for the purpose of fulfilling the water requirements of the Capital City, but also as an irrigation work for the purpose of fulfilling the Inter zonal water requirements. Although the construction of the Yodha Ela across *Kala oya* and *Malwathu oya* could be identified as a complete irrigation work, during the early phase Yodha Ela has been constructed to some extent, only for supplying water to tanks in the intermediate zone and the settlements. Although the Yodha Ela flowed in an inter-zonal area between two main *oyas*, no suitable landscape setting is there, for obtaining water to Yodha Ela from those sources. This fact was revealed from an examination of the elevations of the contour lines in the study area. Taking these factors into consideration, with the aim of expediting the water utilization of the cascade system, and the supply of the water requirement of the lowermost settlements, Yodha Ela has been constructed. Due to this reason, it is clear that even at present the cascade system of the lowermost zone has been able to remain active and quite unaffected by the influence of those activities.

Table No. 04, The lowermost system tanks from *Kalaweve* upto *MahaIlluppalama*.

Serial No	Main tank	Sub tank- i	Sub tank- ii	Sub Tank- iii
01	<i>Mahailluppalama</i>	<i>Sangettewa</i> <i>Sirikkulama</i> <i>Maha- Mii</i> <i>gassegama Kuda-</i> <i>Mii gassegama</i> <i>Maradankadawala</i>	<i>Koniththi ela</i> <i>-Kattiyawa</i> <i>wewa</i>	<i>Katiyawa ela-</i> <i>^Nawagala</i> <i>Settlement&</i>

Source: through Sector Studies

Plan No. 05, *MahaIlluppalama* Cascade

MahaIlluppalama cascade which can be identified in the form of a fan, is fed by a number of tanks in the uppermost zone. Those tanks have later been found to be fed from Yodha Ela, was revealed during the research study. Water from *Maradankadawala* (1a), *Sungettawa* (1b), *Sirikkulama* (1c), *Miigessagama* (1d), *KudaMiigessagama* (1e), feed the *MahaIlluppalama* tank. According to the large extent of the spread of the catchment area, this tank can be identified as a large tank. Water from *MahaIlluppalama* is feeding the *Kattiyaweve* (1) through *Koniththi Ela*. Within this zone, historic period human settlements could be found, and accordingly can be identified as human settlements after the construction of the Yodha Ela.

Table No. 05, lowermost tanks from *MahaIlluppalama* up to Batuwatta

Serial No	Main tank	Sub tank-I	Sub tank-ii	Sub tank- iii	Sub tank- vi
01	<i>Kuttikulama</i>	<i>Ihalagama Galmaduwa Nabadewa Katiyawa</i>	-	-	-
	<i>Aluthwewa</i>	<i>Poththegama Galmaduwa</i>	-	-	-
02	<i>Eppawala</i>	<i>Koonwewa Mahaganewewa Kudagane wewa Eppawala Katiyawa Madiyawa</i>	<i>Madiyawa ela- Veheragala Ruins</i>	-	-
03	<i>Kaduru wewa</i>	<i>Palugaswewa Meegahagama wewa Makule wewa</i>	<i>Eliyadiuwewewa</i>	<i>Rajjallegama Hurigaswewa</i>	<i>Pahala halmillewa</i>
	<i>Halmillewa</i>	<i>Pahala halmillewa</i>	<i>Ipalogama</i>	<i>Achiriyagama</i>	<i>Veheragala Settlement</i>
04	<i>Getakela</i>	<i>Kudagama Paindikulama</i>	-	-	-
	<i>Kiralogama</i>	<i>Kubukwewa Paindikulama</i>	<i>Mahabellan- kadawala</i>	<i>Kudabellankadawala thalakolawewa Rajapakshayagama</i>	
	<i>Galnewa</i>	<i>Meegassegama Paindikulama</i>	-	-	-

Source: through Sector Studies

Plan No. 06, Galmaduwa Cascade

Taking the spread in the form of a fan, *Galmaduwa* cascade could be identified as an irrigation work fed by the Yodha Ela. In here two main networks of tanks could be identified, while *Kuttikulamawewa* (1a) is fed by the Yodha Ela and the “Drainage water” from the feeder area, join the *Ihalagama* (2), and then the *Galmaduwwewa* (3). Starting

in the *Huriyagasweva*. From the feeder zone of *sooriyagasweva*, water is received to *Halmilleweva* (4) feeder zone, out of which the excess after feeding *Mediya Ela* and *Katiyawa Ela*, and it flows through *Weragala*, *Nawagala* join *Kala oya*. Within the latter half of that cascade system, it is quite clear are also fed by *Halmillewa* (1a), *Ipalogama* (1b), and *Aachariyagama* (1) tanks.

Plan No. 09, *Paindikulama* cascade

Plan No. 10, *Hoorigasweva* cascade

Paindikulama cascade is a cluster cascade identified in the lowermost zone of *Yodha Ela*. What is special in here is that this cascade is being fed by a couple of other cascades. Before the *Yodha Ela* was constructed these tanks would have been in an active state. There are three pairs of main feeder tanks to these cascades, viz; *Galneva* (1c) *Miigassegama* (1b) tanks, *Kiralogama* (1b) *Kumbukweva* (1a) tanks, and *Ketakala* (1b) *Kudagama* (1a) tanks are feeding the main tank which is *Paindikulamaweve*. Water from *paindikulama* is received by the *Mahabellankadawala* (2), while *Mahabellankadawalaweve* is fed by *Thalakolaweve* (2a). *Thalakolaweve* (2a) is also fed by tanks *Delnegama* (2ai), and *Akuranayagama* (2bi) which also feeds *Mahabellankadawalaweve*.

Identified as *Hoorigasweve* belonging to *Yodha Ela* zone from *MahaIlluppalama* up to *Batuwatta*, "Drainage waters" from the *Kudagama* (1a), *Ihalasiyambalawa* (1b) tanks feed the *Eliyadivulweve* (2b). Towards the left of *Eliyadivulweve*, connecting from vertically above, receive water also from *Ihalaweve* (1b), *Ihalagama* (1a) tanks. While water from *Eliyadivulweve* (1) supplies water to *Hoorigasweve* (2a) and also to *Rajjallegamaweve* (2), thereafter join also with the *Halmillavetiyaweve* (3). *Rajjallegama* and *Hoorigasweve* are joined together spreading from the uppermost zone to the lowermost zone as a chain of tanks, they are grouped and studied separately in here.

Table No. 06, lowermost cascade from *Batuwatta* upto *Thisaweve*

Serial No	Main Tank	Sub- Tank-I	Sub tank-II	Sub tank-III	Sub tank-IV
01	<i>Tirappanaya Nabadewa</i>	<i>Kaduruwewa Kudagama Kadahagaha wewa</i>	<i>Ihala thalawa wewa Kudagaha wewa</i>	<i>Kumbukgaha wewa</i>	<i>Wehera godella</i>
02	<i>Ekiriya wewa</i>	<i>Miigahawewa Mandagaha wewa Waduressagama Maddhumagama</i>	<i>Ekiriya wewa Galayagama</i>	<i>Illuppankadawala Uhukkulama Kudagama wewa</i>	

Source: through Sector Studies

For the purpose of sector studies, and according to the arrangements of the terrain, from *Batuwatta* up to *Thisaweve* and Fed by *Yodha Ela*, a twin cascade system could be revealed. *Ethiriyaweve* cascade whilst spreading in a vertical direction, and taking into consideration their spread, arriving at any decision on the topographical landscape of those zones, is quite a clear fact. Accordingly, the terrain in that zone could be identified as spreading with an inclination towards *Kala oya*, which was confirmed by the calculation of the mean sea levels of that zone. The beginning of the *Thirappanaya* cascade takes place from twin tanks. viz; *Kudalama* (1a), *Thirappanaya* (1b), and *Waragoda* (1c) tanks. The “*Drainage water*” from the tanks fed by the *Yodha Ela* waters, also join the *Ihalathalaweve* (1). *Kaduruweve* (1d), which is on the left side, and the *Gambirisweve* tanks, and from *Moragoda* (2a i) and *Kadagaha* (2) tanks, *Kumbukgahaweve* (3) and *Katiyaweve* (4) tanks are fed. The water from *Katiyaweve*, after distributing to the settlements, flows down to *Kala oya*.

The uppermost tanks of *Ekiriweve* cascade are a triplet. They are, *Miigahaweve* (1a), *Mandagamaweve* (1b), and *Wandurassagamaweve* (1c), while their “*Drainage waters*” get collected to *Maddumagamaweve* (1). This cascade for the reason that it is spread in a vertical direction, waters from tanks in the uppermost zones, which

are the *Galayagamaweveva* (2a) and *ullukkulamaweveva* (3a) tanks, join together and feed *Illuppankadawalaweveva* (3), and *Kudagamaweveva* (4).

The cascades which existed before the construction of the old Anuradhapura Yodha Ela, have operated in a new fashion along with the construction of the old Yodha Ela. Although before the construction of the Yodha Ela, a large number of Village tanks could be found in this Zone, later on that when the water requirement from there was insufficient for the settlements, agricultural needs, Yodha Ela was constructed in the related zone, has been a fact revealed through this scientific study. That the creation of Yodha Ela is an extension of the settlements development, could be confirmed through the analysis of the relevant information gathered conforming to the objectives.

Early period *Kalaweveva* and *Thisaweveva* intermediate zone, were fed only with rainwater, and over a period the changes that occurred with the climatic conditions, and due to the increase in complexities of the settlements, Yodha Ela may have been constructed through this Zone. In mobilizing the Yodha Ela construction technology, creating the flow traversing the uppermost terrain around each tank, is a speciality. From MahaIlluppalama upto Batuwatta, with the associated tanks which are; *Medagama*, *Kuttikulama*, *Aluthweveva*, *Ithalaweveva*, *Maradankadawala*, *Amunukolaya*, *Kiriamunukolaya*, *Konweveva*, *Kiralogama*, the Physical bank portions, and although the remnants of which can be identified even today along the path taken by this canal, because of the *Mahaweli* development project, have come to an inactive state. Another important factor which can confirm the above fact is the creation of Yodha Ela to circulate around each and every tank, but also the Anicuts deployed to supply water to each and every tank, from Yodha Ela, remain as remnants today. Even in the water management of the last tank of the lowermost cascade so discovered, the irrigation works planner has utilized diverse methodologies. The water from these tank, while it is not allowed to be just drained down directly to *Kala Oya*, but have also acted deploying canals in between tank as well as among the settlements, making it possible for the inter-exchange of water.

When taking into consideration of all these factors, what is clearly understood is that in the study area, well before the construction of the Yodha Ela has had an organized water management methodology, and due to changes in weather pattern and climate, later on Yodha Ela may have been created. Although, before construction of Yodha Ela, the early cascade systems as from the uppermost up to lowermost that may have existed, remained intact even after the construction of Yodha Ela, the uppermost and the lowermost cascade systems have now come to function as two differentiated systems. However, through this it can be shown that it is a complete irrigation work done in order to fulfil the water requirements of the capital city, and those of the inter-zonal settlements of the *Kala Oya* uppermost valley.

Discussion

The spreading of the cascade according to the topographical landscape from the uppermost to the lowermost, is the result of the settlement incremental approach, has been

shown in the research study. Before the Yodha Ela was constructed, the water requirements of the *Kala Oya* valley uppermost area settlements was fulfilled by the cascade system which can be identified as the principal water management methodology. The cascade system which was networked from the uppermost areas up to the lowermost areas, can now be identified as acting in isolation, along with the construction of *Yodha Ela*. In here, to what extent the distribution trends of the established cascades, topographical landscape, water management methodologies, can be justified in the early researches done, has been subjected to scrutiny.

Functionality of cascades before construction of the Yodha Ela

The cascade Systems in the *Kala Oya* valley uppermost zone, before the construction of Yodha Ela, were identified. Among them, the vertically disposed *maradankadawala*, *Ganthiriyagama*, *Kuttikulama*, *Kon weva*, *Kele Divulweva*, *Thirappanaya*, *Aathikulama*, *Pallekagama*, *Karabewa* and the like are important. Four principal ways in which the topographical functionality of these cascades, have been illustrated (Bandaranayake, 2018). Out of which, in the study area, cluster cascades with two or more associated tanks, and single cascades, have been identified. Cascades that are spread in an angular direction too have been an important discovery in the research. Among them, *Maaneva*, *Aamane*, *Thirappanaya*, *Aathikulama* cascades, and *Nallamudawa*, *Mahaganeweveva*, *Nambadeva* as cluster cascades, are important.

As a research done within the country; “Scientific foundation on some of the traditional practices in the land and water management of village lake cascades”, is important (Madduma Bandara, Yatigammana, Paranavithana, 2010). In this research, as some of the associated tanks, *Ethidathkella*, *Millawetiya*, *Sandamaleliya* and others are important among the cascades. This is important as an environmental factor in understanding about topographical landscape of the relevant study zone.

Map No.01 Map showing the division of the uppermost and the lowermost cascades.

During the study of the water management methodologies in the associated village tanks that belonged to cascades, a complete understanding of the irrigational components has been acquired. As tanks connected to the uppermost zone cascades; *Kurundan Kulama*, *Wellamudawa*, *Wagayakulama*, *Halmillewa*, *Kurundu Weva*, *Dikweva*, *Rota Weva*, *Kuda Weva*, and as the irrigation components identified in those lakes; *Perahana*, *Iswetiya*, *Godawala*, *Kuluweva*, *Tisbambe*, *Kivul Ela*, *Kattakaduwa* and their features are important. As a research carried out in this connection, "Traditional tank systems for conservation and effective use of water" the research paper has illustrated the utility features of the irrigational components, in an old tank which are; *Godawala*, *Gasgommana*, *Iswetiya* and the like (Dharmasena, 2005). Likewise, in the research paper "Kattakaduwa: Potential land for agro-forestry system development in Sri Lanka", Dharmasena has illustrated, that by conservation of forests how the features of a village tank could be developed. In here, it has been shown that forests, scrub Jungles, *Henas*, Village, *Paddy Fields*, *GasGommana*, *Tisbambe* as components that belong to the uppermost region, and *Kattakaduwa*, to the lowermost region of a tank. Herein, it has been shown that by protecting the uppermost components, the *Kattakaduwa* too was protected (Dharmasena, 2005). *Tisbambe*, which is situated in a somewhat raised landscape above the Tank, and that in here the Community Settlements were spread, has been revealed in the research. Centralized on *tisbambe* associated with the village tank that the settlements may have spread, is shown by Dharmasena (2005) and Brohier (1975), and in here *Mii*, *Amba*, *Coconut* like tree varieties which require only a minimum soil water condition, that the settlements may have spread centralizing on these zonal areas. Chandana Rohana Vithanachchi in his research on old irrigation works of some components of an old village tank, revealed in his study that among the components discovered included facts on *Iswetiya*, *Denikada*, *Kattakaduwa*, and how their utility values could be established.

Even before the Yodha Ela was constructed, it is quite clear that the water management methodologies which existed centralizing on the tanks in order to safeguard the environmental balance, have been more appropriate methodologies. That the distribution of settlements in the study zone has had a direct link with the irrigation works, has been established. Although the early settlements which were centralizing on the uppermost areas, later on taking into consideration of the efficacy in the agriculture and water management methodologies, those settlements may have spread towards the lower flat land areas. Along with the increase in the complexities of the settlements and due to the lowering of the efficacy of the irrigation facilities along with the diminishing in productivity of the water catchment areas, and as an alternative to it, Yodha Ela may have been created during the historic period. However, even before the creation of Yodha Ela, settlements had been spread in this zone, and that later on as an extension to the development of settlements, Yodha Ela may have been constructed, is also quite clear.

The origin of the water resources of these cascade has found in this research, to be either a natural stream or a scrub jungle. From the uppermost up to the lowermost, the excess waters from these cascades finally get collected at the Kala Oya. Before the

construction of Yodha Ela in this area, and since associated with the Kala Oya uppermost valley areas, original and prehistoric human settlements could be identified, the origin of the cascades too must have been those uppermost valley areas, has been shown in this research. During the early historic period, and in the middle or later time periods, with the construction of Yodha Ela right across the cascades, the functionality of the cascades has been sub-divided into two sections.

Plan No. 13, Katiyava cascade

Plan No. 14, Mediyava cascade

According to the topographical pattern of the cascades discovered from this zone, they had to be shown as cluster cascades, linear cascades, and angular cascades. The geographical formations of the cascades have been influenced by the topographical landscape pattern of the relevant zone. Although the origination of the cascades identified in the uppermost area was either a natural stream or a water shed area, after the construction of Yodha Ela, the originating tank of the lowermost cascade was found to be a tank connected to Yodha Ela, has been revealed.

Table No.07, Water Catchment Areas

Catchment area	Village tank	Fertilize area
Shrub jungle	<i>Kadiyangalla</i>	<i>Yodha ela</i>
Shrub jungle	<i>Ihala wewa</i>	<i>Yodha ela</i>
Thick jungle	<i>Ulankulama wewa</i>	<i>Yodha ela</i>
Thick jungle	<i>Puliyankulama wewa</i>	<i>Yodha ela</i>
Thick jungle of <i>Kiri amunukolaya</i>	<i>Tammennagala</i>	<i>Yodha ela</i>
Thick jungle	<i>Dikwewa, Aliyawatunu wewa, Gatadiula</i>	<i>Yodha ela</i>
Thick jungle	<i>Kalekubuk wewa</i>	<i>Yodha ela</i>

Source, Field visit

For the convenience of study of the Yodha Ela, the terrain was sub-divided into three portions. Accordingly, within areas from *Kalaweve* up to *MahaIlluppalama*, *MahaIlluppala upto Batuwatta*, and *Batuwatta to Thisaweve*, 12 cascade could be established. A conceptual approach regarding the term cascade "Mother Tank" is clear from the interpretation given by Madduma Bandara. That it is "Collected from short term water ways and transported while being made use of and feeding the living beings within the dry zone geographical landscape, and an organized and interconnected chain of tanks", is said by him (Madduma Bandara, 1985). As shown in the research and before the construction of Yodha Ela, the cascade mother tank has been a tank connected to the uppermost water ways or a scrub jungle area, and after the construction of Yodha Ela the *mother Tank* of the lowermost cascades is fed by the Yodha Ela (Table No. 02). The main reason for this is the fact that depending on the functionality of the cascade tanks, the concept of appearance of the catchment areas. The uppermost cascades are fed only from rain water or the natural spring water, and over a period of time or due to climatic reasons made the changing movements. But, since the lowermost cascades are now fed by the Yodha Ela, through those cascades an active supply of water is now received throughout the year.

Due to the influence of the ground water and in comparison to the uppermost zone, the lowermost zone soil developed into more suitable terrain for agricultural works, and the spread of the settlements to this zone too may have been influenced by this irrigation work. Compared to the external geophysical factors, the internal geophysical arrangement too have an influence on the functionality of the cascade, is explained in the analysis given by Dharmasena on the cascades. "On a sustainable basis with the interference of man, water, soil, air and vegetation fulfilling the fundamental requirements of man, vegetation, and animals, in the dry zone geographical landscape within the feeder zone areas for the living, consisting of ground and water resources rich environmental system", by which it is made clear (Dharmasena, 2017:10). What is understood from this is that there is a strong networking in the representation of the entire social system which is displayed through cascade. In order to maintain the social balance and as some of the factors shown by binford, which are the climate, weather, soil, vegetations, water and the like physical factors are important, while in the identification of building up of the external environmental culture which is formed corresponding to the internal functionality of an cascade, this is important. The variations in those factors mentioned above may also have influenced the settlements spread, has been a fact that could be identified.

The study of the rajarata cascades from a scientific research point of view was first initiated during the decade of eighties in the 20th Century. Through these research, attention has been paid only towards the functionality of the cascades systems in the uppermost zone originating from short waterways. As such, some of the cascades which originate from a tank, are the *Thirappana* starting from *Naachchaduwa weve*, and *Horiwila* cascades, *Kadiragama*, *Thoruwa Ellanga*, *Maaminiya Oya*, and the tanks that spread parallel to *Malwathu Oya*, are important (Madduma Bandara, 1991). Centralized on *divulweve*, the

Rathmale Cascade, (Madduma Bandara, 1985), the *Kapiriggama* cascade, too have been originated from a tank (Panabokke, 2000). But, to develop the water capacity of these tanks, cross canals from other water resources have been connected, although in those earlier researches only a minimum attention has been paid on this. Use of such alternative methods for system tanks may have been followed also due to incremental results of the settlements and climatic changes, is also clear.

As some of the major factors that contributed towards the functionality of the cascades; rain (Weather), landscape pattern, soil conditions, environment, and temperature can be identified. That from the middle of the Iron Age up to the historic period, the climatic and weather factors have not been stable, is clear from the variations in the cultural and historical landscape changes. Over a period of time along with the variations in the rain and climate changes, due to complexities in the requirements, and the water movement activity of the village tanks may not have been sufficient. The remedy adopted in such situations had been the construction of a horizontal canal pathway across the vertically spread cascades and feeding them. This can be considered as an awakening stage of an irrigation culture trend, though no attention on such trends have been shown through any of the earlier researches carried out. The old Yodha Ela of Anuradhapura which connects with the main cascades identified in the intermediate zone is a cascade system originating from a tank connected to Yodha Ela. As a result of the climatic and seasonal variations, the census carried out by Panabokke on Rajarata Tanks, has shown that out of the Total of 4017 tanks, nearly half of it had become inactive (Panabokke, 1999). Accordingly, it is clear that even the Yodha Ela may have been constructed across this zone, as an alternative solution corresponding to the situations prevalent during that period, due to changes in the climatic conditions. During the early stages, the spread of the settlements and to fulfil their requirement of water received from the cascade, and in order to expedite the water flow and to feed cascades with external resources of water has been done through the construction of intermediate canals. What is understood from this is that in this zone, even before the construction of the Yodha Ela, their Water Requirements may have been fulfilled through prevalent tanks system, and the construction technology of the Yodha Ela by allowing the water to flow also around the highest tank of the tank system, it is quite clear from the study of the construction technology, that it was a recuperation measure that had been undertaken.

Discovered as a cascade connected result can be shown the water movement affected by the *Kattakaduwa*, and centralizing on the lowermost lake of the cascade, the establishment of the spread of the settlements could be realized. These settlements which belong to a historic period, and from the times the cascades were active and the migration happened quite after the construction of the Yodha Ela, has been shown and for this to happen, that an appropriate terrain with suitable soil, or internally suitable environmental factors, and a proper active movement of water in the lakes would have caused them. An important research paper done in this regard, "Scientific foundation on the traditional knowledge in the water management of the village tank cascade system" is important.

Through this, that the water movement within the cascades as well as in the uppermost, are quite different from one another, has been identified, and the variations in the water quality under the surveillance of the electrical conductivity, and the introduction of water immersions for the protection of the *Kattakaduwas* of the cascades as the objective, this study has been carried out (Bandara; Yatigammana; Paranavithana, 2010). Regarding the accuracy of results on the facts revealed in this research, it is reasonable to show that there is a connection between the functionality of the *Kattakaduwas* of the tanks belonging to cascades originating from Yodha Ela. According to this decision, activity of the ground water of the cascade had been caused by the water movement of the *Kattakaduwa*, from the uppermost to the lowermost. From the said research, destruction of the *Kattakaduwas* of the village tanks, and due to not affecting maintenance works, and by identifying the differences in the electrical conductivity, this fact has been confirmed. Accordingly, salts and iron which are two of the main twin polluting components in that water showing a higher concentration within the cascades from the uppermost up to the lowermost, the electrical conductivity at the *Kattakaduwa* right below the tank bund increasing by a few folds, and along with the *Kattakaduwa* Water too flowing into the lowermost, how the conductivity of that water has gone up, is shown. In order to regulate this situation exercised through the Yodha Ela bund construction technology can be thought of, since the cascade system of the lowermost is fed by Yodha Ela, establishment of sluice gates in order to provide water to the tanks, and Water from the Village Tanks situated in the uppermost were connected to Yodha Ela through ground water, and the like features. In that research, it has been shown that in order to allow the flow of surface rain water to the tank, by establishing anicuts at a higher elevation, thus allowing accumulation of only a lower concentration of salts in the Paddy Fields, and this task has been accomplished by the ancient Irrigation canal technicians through the use of '*Ketasorrowva*' (Bandara, Yatigammana, Paranavithana, 2010). This is made clear from the manner in which the Anicuts are placed at a higher elevation on the Left bank in supplying water from Yodha Ela to the cascades. Quite apart from this, the fact that by allowing the flow of water in the canal to flow covering a large area encircling the tanks, infiltration of water with a low concentration of salts and irons to the Tanks through the right bank are allowed to get connected to the tank after getting infiltrated through the left bank. From the citing of the sluice gates, it is clear that in order to obtain water they have been established at a much higher elevation, and by citing the Sluices at a higher elevation, thus preventing these salt mixed water from getting accumulated in the cascade as a precautionary technological measure undertaken. Accordingly the irrigation technician may have had a prior understanding not only on the citing of irrigational components corresponding to the landscape pattern, but also on the consequences of such actions. The aim of the research paper titled: **Kattakaduwa: A potential land for agro-forestry development in Sri Lanka** had been undertaken to study that through *Kattakaduwa* during the water movement of the cascades, the Water seepage through the lake bund is minimized, and that along with the Water the collection and the mixing of salts and iron which pollute the soil and the agricultural Products is controlled (Dharmasena, 1995: 1-10). As sample tanks

used in this research are some of those Tanks that bear a connection to the Uppermost Study Area, those results were subjected to this discussion (Dharmasena, 1995: 1-10). What is so special here is that not only through the environmental conservation, and the water movement activity of the cascades, but also through the connected technological studies done on the canal waterways during later periods, this fact was further established. Through the Yodha Ela canal bank construction technology, the efforts taken in safeguarding the activity of the *Kattakaduwas* in the Tanks" of cascades connected to the Yodha Ela, and the supply of water to the lakes based on the topographical landscape distribution of both the lowermost and the uppermost lands of Yodha Ela, were taken into consideration. While Yodha Ela does not supply water to cascades in the uppermost region, those systems are fed by *Kuluwev* and *Olagamwev*, is shown in the study. Although the supply of water to cascades originating from the Yodha Ela had been done through two sluice gates, water management methodology of the Yodha Ela canal system is of a more complex nature. Yodha Ela has been made to circulate around the tanks covering a large area, and this has acted to make it possible the maintenance of the ground water table at a higher level. As an object of those earlier studies, through the *DiyaGilma*, Protection of the *Kattakaduwa*, that the protection of the ground water Level, can be sustained. That the Yodha Ela though quite indirectly has accomplished these tasks, is confirmed by the fact that in order to facilitate *DiyaGilma* on the canal right bank, conforming to the sloping of the terrain, construction of the canal pathway has been done. This technological procedure is not confined only to the tank concerned, but has been able to protect the ground water level of almost 54 miles of terrain. As such this creative technology may have been used with the aim of developing the ground water level of all the cascade systems spread on to both sides, is quite clear. In the construction of the Yodha Ela, a special attention has been paid to the elevation of the geographical landscape of the terrain. When the elevation of the terrain is of mid-sloping or low-sloping nature, that it has been possible to maintain the ground water table at a higher level, could be confirmed.

Plan No. 15, for purposes of water management the nature of the terrain sloping situation

The supply of water requirements for the settlements and agricultural grounds situated below the mid or large capacity tanks is done through sluice gates established, taking into consideration the altitude of the tank. But in the village tanks which are built up through a networking of cascades, the movement of water is taking place through ground water activity. Interchange of water among these tanks which have been created taking into consideration the topographical Landscape, and since the water movement between these tanks takes place underground, the tendency of silt getting accumulated in the tanks below, is at a minimum.

The direct influence of the ground water from the highest lake of the cascade is received in the zone called '*Purana Wela*', Asweddumization is first carried out in the corresponding paddy field of that tank called the *Purana Wela*, which is situated in the lowest topographical landscapes of the tank. Secondly, Asweddumization is done in the other paddy fields taking into account, the water capacity of the tank. The connection between the tank and the *purana Wela* is decided upon by the size of the tank, and the Feeder Area of the *Purana Wela* is decided on the water capacity of the uppermost tank, has been shown (Dharmasena, 2009). What becomes clear in here is that the functionality of the cascades has happened according to an Activity of the Ground Water movement, and that may have influenced the building up of the relationship between the tank and the associated village community.

Conclusions

During the early historic period, taking into consideration the environmental and topographical factor requirements for agricultural needs, and as a result of networking of the Village Tanks so constructed from the upper lands up to the low lands, cascades have originated. Even before the construction of the Yodha Ela, the settlements in the *Kala Oya* uppermost zonal valley have fulfilled their requirements of water through cascades. As an example, *Konapathirana* Cascade spreading from uppermost early historical settlements of *Ihala Weva* (Maaneva) up to lowermost *Mahalluppalama*, uppermost *Kiriamunukolaya* originating from the highland where the *Muukalas* are situated, and the *Ulankulama* is the highest Lake of *Kuttikulama* cascade, while the lowermost (Lowest) lake is the *Katyawa Weva*. During the early historic period, construction of the Yodha Ela has been done by allowing the water flow to cover the centre portion of each cascade. As irrigation components used in the water management of lakes connected to cascades; *Perahana*, *Iswetiya*, *Godawala*, *Kuluweva*, *Tisbambe*, *Kivulela*, *Kattakaduwa* and the like, were revealed in the research. In order to manage the natural rainwater and fountain waters, each and every irrigational component has been cited according to the ground elevation. through this methodology, the control of silt in the water, and to make it suitable for consumption and in agriculture, in filtering off of toxic water polluting elements *Godawala*, *Iswetiya*, *Kiwul ela*, *Kulu weva* have contributed, while the supply of ground water is accomplished by *Kattakaduwa*. Even before the construction of the Yodha Ela, cascades had been made use of as environmental concepts in water management, is quite clear.

Cascade which became active right from the uppermost zones, after the construction of the Yodha Ela, its lowermost portion only had a continuous water movement activity. As a current need, along with the construction of Yodha Ela, the migration of the settlements from the uppermost towards the lowermost zone, may have happened as an influence of this irrigation works. But, as a result of the climatic changes in this zone, that the migration of the communities towards the lowermost zone has happened, is also quite clear. While centralizing on the tanks in the lowermost zones settlements were revealed, no human settlements were discovered in the cascade mid-zones. What becomes clear by this is that, connected to this zone, that settlements spread was not there, but due to the over-utilization of land, and the settlement areas called the 'Tisbambe', were later on converted to agricultural lands.

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**The Hindu- Buddhist religious and social
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Abstract:

This topic and the research undergone the subject of Historical Archaeology and its social factors which were covering major part of nature of the subject. The Archaeological evidence confirms that the cross-cultural and social ties between the people of South India and Sri Lanka in pre-Buddhist time of the history are being revealed from earlier years. Archaeological evidence of various artefacts as well as settlements such as coins, pots and carvings belonging to the pre- Buddhist period have been found in the North, North Central, North Western and Eastern as well as Southern Provinces of Sri Lanka. According to these facts, among the religious beliefs practiced by the people in the early period before the conversion to Buddhism were tree worship, rock worship and sun deities, etc, these religions attributed divinity to objects of nature are prominent, and there is evidence that religions such as phallic worship, which were part of the Vedic Hindu faith, were prevalent among the people

Keywords: *Buddhism, Hinduism, Brahmanism, reconciliation, equality*

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Introduction

The carvings associated with the Buddhist stupas reveal clear evidence that these religions continued to coexist with Buddhism even after the conversion of the Sri Lanka people to Buddhism in the third century BC. *Ganesha* and *Kubera* depict such Hindu deities in Buddhist stupa carvings, confirming the existence of a religious reconciliation between the two Hindu-Buddhist groups. Hindu deities may have added their carvings to Buddhist shrines as a way of paying homage to the Buddha. There is ample evidence of the preservation of the features of this Hindu-Buddhist reconciliation during the times of the Tamil rulers like *Sena-Guttika* and *Elara*, as well as during the times of the Sinhala Buddhist rulers like Duttagamini (161 BC–137 BC), Kanittatissa (165–193 AD) and Gajabahu (113–c. 135). After the conversion to Buddhism, the names and titles of the Brahmi inscriptions from the third century BC to the first century BCE, indicate that the people of this country may have known Hindu beliefs from pre-Buddhist times. The nature of this mechanism of reconciliation can be gauged from the sources included in major literary sources such as the *Deepavamsa*, the *Mahavamsa*, the *Wansatthappakasiniya* and the *Attakatha*, which were written later and include details of that period. From the very beginning of the reign of King Mahasen (277–304) in the latter part of the third century AD, it appears that the policy of reconciliation was hampered by anti-egalitarian practices such as the demolition of Hindu temples. While the doctrine of equality plays an important role in the teachings of the Supreme Buddha, there is ample evidence that many Buddhist and Hindu rulers practiced it in a way that preserved it. Research problem is the Hindu-Buddhist religious reconciliation born out of the pre-Buddhist beliefs in Sri Lanka and the cross-cultural religious environment created by the political power struggles between Sri Lanka and the South Indian Chola region.

Results and discussion

There is ample evidence that the people of India and Sri Lanka in the pre-Christian era worshiped a variety of natural objects and tribal chiefs and regarded them as deities. Benjamin Roland points out that the worship of demons, trees and trees, water and cobras, as well as the worship of cobra female and male hybrids has existed in Hinduism and Buddhism since its inception (Roland. 1953. 24). While these philosophical factors of both religions stand out by creating the esthetic verism.

The people who highly assimilated to the divine souls in their daily living life and they were respected and venerated to the souls in a part of the social and religious culture (Paranavitana: 1929.327), those spirits were revered by the people and were incorporated into their daily lives in large numbers. Perhaps the more intelligent people believed in Brahmanism. These beliefs are very similar to the religious beliefs of the time when the Buddha was alive in northern India. Sources can also point out how the lifestyle of the Hindu caste system in this country was affected during this period.

Buddhism was embraced to Sri Lanka in the 3rd Century BC in consequence of contemporary political activities preceded by the emperor Asoka and king

Devanampiyatissa respectively India and Sri Lanka. According to the foregone data, based on our previous observations, pre-Buddhist beliefs existed and it is believed that Buddhism was known to the people of this country before Devanampiyatissa.

The phallic worship had become one part of religion which was followed by the people in Sri Lanka in the period of king Pandukahanbhaiya in 4th century BC. Although Vansaththappakasiniya gave both the meaning of the word “*Sivikashala*” as a hall and a maternity ward for the worship of Shiva, Paranavithana points out that it is more appropriate to accept the original ideas as this name is also mentioned among the names of religious buildings (Paranavithana, 1929.326). Accordingly, he explains that it is reasonable to think that phallic worship was prevalent among the religious beliefs of the people of this country during the reign of King Pandukabhaya. Ipso facto the archaeological facts, especially from the lithic records engraved from 3rd Century BC have given clear disputable clues about the correctness of the above hypotheses. According to the Indian Shilpa text *Kautilya’s Arthashastra* written in between 4th century BCE to 3rd Century BCE period clearly mentioned, chapels reserved for each of Hindu gods including *Shiva*, should be constructed inside the king’s city to pay homage to them. It does not specify whether the deities are represented as idols or gender symbols. It cannot be pointed out that Shiva became as important among the Hindus during this period as he was later, as a major deity. Kautilya’s *Arthashastra* mentions Shiva with sub-deities such as *Asvins*, *Vaishravana* and *Madira* (the lord of liquor) (ibid, 326).

However, Hema Ellawala explains that the word *Shivika* hall means a hall with a spherical shape, as *Sivika* is a palanquin (Ellawala: 2002.143). This elliptical oblong shape hall most possibly utilised for housed an objects, belongs to god Shiva which has been introduced by the words *Shiva Deva*, *Shivika*, *Shika Sala*. The general ground plan of a Hindu temple in India basically in its incipient period consists of frontal oblong shape vestibule and that adjacent behind it square shape sanctum in which house *Shiva linga*. Therefore the foregone palanquin shaped hall probably may have a very primitive shape of the Shiva temple in 4th century BC, this must be constructed based on the bamboo frame with wattle and daub finished. Reverend Buddha Ghosha in his *Pali atthakatha* text name *Saddharma pundarika* and *Udana* written 5th century, also commented with compromise on above mentioned meanings of words *Shivika Sala* (ibid 143). Therefore we are able to deliberately conjecture about the originate period of the credo of *Shiva* worship under the Patronage of Pandukabhaya. Thus it was the part of the propensity in religion that had been followed by the people in this intricacy period of Sri Lankan society.

Therefore, it has been pointed out that even after the conversion to Buddhism in the third century BC, the Sinhalese people still revered the Shiva linga as in earlier times. It is also mentioned in the original Brahmi inscriptions such as *Shiva*, *Maha Shiva* and *Shiva gutha* that the god Shiva was worshiped by the Sinhalese people from the time before the 3rd century BC (Paranavithana:1929.327).

The names of Buddhist worshippers as mentioned in these three Brahmins inscriptions from 3rd Century BC up to 1st century BC period such as *Bamadatha (Brahmadatta, Gopala, Kana, Krishna), Maha Shiva, Mahasena, Rama (Rama) Shiva bathi, Shiva guthi, Shiva rakta, Vesavana (Vishravana)*, were reflected the knowledge about the Vedic Hindu Gods as well as *Shiva* in aforementioned period of Sri Lankan people. Paranavitana speculates hitherto as for evidence still discussed, these people were earlier followed Hindu customs and beliefs, then they converted into Buddhism after the third century BCE (Paranavitana 1970.Vol. I, CXXIII-CXXIV).

“*Visadeva*” appears in another inscription as a code name. (JRAS (CB) NS, Vol. 59.part II, 2014), an example of the ancient Sinhalese belief in *Sivagama* is that the word “*Velu*” (CJSG. II: 225, No.745) in the scriptures means “*vail*” in the language. One of Shiva’s sons, *Murukan*, is called “*velusu*” because he bears the spear. Thus, the connection of the word *velusu (parumaka velusu puta parumaka pusa devaha lene)* in our inscriptions to *murukan* (JRAS (CB) NS, Vol.II, 132; No.54) seems to be a definite explanation. If those who used the code names “*Velu*” and “*velusu*” were not followers of *Sivagama*, then it is fair to say that they at least belonged to families that practiced the same religion (Ellawala: 2002, 144).

Another crucial evidence recorded in the 2nd century BC inscription is the personal name of *Vasudeva* (Ellavala: 1962, 145), a devotee who lived at that time. The name *Vasudeva* means Hindu *Ganesha* or *Krishna*. Therefore, it can be concluded that the people of Sri Lanka may have known *Shiva* as well as *Ganesha* from the pre-Buddhist era. The *Pali Atthakatha* text named *Dhamma Sangani* written by Buddhagosha in 5th century AC, Mentioned an institute named *Vasudevayathana*, also given an idea about the temple constructed for god *Vasudeva* alias *Ganesha*, (Ellawala:2002.145) thus a Person who beared that name known about the meaning of that word and have an idea about the good God *Ganesha*.

The early historic period from 250 BC to 300 CE.

Firstly, we would like to give the attention about the religion followed by the Tamil people who lived in that forgiven period in Sri Lanka and the impact directly offered on their religious environment due to the relevant political incidence. According to the Mahavamsa of the 3rd century BC, the people of Sri Lanka had only a few years to convert to Buddhism, and *Sena* and *Guttaka*, two Tamil horse traders, overthrew the king of Sri Lanka and ruled impartially for 22 years (MV: 21.11; Paranavitana, 1959.104; Indrapala, 2005, 157). One edition of the Mahavamsa, it has been recorded of *Sena* and *Gutthaka* believed in the doctrine that sin are washed away by water, and in order to carry out their secrets ablutions without having to go far, they diverted the course of the river of Kdamba (Malwathu oya) to run by the side of the city of Anuradhapura, was their (Paranavitana,Ibid 144;Indrapala Ibid,157) Centre of power. Previous scholars have suggested that this may indicate they followed Brahminical rituals (Senevirathne: 1985.523) in fact, the chronicle states that *Sena* and *Gutthaka* reigned justly. In this way

we could be able to suggest that the Tamil and Sinhala people lived in Anuradhapura, they followed Hinduism and Buddhism in equal status.

King Asela, the successor of king Surathissa ruled for ten years until Elara, a Tamil prince from Chola country, seized the kingdom and reigned for 44 years (Mahavamsa:21.14). However this may be, the princes of Devanampiyathissa's house lost control of the northern half of the Island not many decades after his death; and Buddhism, for the time being, ceased to enjoy the privileged position which that monarch had accorded it in his dominions. The incursion of Tamils at this period was perhaps not unconnected with the decline of the Mauryan Empire after the death of Ashoka. After withdrawal of the Maurya power from South India would have given political adventures from that region the opportunity to try their fortunes in this Island (Paranavitana, 1959.144). Elara reigned 44 years before the period of 161 BCE, in this period credence of the Jainism has been activated which contemporary Hinduism, due to political patronage had given by the Elara's chiefdoms and was the decisive factor for this, was the devotee of Jain saint Thiruvalluvara (Vavwage: 2005.90). Vavwage believes that Elara's ambition is to dravidization of the island. Therefore religious and multiple racial amalgamation culture occurred in this second century BC period due to reason of the South Indian Tamil people seems to have been migrated to Sri Lanka by in groups and settle down of proliferated in Northern, North Central and Eastern provinces, as well as large Tamil armed personnel who stationed specially in Northern and Eastern provinces. The situation was likely more dominant than the conditions that arose during the period of *Sena* and *Gutthaka*. Finally Elara's mastery reached its climax, through in his political and military mission had been undertook aforementioned provinces and furthermore captured interphase along the river bank of Mahaweli area from Vijayapura in Polonnaruwa up to far Southern foremost historical battlefield named Mahiyanganaya. Elara thus stopped the military units led by his generals from taking control of the territories (Mahavamsa: 25.7). Chattha, who was a general of Elara, chief in charge at the region Mahiyanganaya, from there he conducted the battle against Buddhist Sinhala hero Duttagamini. However Dighabhaya who was a Sinhala Buddhist chiefdom, join with Elara's forces in his political campaigns (Mahavamsa:25.12) nevertheless Malayadesa alias upcountry and its South and South Western provinces have not been compound to dominion of Elara, those areas were controlled by the Single Buddhist princes (Vavwage 2005.112).

Eventually, the political power of Rajarata, the largest Buddhist kingdom in the island, came under the complete control of Elara, and his religious and administrative policy was implemented almost uniformly during this period, based on the policy of reconciliation between the Buddhist-Sinhala people and the non-Buddhist Tamil-Hindu devotees. When Elara appointed Sinhala Buddhists for his council as the ministers (Mahavamsa: 21.13-34) was given a clever path to fulfill this wish of religious reconciliation in his reign. Elara visit to Buddhist monks at Segiriya (Mihintale) East of Anuradhapura city, for upholding royal customs, while when he come back, by his vehicle knocked down on a stupa, at once his Buddhist officials gave instructions for repair that damage (Ibid.21.13-

34). The Mahavamsa record of this event is that it continues to sponsor Buddhist monks, and Vavwage points out that under his sovereignty he seeks to seize the opportunity to spread Jainism with Hinduism over the Buddhist population living in Buddhist areas (Vavwage: 95,105). Even though there is evidence to suggest that both religions were practiced by the common people and the ruling class at the same time. In fact, the villages in these areas inhabited by Tamil civilians are named after the Tamil generals who were empowered to protect these villages (Vam: 376). The facts are related to the Elara's military strength which compiles brigades, generals and fortresses are express in Mahavamsa and Vansaththappakasini, likewise thirty Tamil chiefdoms with their servants, the military cadres with their families station within 32 fortresses and twenty chieftains with their assistance and families who were adjacent to the Elara's army, from this data we able to suggest large Tamil population has been lived at that time in the Zone between area from Vijithapura up to Anuradhapura (Mahavamsa: 25.10-15, 46, 66, 78). Meanwhile Tamil city name *Girilaka* situated near Vijnapura which is highlighted in the chronicle (Mahavamsa: 25.47; Vansaththappakasini: 380). The Mahavamsa epic, written about seven centuries after Elara's reign, convinces us that there were several Tamil chiefs in the Northern Province in the 2nd century BCE. These Tamil civilians were a critical point for paving the path for Dravidization of Sri Lanka in this age (Indrapala: 2005.159-160).

The chronicles recorded four folktales relating to the just rule of Elara (Mahavamsa, .Xxxi.15-34). The underlying purpose that gave rise to these legendary stories is clear, namely to illustrate the fairness and justice with which the king ruled his kingdom. Indrapala has given further comments about the author of these folktales, a prophecy which is indeed admirable that a Buddhist monk living in Anuradhapura almost seven centuries after the rule of Elara considered it important to conclude these four stories in his account of this ruler's reign. On the one hand, it shows the strength of the folk tradition during Elara's reign, and on the other hand it is a measure of a reasonable mind and the author's lack of prejudice. Accordingly, it appears that Ven. Mahanama Thera has submitted a just document on the rule of a non-Buddhist and non-Sinhala ruler (Indrapala: 2005.158). Furthermore Elara's love of justice is said to have been stronger than the natural affection he had for his own son. As well as the chronicles describe his rule of even justice toward friend and foe. Stories related of his love of justice, which was so great as to compel even the gods to rain in due season, are also narrated in Tamil literature in connection with a mythical Chola king, Manu Chola (Paranavitana: 1959.145). Nevertheless Dipavamsa, the Chronicle compiled earlier more than hundred years after Mahavamsa, mentions king Elara reign over 40 years with justice (Dipavamsa: 242.50). Eventually we are able to surmise that the faith of Jainism and Hinduism assimilated into the Sinhala Buddhist society, were coalesced religious faiths with Buddhism, it was the precedent religion which received patronage from Elara. Therefore, in consequence of these foregone historical facts, the Hindu Buddhist religious reconciliation seemingly built up in the periods of *Sena* and *Guttika*, and *Elara* in 2nd century BCE.

Another famous Hindu god *Skanda Kumara* and its belief popular in Sri Lanka as the god of Kataragama, mostly in ancient Ruhuna of Southern Sri Lanka. The creed

of this god has been evidently proved that it was generated in this same era. The earliest records revealed of this faith by oral tradition, that the king Duttagamini (161-137BCE), got vow for god *Skanda* at Kataragama before he proceeded the historic war against the Tamil king Elara. After successful completion of war and released the vow, Built the shrine for god *Skanda* at Kataragama (Dharmadasa and Thundeniya: 1994, 168), David Blandale quoted this story, from the primitive source named *Skandamala* (Blandale: 1997, 128). Pathmanathan stated that the names *Vishakha* and *Kumara* mentioned in Brahmī inscriptions between 1st century BCE to 1st century AC period, are personal names adapted for devotees of *Skanda Kumara* (Pathmanathan: 2006,350). The indirect reality of this we should understand that not only the general public as well as the king himself also followed the Hindu beliefs in this period. Therefore that kind of Hindu religious belief strongly assimilated into the Island's Buddhist society at the aforementioned period of 44 years reign by King Elara. Ananda coomaraswamy commented that Elara was the pious patroner of god *Skanda* (Kumaraswami: 1962.1).

In the period of three decades after the death of king Duttagamini, the Mahavamsa records that 7 Tamils arrived with an army from South India, defeating the king Vattagamini Abhaya (103 BCE), and ousted from the throne, they were usurpers of the Anuradhapura kingdom, of the seven, five sat on the throne (103-89 BCE), one after the other, and ruled for 14 years. Sinhala king Vattagamini who recaptured the throne when at 89 BCE and ruled till up to 77 BCE (Mahavamsa: 33.102) in this entire period the Hindu -Buddhist religious reconciliation seemingly backlash due to the enigmatic and misconduct activities occurred by these Tamils.

The period from early 2nd century AC, onwards some pious kings were like Gajabahu (114-136 AC) and Kanitthatissa (167-186 AC), declare their religious policy reflected more equality style, Gajabahu went to South India as an enemy of Chola ruler, he must have considered Cera king as his ally, his presence at the consecration of a shrine in that country, and his introduction into this Island of the worship of the goddess Pattini favoured by the Cera, thus appears plausible.

According to the Tamil epic poem named Silappathikaram, was composed in the 2nd century, which contemporary to the Gajabahu's reign, of which the subject matter is the story of Kannagi, deified as Paththini, refers to Gajabahu of Ceylon as named Kayavagu. He is said to have been present on the occasion when Senguttuvan, the Cera king constructed a shrine in honour of Pattini. In the Sinhala ballads, as well as late Sinhalese historical work the Rajawali, Gajabahu is said to have brought to Sri Lanka, The anklet of the Goddess Paththini (Paranavitana: 1959.184). Hereafter Gajabahu is the hero of a considerable cycle of Sinhalese ballads and folk-tales connected with the cult of goddess Pattini, still an important element in the religion of the Sinhala Buddhist.

In view of the reference in the reference of the Silappadikaram, stories which state that Gajabahu undertook a military campaign in South India, overawed with the Chola king and brought back to the island, not only the Sinhalese who were taken captive

there in the reign of his predecessor, but also 12000 men from the Chola as kingdom as reprisals. The Pujavali, 13th century poetic work, stated similar story about this incident, if we consider these ballads on their own merits, Cannot be regarded as altogether baseless (ibid,184).

Adhikaram pointed out these large gathering of Tamil captives settled in the Island, with kings patronage in consequence of it several Hindu believes such as Kartikeya defined as Skanda letter alias god of Katharagama, Pattini, Vishnu and Natha derived from Vedic origin, firmly integrated and intermingle to the Single Buddhist culture (Adikaram: 2003.211). Earlier the Abhayagiri Vihara and its stupa had been founded by King Vattagamini, Stupa in this monastery Gajabahu had enlarged. The earliest phase of the Wahalkada or frontispiece entitled this enlargement works of that stupa, as well as stone sculpture of Surya Deva and *Kuvera* also including this originate phase of its construction. The stone carving of *Kuvera* alias Vishrawana depicted on the stale of the frontispiece at the Tissamaha stupa at Dakkhina Vihara (Mv: 33.90) when including to the latter period of aforementioned representations. The figure of *Kuvera* in this scene, seeming a noble it wears a garment covered one shoulder and Keep up a large stomach and below this figure appear a servant who collecting coins, and from this the Hindu god Kubera for wealth and prosperity in make connection with the mythical philosophy of Hindu pantheon reflected from this entire scene (Edwards: 1976).

Paranavitana concludes the Gajabahu's name is associated with non-Buddhist cult which the orthodox members of the Buddhist church in Sri Lanka do not appear to have received with favor (Paranavitana; 1959.185). The author of Mahavamsa, concern mainly with the fortunes of the Mahavihara, have therefore dealt with the career of Gajabahu, the supporter of their rivals, in a perfunctory manner, and were not disposed to be eloquent about his non Buddhist religious achievement. These may have been considered by the later chroniclers like Rajavali and Pujavali compounds respectively in 13th and 17th centuries, as in even-handed manner due to the comparable reconciliation religious behavior adhere to the nation.

When in connection with the ancient composer studies in Sri Lanka, early second century AC period was the most intrinsic archaeological factors are noted, dealing with the region of king Kanittha Tissa, built frontispiece or building facade was placed in four cardinal directions of the stupa and adorned with the stone carvings in which reflect the religious requirements of non-Buddhist and Buddhist pilgrims, who were lived in that period. These stone and masonry embodiments on the frontispiece reflected an idea about the coalesced syncretism in between pre-Buddhist beliefs and Buddhist philosophical thoughts. Revivalism of the pre-Buddhist Naga emblems with the characteristics of Brahmanic and divine fable figures such as Surya Dava, Brahma and *Yaksha* chief Vaishravana able to identify properly (Paranavitana; 1964.240).

From the first century to the second century CE, an image of the god Ganesha and his assistant dwarf was created at the top of the northern front of the Kantaka Chetiya,

or Wahalkada, at Mihintale (Paranavitana: Ibid, 240; Paranavitana, 1935.4-6; Elawala: 2002). 144- 146), another *Ganesha* statue is also carved on the eastern side of the stupa. The *Ganesha* stands on Northern frontispiece had been embossed by a procession made by several dwarf alias *Bairava* figures, was the Hindu mythical creation in connection with the paternity of *Kuvera*, in this depiction they carried some mythical objects such as Palm leaf, *laddu* and a mango for offer to God *Ganesha*.

Earliest Ganesh figures revealed in India, allocated to the time period of 1st century BCE (Sircar: 1942. Vol,I,90-91), almost contemporary with the aforementioned Sri Lankan creations liken with carvings of the South Indian Amaravati and further stone emblems revealed from the Maurya and Sunga periods (Paranavitana:1964.240).

Therefore in consequence of Hindu Buddhist religious intermingle practical experiences the foregone sculptures such as *Ganesha*, *Kuvera* and several other Hindu mythical carvings assimilated into Buddhist pilgrimage places, most outstanding among these the stupa reveal the most oldest sculptural presentations in Sri Lanka relating our hypothesis.

Media of currency and relevant other commercial activities conducted by Sinhala and Tamil merchants altogether, when the early Anuradhapura era, moreover is subject to discuss the milieu of Hindu Buddhist with its reconciliation. The copper and bronze coinage named *Laxmi* plaque has been found in many archaeological places and was practiced in between the period of first century BCE to second century AC in the island (Parker:1903.466-469;Kulatunga:2015.238-239). Lakshmi was the spouse of the God Vishnu, and has received homage as traditional gods for prosperity from the people of Lanka since from 3rd Century BC up to second century AC. As stated in the Hindu myths exemplified by the embodied figure on the top side of the coin in some instances Lakshmi anointed by two elephants.

We able to confirm the Hindu temples of Brahmanic reign have been safely function from pre Buddhist time till up to beginning of king Mahasen's reign (276 AC-303 AC), chronicle comments king demolish the shrines those were utilized for observe rituals on divine Hindu characters (Mahavamsa: 37.40),as well as Vamsatthappakasini latter compiled for Mahavamsa, further mentioned this king destroyed the shrines, in Gokarna in Eastern province and Eracavilla and Kalandaka in Rohana, Southern province (ibid.685), in those housed Shiva linga (Vam:502), therefore has been introduced as institutions were followed superstitious ideology. After dismantled these shrines and he built Buddhist vihara's in these places were in connection with Mahayanism, was the religion compound the heterodox teachings, against fore it arose resistance from orthodox Buddhist Institute, Mahavihara (Mahavamsa:37,3-9:), from this information quoted from Vamsatthappakasini, alludes the phallic worship have been spontaneously continue since pre- Buddhist time to beginning of king Mahasen's period (Rahula: 1984.49). Paranavitana's hypotheses on this religious propensity, is the Dravidian people of South India a very close neighbors of the people of Lanka, and if We consider the phallic

worship is the major religious faith of Hindus, deliberately surmise that disposed the phallic worship before they embraced Buddhism (Paranavitana:1929.327)

Therefore as yet the religious reconciliation, that was the political policy, have been accepted by many previous rulers, even though there is a seeming backlash in the period of king Mahasen (276-303 AD) who does not follow the equality policy as the Buddhist king of Lanka. Our conclusion on the religious milieu of Mahasen's period alike plausible with the Pathmanathan's comments as this hostile religious activities of Mahasen (276-303 AD) against the Hinduism and Brahminical shrines, verily had not in sense general religious policy of all Buddhist Kings seeming obviously they had given their patronage in favor of Hindus and their religion with the Brahmanical temples.

Conclusion

These Hindu deities may have been considered obedient to the Supreme Buddha and contemporary kings may have added their representations to their Buddhist shrines. These deities were included in a section related to the stupa built to represent the supreme Buddha, with the intention of stating that they were devotees of the Buddha and therefore that their power could be applied to people who believed in the Buddha. The result of this union may have been that the Vedic deity *Varuna*, an ancient national deity of the Sinhalese, was made the protector of Ceylon (D.ni: 2008.62) and another such deity, Yama, was made a worshiper of Sri Pada at the top of the Sumana kuta. The stories of the arrival of the Supreme Buddha in Sri Lanka to subdue the demons and snakes (*Nagas*) associated with the beliefs of the common people may also have originated from the movement to convert the pre-Buddhist faith to Buddhism. The result is that the inscriptions of this period after the second century do not mention the Brahmins, who had greatly influenced kings and commoners in earlier times. Sacrifice dances and music, and sometimes drama, which were an important part of the worship of the deities and which were generally highly loved by the people, were associated with stupa worship during the reign of king Bhatika Abhaya (22 BC - 7 BC). (Dipavamsa, 253.36) It may have helped to draw the minds of the people who used to go to the temples frequently towards Buddhist places of worship. (Paranavithana, 1964.240)

Some scholars already conclude this was such a Hindu impact on the Sinhala Buddhism, but it would be very difficult to explain that depend on one handed mind, rather without a knowledge on the ethnic behavioral patterns spontaneously activated in between the two ethnic groups such a Sinhala Buddhist and non-Buddhist Tamil since pre-Buddhist time. The most suitable way to discuss the significance is based on the influence that has been generated as a consequence of the cross-cultural impressions reflected by social and cultural embellishments in Sri Lanka. If we need to reach satisfactory and even-handed conclusions it must be applicable to theories like time and space which are popular for making hypotheses in the fields of historical archaeology.

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Introduction to Comparative Models for Innovation Theory. (Review of Chapter 14; Introduction to Modern Economic Growth by Daron Acemoglu, 2008)

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Abstract:

This review paper introduces basic endogenous technological change models based on comparative innovations with research and development (R&D). Mainly this paper explains three endogenous growth models. Those are The Baseline Model of Competitive Innovations, One-Sector Schumpeterian Growth Model, and Step-by-Step Innovations Model. The methodology of this paper based on the review paper structure and referenced to the book: Introduction to Modern Economic Growth by Daron Acemoglu written in 2008. Also, qualitative review concepts have meaningfully integrated into this study. This review has identified, these models were relatively interconnected with the R&D and Innovations. These all models have identified technology is generating new machine, and machines are working in the production process with skill labors in R&D field. Machines have been utilizing in production. It has been working to either improve the quality of an existing product or lower production costs. However, innovation is not the same as creating machines. Because innovation has been increasing quality and reducing costs in the production using the replacement impact, which should be more involved in the Research and Development process (R&D) than those who make just machines. In conclusion, the replacement impact has based on the previous version of the technology. Simply replacement impact is a comparative replacement. This replacement has based on the R&D. Therefore, this deference is made by comparative innovations.

Keywords: *Baseline Model, One-Sector Model, Step-by-Step Model*

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Introduction

Technological advancement does not always imply the addition of new products or machinery. It also emerges of higher-quality productivity. These quality products are a mandatory condition for the economic growth of a country. Innovation is the process of practices. Global production practices are generating innovations. These practices are a continuous process of the development of vintage production. Vintage production is old technology used productions in the firms. Innovation is comparative development of the replacement impact of the vintage technology or machine. For Example, if you introduce a higher performance computer into your production process, it will work much effectively than your vintage computer. This change has identified by the continued practices in the production field. Therefore increase in the varieties of computer types is important since economic growth is driven precisely from the production function. Simply, Innovations have been driving by the economic growth in the future positive economics. Therefore, this paper illustrates developing tractable models of economic growth with competitive innovations. Furthermore, this paper presents fundamental models of competitive innovations, which were initially introduced by Aghion and Howitt (1992) and then further extended by Grossman and Helpman (1991a,b) and Aghion and Howitt (1992;1998). Also this study presents these models in a way that replicates the mathematical structure of expanding varieties models, emphasizing the similarities while also highlighting the contrasts.

The literature presents a baseline model of competitive innovations based on Aghion and Howitt's work (1992). Segerstrom, Anant, and Dinopoulos (1990), as well as Grossman and Helpman (1991), developed similar models (1991a,b). Aghion and Howitt (1998) present a comprehensive overview of different Schumpeterian economic development models and their expansions. Uneven growth and prospective growth cycles have discussed by Aghion and Howitt (1992). Aghion and Howitt are the first to investigate the impact of creative destruction on unemployment (1994). Francois and Roberts (2001) and Martimort and Verdier (2001) address the consequences of creative destruction for firm-specific investments (2003). In Aghion, Harris, Howitt, and Vickers (1999) and Aghion, Harris, Howitt, and Vickers (1999), step-by-step or cumulative advances were studied (2001). Acemoglu and Acikigit (2006) give a simplified version of their model, which includes a comprehensive study of the consequences of intellectual property rights regulation and licensing in this class of models. More competition may stimulate economic growth and technical advancement, according to Blundell (1999), Nickell (1999), and Aghion, Bloom, Blundell, Griffith, and Howitt (2005). Greater competition may increase development in step-by-step models of invention, according to Aghion, Harris, Howitt, and Vickers (2001) and Aghion, Bloom, Blundell, Griffith, and Howitt (2005). Another factor for expansion, according to Aghion, Dewatripont, and Ray (2000), is competition. Competitive forces boost management incentives and efficiency in their model.

Today growth economics have mainly based on quality and cost-effective products. For that R&D, comparative innovations and technology-based production have been

taking the key role. Therefore this paper has generated a significant introduction for the readers to flow up the main reference for their studies.

1. The Baseline Model of Competitive Innovations

The assumptions have based on the close economic conditions. The economy has been working with R&D and expanding the machinery. The model has revealed the fundamental economic differences that arise as a result of competitive innovations. Time (t) has given in continuous conditions. Population is constant at L and labor is supplied by constant amount in given time (t) Machines used to produce final goods.

$$C(t) + X(t) + Z(t) \leq Y(t) \quad 1$$

Where $C(t)$ is consumption, $X(t)$ is aggregate spending on machines, and $Z(t)$ is total expenditure on R&D at time t .

If the machines have not expanded, the input rate is equal to 1, quality of the machine line is $v \in (0,1)$, and innovation is the engine of the economic growth. Innovation works for improving the quality of machines. Let $q(v, t)$ be the machine line quality at time t . For each machine type, we assume the following “quality ladder.”

$$q(v,t) = \lambda n(v,t) q(v,0) \quad 2$$

Number of innovations are represented by $n(v,t)$ and $\lambda > 1$. These innovations are working in the machine line, machine line situated between time 0 and t and $\lambda > 1$. Innovations have been improving the quality of the machines, and it is the leader of economic growth. Under these conditions, aggregate production function has derived. It has given below,

$$Y(t) = \frac{1}{1-\beta} \left[\int_0^1 q(v,t) x(v,t/q)^{1-\beta} dv \right] L\beta \quad 3$$

If v is quality of the machine and q is the quantity of used for the production $x(v,t|q)$ is the total quality machines have used for the production. Herewith, apply an assumption, any given time quality level has not changed. The equilibrium level represents the higher level of quality machines that have used.

New machines have invented by the R&D. Also new Machines have developed according to the grid of the vintage machine difficulties. Ex; v is machine line. It has $q(v,t)$ at a given time t . R&D has been working for the improvement of the quality of the v . Let suppose the firm has spent $Z(v,t)$ units for the final good. Then production function generate $nZ(v,t) / q(v,t)$ innovations. These innovations are the leader of the economic growth and quality of the productions.

There were some critics of this model. The main criticism is this model has not applicable to developing countries. Because of that, R&D is an expensive task for

developing countries. Therefore this model is relatively applicable for the advanced economies in the world. Also, R&D cost is a higher risk for new firm in the economy. Because R&D makes benefits in the last stage of the production process. Simply last stage means, the firm can replace their machines with themselves. A new firm in the economy cannot be replaced by machines themselves in a short time.

2. A One-Sector Schumpeterian Growth Model

This section discusses a model more closely related to the original Aghion and Howitt (1992) thoughts. The previous model has based on the quality improvement of the machines. Also, innovations have been working as a factor of the production inputs. But this model explains labor supply of the R&D field in the production process.

Let us assume that, same previous assumptions have grounded here. Also rational propels are working in the market. Only deference that consumers are risk neutral. Under that conditions, aggregate production function is given below,

$$Y(t) = \frac{1}{1-\beta} x(t/q)^{1-\beta} [q(t)L_E(t)]^\beta \quad 4$$

$q(t)$ is the quality of the machine in production. But deference about the previous model and this, these machines have labour access. It calls labour-augmenting a unique machine. $x(t/q)$ is the quantity of this machine given at time t and $LE(t)$ denotes the amount labor used in production at time t , which is less than L , since $LR(t)$ workers will be employed in the R&D sector. According to these conditions, equation 5 explains the market clearance request,

$$LE(t) \mid LR(t) \leq L \quad 5$$

Machines are involved in production at the constant marginal cost ψ in terms of the final good. After that point, production has been continuing by the labors using R&D and innovations. In particular, each worker employed in the R&D sector generates a flow rate η of a new machine. When the current machine used in production has quality $q(t)$ the new machine has quality $\lambda q(t)$ Simply, after the point of the $\psi \equiv 1 - \beta$, Production has been governing by the skilled labors working in the R&D field. As a result, this study shows that the core findings of Aghion and Howitt's (1992) one-sector Schumpeterian model are quite similar to the baseline model of competitive innovations presented in the previous section.

3. Step-by-Step Innovations

This model is also highly appreciating the quality improvements of productivity. But deference is this model has undertaken innovation of any machine in the process. This means previous models have undertaken only innovations of the machines line in the productivity. But here this model has considered any machine in the process without

having developed any know-how on a particular line of business. This model is useful in providing a different conceptualization of the process of competitive innovations. Also analysis of the effects of competition and intellectual property rights policy. Consider time is continuous at given by t . Final productivities have allocated to economic contribution. Individuals with 1 unit of labour endowment populate the economy, which they offer inelastically. We assume that the instantaneous utility function has a logarithmic shape to make the calculations easier.

Let $Y(t)$ is the aggregate production at the given time t . Production has been working on the closed economy, and consumption has based on final good only. Which means $C(t) = Y(t)$. According to these conditions, economic growth function is given below,

$$g(t) \equiv \frac{\dot{C}(t)}{C(t)} = \frac{\dot{Y}(t)}{Y(t)} = r(t) - \rho \quad 6$$

The equation defines $g(t)$ as the growth rate, and $r(t)$ is the interest rate at date t . The final good Y is produced using a continuum 1 of intermediate goods according to the Cobb-Douglas production function.

$$\ln Y(t) = \int_0^1 \ln y(v, t) dv \quad 7$$

Equation 7 shows aggregate production, where $y(v, t)$ is the output of v th intermediate at time t . v is the final good price of at time t by $X(v, t)$. Where $y(v, t)$ based on the, $l_i(v, t)$ is the employment level of the firm and $q_i(v, t)$ is its level of technology at time t . This relationship is given below,

$$y(v, t) = q_i(v, t) l_i(v, t) \quad 8$$

This model explains, R&D and labor in the R&D field by the leader or the innovation. , also undertake R&D to catch up with the frontier technology. Because this innovation is for the follower's variant of the product and results from its R&D efforts.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this review paper introduces basic endogenous technological change models based on comparative innovations with research and development (R&D). Mainly this paper explains three endogenous growth models. These models were based on the "competitive innovations" to underline the role of company competition in both the invention process and the product market and labor in the R&D field. Competitive innovations result in a creative destruction process, in which new items or machines replace older versions, and therefore new enterprises replace ineffective ones. Also, technological progress does not always correspond to new products or machines. It emerges in many ways, R&D, skill labors working in the R&D field, and innovations are the key economic growth inputs in the future world. Also this study concludes the replacement

impact has based on the previous version of the technology. Simply replacement impact is a comparative replacement. This replacement has based on the R&D. Therefore this deference is made by comparative innovations. Finally, these models might provide useful frameworks for the analysis of a range of industrial policies, R&D policies for future positive economies.

This paper important for study for understanding positive economics with policies, innovative practices, and growth theories. Therefore this review paper has motivated researchers to study comparative innovation theory for future economic development.

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Anthropological analysis on the new trends and changes of Catholic system of belief and rituals (With special references to Chilaw, Sri Lanka)

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Abstract:

Christianity is a religion based upon the teachings and miracles of Jesus. It plays one of the main moves around *Chilaw, Nattandiya and Wennapuwa*, Sri Lanka. This research examines the new trends and changes of the system called beliefs and rituals in Christianity. Catholic is the main Church in this area, and due to various reasons, several changes occurred in their belief and ritual system. Prominent example is during their early practices using Latin as the official language, the community did not familiar with the church because of the language difference and after these changes, administration made native language as their main performing language. This explorative, descriptive study based on these faiths and their significant characteristics. In this research, the sample size is 40 and respective fathers, sisters, brothers, and devotees were purposively interviewed utilizing unstructured interview method. The main aim of this research is to provide an anthropological knowledge of the latest trends in Catholic beliefs and rituals, through the changes of Sri Lankan social system and Christianity using *Chilaw* as the research area. To accomplish this research, the researcher utilized interviews, observation, and participant observation. In this study, the researcher observed that the administration as well as the Catholic devotees are still protecting the physical cultural materials of the Church. Prominent characteristics in Catholic beliefs and rituals are changed and modified due to complex social and cultural changes.

Keywords: *Believes, Christianity, Catholicism, Denominations, Rituals*

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Introduction

Religion is one of the prominent concepts in the social sciences. Christianity is the religion one of the prominent topics that study, under various fields in social sciences. The word religion is derived from Latin “religio” used by the Romans, before Jesus Christ, to indicate the worship of the demons. Generally, the idea that emphasize from the concept of religion is that the belief in and worship of a superhuman controlling power, especially a personal God or gods. It is a fundamental set of beliefs and practices generally agreed upon by a group of people. These set of beliefs concern the cause, nature, and purpose of the universe, and involve devotional and ritual observances. They also often contain a moral code governing the conduct of human affairs. The comparative study of religion formed a central building block of anthropology as the discipline emerged in the nineteenth century and early twentieth century. Evans-Pritchard focuses on a single African case study, showing interrelations among religious, social, and political aspects of Azande life. The book assesses the logic and consistency of Azande modes of thought and indicates how they might be translated into the understandings of a Western readership (Anthropology of Religion: Definition, History, Themes -iResearchNet, n.d.).

Tylor defines Religion in his book, “Primitive Culture”, (1871) as “belief in spiritual things.” His characterization is terse in comparison with Durkheim’s assertion in his book *The Elementary Forms of Religious Life*. Durkheim defines that a religion can be seen as “a unified set of beliefs and practices relative to sacred things, that is to say, things set apart and forbidden beliefs and practices which unite one single moral community called a Church, all those who adhere to them” (Durkheim, 1912). This definition of religion as a certain kind of object of study therefore also points toward a specific method of study. Durkheim’s depiction of social order proved highly influential for the British anthropologist Alfred Radcliffe-Brown, who in the middle years of the century drew on such ideas in developing the notion of ‘structural functionalism’ a view of society as made up of, and stabilized by, interlocking and complementary components, including religious institutions. The emphasis on observable reality also informed Bronislaw Malinowski’s stress not on the evolution of religion, but on the importance of fieldwork in discerning the contemporary societal and psychological rationale behind ritual and magic. According to Clifford Geertz, Religion is a system of symbols which acts to establish powerful, persuasive, and longlasting moods and motivations (Geertz, 1973).

In Sri Lankan socio-cultural context, Buddhism plays one of the prominent protagonists. Gananath Obeyesekere and Richard Gombrich plays one of the most leading roles when considering the early works which attended to understand the changes of Sri Lankan Buddhism. Their controversial ideas on “Protestant Buddhism” built novel dimensions in religious studies in Sri Lanka and their theoretical aspects still utilized by scholars for their academic addresses. Obeyesekere and Gombrich (1988) pointed out the change in the cosmology and the creation of new religious roles which interconnected matters based on gods and other figures. Although they argued that strictly Buddhist ideas,

roles, and institutions have not remained unaffected by the new trends according to that period. Anyhow, their proposed concept called “Protestant Buddhism” caused novelty in the practices of Buddhism and prepared the field for a new term called “Applied Buddhism”. Sri Lanka has been conventionally considered a fort of Theravada Buddhism. According to Tilakaratne (2020) the organizational aspect of modern Buddhism, the sasana, comprising the four groups of bhikkus, bhikkunis and upasakas and upasikas, has undergone change. Pondering the new trends in Buddhism he highlighted about such concepts like, Trans-yanic Buddhism, American Buddhism, and Eco Buddhism (Green Buddhism). Amunugama (2016) besides underscored the contribution of Anagarika Dharmapala, Piyadasa Sirisena, John De Silva on the new trends of Sinhala Buddhism as well as the impact of theosophical society of Olcott. Although Christianity also playing one of the significant roles in Sri Lankan religious context.

Christianity as a tradition implicates the anthropologists in much more than the study of “a religion,” and while Asad’s approach to the study of Islam is methodologically sound, applying it to the case of Christianity involves specific challenges (Marshall, 2014). The anthropology of religion has become increasingly aware of how much of the supposedly “objective” tool kit of comparative concepts comes from Christian traditions and Christian ideas of what a “religion” is supposed to be (Hoskins, 2014).

Considering Christianity Holy Bible is the centre of the sources. The word “Christ” means anointed one. Christ is not Jesus’ last name. Jesus is the anointed one from God the Father who came to this world, fulfilled the Old Testament laws and prophecies, died on the cross, and rose from the dead physically. He performed many miracles, which were recorded in the Gospels by the eyewitnesses. He is divine in nature as well as human. Thus, He has two natures and is worthy of worship and prayer (O’uioiais ysñ” 2004).

This research was carried out under the research problem of how cultural diffusionism effected the Sri Lankan Christianity and what are the new trends and challenges caused by it. Considering the main objective of this research is to utilize the anthropology of religion knowledge to study about religions and understand the cultural anthropological perspective in religious studies. To provide a comprehensive knowledge on Sri Lankan Christianity is a specific objective of the study. Considering the previous studies conducted through the dimensions of Christian communities, insufficient of cultural anthropological perspective can be identified. Therefore, this research attempts to fill the gap in Sri Lankan anthropological point of view in Christian cultural aspects as well their behaviors.

When considering about the subjective value, this whole research was based on socio-cultural anthropology as well as the anthropology of religion. Through this research the researchers can identify about the theoretical valid and the practical usage of those aspects. Every natural science, social science depends on the development of knowledgeable consequences. Through these types of researches those knowledges can develop and clearly identify about misplaces of those works. When clearly stating about this research it’s a significance process of understanding a particular social and cultural

element. So through this effort, future researchers also can perfectly sort out their topics and other phenomenon from this project. When consider about practical importance of this research, through this research the society can identify about the hidden characteristics of Christian beliefs and rituals and their modern features. So it's quite importance and significance identify those cultural elements and other factors. This research is quite important for policy makers in government and private sectors. They can clearly identify about the characteristics those denominations and their beliefs as well as their rituals. So through those features those sectors can make proper policies and other facilities for those communities. It's very important to have a proper idea about these societies and their needs to accomplish government and private development projects.

Methodology

This research attends to explore about the evolutionary aspects of modern Christianity utilizing Chilaw as the research area. Justifying the reason for selecting Chilaw, is that it plays one of the prominent roles in Sri Lankan Catholic communities. To fulfil the objectives the researcher selected 3 churches from respective area and 40 amount of sample along with 4 categories of data contributors as fathers, brothers, sisters and devotees purposively.

Table 1: research area and sampling aspects

Research area	Purposively selected religious institutions	Purposively selected data contributors	Sample size
Chilaw, Puttalam District, North Western Province, Sri Lanka	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. St. Joseph Church–Chilaw 2. Shrine of Lourdes–Nattandiya 3. St. Joseph's Church–Wennapuwa 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Fathers ▪ Brothers ▪ Sisters ▪ Devotees 	40 (purposively selected)

Thematic analysis was utilized and qualitative data (as this is a qualitative research) was analyzed and identified the respective findings along with a scientific methodology. Data were collected by unstructured interviews, observation, and participant observation.

This whole study was based on some prominent theories in Socio-Cultural Anthropology like cultural diffusionism, and subculture theory. The main proponents of British school of Diffusionism were Elliot Smith, William J. Perry, and W.H.R Rivers. Generally, the meaning of this theory is the spread of cultural beliefs and social activities from one group of people to another. Consequently, when considering this research, it can clearly identify that people of Chilaw and other mentioned areas who belongs to Christianity gathered the cultural elements that were injected by outside cultures (Example: British colonization). Those cultural behaviors straight connected with this study because we can clearly identify some prominent characteristics from the people through these areas that changed their aspects on Christian belief and rituals (Your Dictionary, 2018). The

concept of subculture has a particularly strong, yet controversial trajectory in the social sciences in general and anthropology. The concept was formulated in early social theory to address a variety of sociocultural forms that are included in a totality, be it society or national culture. These forms could be the subdivisions of national culture, minority groups, immigrant or refugee populations, or rural/ semi-rural communities, for example. Many authors saw subcultures as both “cohesive social systems” and variants of a national culture, cultures within a cultural world. For instance, various community studies of rural populations were conceptualized as completely integrated systems, subcultures that are autonomous from the works of the nation-state.

Figure 1: Research framework

Results & Discussion

In *Chilaw* area, through the interviews the researcher identified following types of denominations.

1. Catholic Church
2. Anglican Church
3. Jehovah’s Witnesses
4. The Faith of the “flotsam and jetsam”
5. Bible Church

Catholic Church is the core of world Christianity. According to the interviews of this research, the researcher identified that the belief system of Catholicism is mainly

based on Holy Trinity and the Holy Bible. Majority of the world in Christianity believe in these elements. Additionally, the particular research area includes Anglican, Jehovah Witness, Jetsam, and Bible organization. Anglican Christianity, which stems from the Protestant Reformation, is one of the largest Christian traditions in the world. Moreover, its adherents have often exerted tremendous social and cultural influence, particularly in English-speaking countries. The name “Anglican” means “of England” but the Anglican Church exists worldwide. The Anglican Church, although it has apostolic succession, is separate from the Roman church. The history of Christianity has produced numerous notable separations. In 1054 came the first major split from Roman administration of the church, when the Eastern Orthodox Church and the Roman split apart. Jehovah’s Witnesses believe God is the Creator and Supreme Being. Witnesses reject the Trinity doctrine, which they consider unscriptural. They view God as the Father, an invisible spirit “person” separates from the Son, Jesus Christ. However, the researcher acquired that the prominent denomination is Jehovah Witness and the core centre known as the prominent Catholicism. Mainly, the prominent beliefs of these two divisions can mention as following.

The researcher found following beliefs as their main doctrines according to the church of Catholic. Trinity is one of their main believe and other than that, belief in Christ’s redemptive death, Jesus is both God and man, salvation by Grace, all men have the possibility of salvation, belief in Sacrifice of the mass, denomination has a valid ordination of priests, fidelity to the Pope as teacher of the faith, belief in the ability of the individual Christian to lose salvation, belief in distinction of sin, belief in equality of Holy Scripture and Holy Tradition, Bible canon contains 73 books including all seven books in the Septuagint canon, Baptism is normatively necessary for salvation, and belief in all seven sacraments of the Church are confirmed as prominent beliefs.

Considering the belief system of Catholic Church and Anglican Church, following type of features were identified by the researcher.

Table 2: Comparison of Catholic and Anglican beliefs

Belief	Catholic	Anglican
Trinity	√	√
Belief in Christ’s redemptive death	√	√
Jesus is both God and man	√	√
Salvation by Grace	√	?
All men have the possibility of salvation	√	√
Belief in Sacrifice of the Mass	√	√
Denomination has a valid ordination of Priests	√	X
Denomination has a valid consecration of the Eucharist and belief in the Real Presence	√	X

Fidelity to the Pope as teacher of the Faith	√	X
Fidelity to the Pope as Apostolic Primate	√	X
Belief in the ability of the individual Christian to lose salvation	√	√
Belief in distinction of sin	√	√
Belief in equality of Holy Scripture and Holy Tradition	√	?
Adherence and recognition of all the Church's Ecumenical Councils	√	X
Bible canon contains 73 books including all seven books in the Septuagint canon.	√	?
Baptism is normatively necessary for salvation.	√	√
Belief in all seven sacraments of the Church.	√	√

Interview method used for this research; overall, majority stated that their traditional belief system was not changed.

“Christianity does not change the rituals, worships, liturgical or other methods. We call them Doctrines. They do not change...”

Above-mentioned statement cited from the interview with the father from the Bishop House of Chilaw. He described that several denominations in the world defines the true meaning of Christianity according to their perspective. However, there can be different types of changes through prepared various documents.

“The Pope sends an exhortation paper. There may be differences in things. However; liturgical, rituals and beliefs do not change...”

Through an interview from another father, the researcher found some unique characteristics of Chilaw area Christianity. According to his statements, we can identify that the Christianity in Chilaw filled with unique cultural materials and prominent practices. This particular situation described by the respective father as following.

“Faith is a general thing. Catholicism in the entire world is in one platform. The Holy Trinity is one. There are unique cultural elements in Sri Lankan Christianity as well as Catholicism. Primarily, under the threat of the Dutch, St. Joseph Vaz tries to protect the Christianity in Sri Lanka. During that time, Rev. Fr. Jacome Gonsalves came to Sri Lanka. He is the founder of Sri Lankan Christian literature. His arrival will bring new things to Sri Lankan literature and culture. For example, the Song of the Psalms can be mentioned. The Chilaw area is very well known. In addition, he introduces dramas as a unique characteristic of Sri Lankan Christianity.”

Through this description, we can identify that the general belief system of Christianity is not changing easily but there can be different types of cultural elements and practices that adding to the core concept of Christianity. According to the theory of Cultural Diffusionism, these practices were acquired by Sri Lankan society. It is not a doubt to state that when the complex society is change numerous materials and practices are adding to any system of beliefs. According to the interviews of Christian devotees, following types of ideas were found.

“Traditional system of beliefs is not changing. As our grandparents today also, we come to the church on Sunday and participating religious observances...”

“No. The beliefs are not changing. As well as the ancient times people stick with the church and faith for the Christ is still in a good line...”

“There are no massive changes of evolutions in Christianity in this area. People still gather in church for their faith and respect. Doctrine is not changing...”

More than half of the interviewers stated that their traditional belief system is not changed. However, some argued that there were some changes occurred after the second Vatican council. Second Vatican Council, 21st ecumenical council of the Roman Catholic Church, announced by Pope John XXIII on 1959, as a means of spiritual renewal for the church and as an occasion for Christians separated from Rome to join in search for reunion. Authority, church, ecumenism, liturgy, and Roman Catholicism are some key topics that discussed in this council. The “Constitution on the Sacred Liturgy” establishes the principle of greater participation by the laity in the celebration of mass and authorizes significant changes in the texts, forms, and language used in the celebration of mass and the administration of the sacraments. In early rituals and practices of Christian society performed by using Latin as the official language. At that context, devotees did not connect rapidly with the church because they are not familiar with the language. After the Second Vatican Council, Christian administration agreed to perform the rituals and other practices from native language.

“The basic core system of Christianity has not changed. Different decisions were made, however, after the Second Vatican Council. One of the main reasons for this council was to discuss the challenges and action to face the main challenges, problems of Catholic Church. At that time, the Catholic Church was fierce enough to kill those who caused scientific revival. The whole of Christianity itself had a black stain due to these activities. In this congregation, the authorities made number of flexible decisions. They agreed to carry out rituals in their own language. Many of those who left the church eventually joined in due to this decision.”

According to the above-mentioned statement of a Reverent Father, we can identify that these types of changes caused directly as a prominent path for the development of Christianity in Sri Lanka. Other than these decisions, there were several activities that popular area in present days.

- Catholic people organize Dansals on Vesak Poya day.
- Giving beverages and other facilities during a Buddhist Perahera.
- Educational and economical supports for every type of groups.

Once a devotee point out the importance of Roman Catholicism which means, why should be important to be a Roman Catholic. To provide the information he cited apart from the Holy Bible as following.

“Go then to all people everywhere and make them disciples: baptize them in the name of the Father and of the Son and of the Holy Spirit and teach them to obey everything I have commanded to you. And remember, I will be with you always to the end of age.”(Mt.28:19-20).

According to the statement of the interviewer, following types of major points achieved as the significant characteristics of Catholicism.

- If the teachings of your Church differ from those Catholic Church, you can be sure that they are not of Christ but of another man.
- The Catholic Church gave to the world the Holy Bible with its collection of 73 books, which contains written and oral traditions.
- If reading the Bible alone is sufficient, how could those who lived before the Bible was printed and those who cannot read be saved?
- A study made in the Philippines reveals that there are approximately 30,000 different Christian sects and cults in the world. All these sects and cults have mushroomed only since the late 19th century. Can they all be right? There can be only one truth.

When stating about the conflict of Christian conflicts between these denominations of Chilaw area different types of opinions found through interviews. Various data resources stated various statements according to their faith. Following descriptions were present by these interviewers.

“No. There is no such thing. All teams are united. In Chilaw area several occasions are organizing by all of us...”

“It does not matter. However, various religions are conducting conversions around. There are bad images about each community due to these actions. At times, law and order violations occur...”

“Jehovah Witness is one of the main group that doing conversions around. Other than these organizations, Bible Group also conducting different programs to convert Catholic people into their religion...”

“Although there are usually no serious levels of Christianity among the Christian groups, the process of religious conversion is common in the area. As a result, there

are issues between Catholic and other fundamentalist groups. As an example, Jehovah Witness visit house to house in Mudukattuwa area and once they visited for a Catholic house and tried to convert them into Jehovah by providing various financial and other facilities. Catholic people got impulsive due to these activities; there was a conflict between particular groups. This situation was increased into civil law circumstances. So, there can be different types of conflicts because of these fundamentalist group activities... ”

“There are no conflicts between Christian denominations and every group of this area united and participating similar religious activities... ”

Another level of serious conflict occurs between the clergy and laity of some mainline a few liberal denominations. Many church members have been brought up to believe in heaven and in the literal truth of Jesus’ virgin birth, divinity, and resurrection. Some believe in the inerrancy of the Bible, and other historical beliefs. However, most clergy have attended theological colleges, and many have developed personal beliefs that reflect current liberal Biblical scholarship. They reject many of the traditional doctrines of the church. This produces a conflict among clergy, between their need to preach the truth as they see it, and their need to support the basic beliefs of their denomination and avoid controversy. In particular, area conflicts between these denominations are not in serious platform. The Vatican’s October announcement of a special process to admit Anglicans to the Roman Catholic Church raised questions for many who perhaps thought that “crossing the Tiber” would require a major shift in belief for Anglicans. The relationship between Anglicanism and Roman Catholicism, however, has always been somewhat different from the other Catholic-Protestant divides, which may make it easier for Anglicans to find a home in the Roman communion. Over the centuries, Anglicans have generally rejected the concepts of transubstantiation and papal infallibility and considered the Marian dogmas of Immaculate Conception and Assumption to be without sufficient warrant in scripture and tradition. Beginning in 1970, however, the Anglican-Roman Catholic International Commission has worked toward common statements of agreement on these topics. As late as the 1980s, there was some hope that the Church of England (if not the entire Anglican Communion) would enter full communion with Rome. Catholics and Jehovah’s Witnesses differ in many other teachings such as that related with afterlife. Catholics believe in eternal hell, heaven, and temporal purgatory. Good people would be allowed to enter the heavens by St. Peter and bad people would be forever punished in hell. On the other hand, Jehovah’s Witnesses believe that after death, the dead person would not feel, see, or experience anything until Jehovah’s Judgment Day, wherein a war would take place between Jehovah and his enemy Satan the devil. After that event, all dead people would rise from the graves and be with their loved ones again.

Considering the difference between the faith of youth and old generations, following statements provided by the interviewers. These answers are provided according to the ‘are there any differences between the faith of youth and old generations?’

“Normally there is a huge gap between the participation of religious observances in the church and old generation is usually connected with the church in every Sunday...”

“There is no difference between these two generations. There are youth organizations and elder organizations in the Church, which actively participate in various projects. Therefore, there are no reduction in the participation of youth and old generations...”

“Due to the complex society young, as well as the old ones are moving away from the Church. I think busy life is the main reason for these reduced participations...”

When consider about the main reasons for these reductions particular interviewers point out following types of statements.

- Busy life.
- Breakdown of the family.
- Militant secularism.
- Lack of spiritual authenticity among adults.
- The church’s cultural influence has diminished.
- The rise of a fad called “atheism.”

Considering the final statements of interviewers, following types of table can provide according to the research topic of Christian beliefs and their changes. Only five devotees were stated that the Christian belief are changed after the Second Vatican Council. Reverent Fathers also stated about the changes of Christian rituals and three of them agreed to it. Only two sisters were agreed for the statement and five of the devotees also agree with it. Majority stated that the whole system of Christian belief system and ritual system is not changed

Table 3: Number of interviewers according to statements

Interviewers	Christian beliefs are changed	Christian Rituals are changed	Christian beliefs and rituals are not changed
Fathers	-	3	2
Sisters	-	2	3
Brothers	-	-	5
Devotees	5	5	15

Conclusion

The study concluded that there had been no widespread alteration in the basic beliefs and values of the Catholic population in the area. Nevertheless, the decisions of the parishes of the Catholic Church in the past have confirmed the rise and fall of the present Catholic religion. New trends are emerging in contemporary Catholic society due to diffusionism as well as the popular culture that is emerging. Among these trends the participation of non-believers in various religious activities is prominent and significant.

Denominations of this area become a noticeable problem for Catholic Church because they perform conversion activities for people as well as native Catholics. Due to complex society and social and cultural change, busy life, there is a trend of moving away from spiritual life, although still people connected with the Church and participate in religious practices.

Chilaw diocese is well administrated by the authority and every father, sister, and brother is perfectly trained and educated to spread the religion around the area; although comparing with other denominations, families for Catholic Church have very large amount a due to these family's amount, fundamentalists have the perfect ability to spread their religion among these population.

As previously stated, diffusionism affected the modern-day Christianity of Sri Lanka as Catholicism, the main Christian denomination arise with popular practices. Although comparing to Popular Buddhism of Sri Lanka, Catholicism changes gradually. This research emphasize the importance of studying Christianity in Sri Lankan context and the importance of applying anthropological knowledge to identify the cultural aspects of a particular religion.

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An Archaeological Comparison of Late Medieval Non-Religious Architecture between Kerala and Sri Lanka

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Abstract:

Literary sources do not contain much information about significant events that took place in the history of a country, but it is not difficult to find them through archaeological sources. Although, it is difficult to confirm something that happened in history, it is possible if the information obtained from the archaeology matches any picture of the past in line with the sources of historical literature. This study of non-religious architecture in Kerala and Sri Lanka can be called a research of that kind. This study focuses on predominant similarities in non-religious architecture between Kerala and Sri Lanka with an archaeological perspective. The main purpose of this study is to show how an architectural tradition developed in the late medieval period is different from the architectural style used in Sri Lanka until then. Here the late medieval period after the 13th century and here the colonial period is also studied. In this study, the data was collected by conducting field visits to some of the chosen regions of Kerala and Sri Lanka, and the snowball sampling method was used to achieve this. The research required the study of a number of architectural textbooks as well as historical sources in parallel with archaeological sources. After classifying the collected data, the anomalies of the architectural features of the two zones were studied. The study concludes by examining the theoretical factors that contributed to the building of architectural similarities between Kerala and Sri Lanka.

Keywords - *Architecture, late medieval period, Kerala, similarity, Sri Lanka*

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Introduction

Archaeology is a scientific discipline but it also applies to the study of tangible and intangible things. Archaeologists examine the material culture in different times and spaces to understand human behaviours, and during their investigations, some similarities in these different times and spaces are encountered by archaeologists. When archaeologists discover the similarities in different contexts, they try to apply the theories or create new theories to get an idea about the reasons for such similarities. This study also focuses on predominant similarities between Kerala and Sri Lanka which is shown via an archaeological perspective. This study reveals undefined wondrous cultural admixtures between Kerala and Sri Lanka which is not yet studied in the field of archaeology. Above mentioned cultural admixture includes landscape, geomorphology, topography, natural environment, built environment, language, beliefs, customs, social organization, foods, arts and crafts. This study mainly analyses built environmental similarities with special reference to the non-religious architecture in both regions.

Methodology

It is important to mention the methods used in this study before discussing the findings. The researcher entered the field of Kerala without prior knowledge of the Kerala architecture or a prior understanding of the similarity of architecture in Kerala and Sri Lanka. Therefore, it was possible to make objective judgments about the ancient architecture and culture without temporary assumptions that were made prior to the study. Entering the field without prior knowledge, the snowball sampling method was used to collect the data. Based on random finds in a particular field, the researcher went to another field and collected data on ancient architectural creations in several districts of Kerala. Following the collection of data, the researcher next referred to the relevant literary sources. Afterwards, the data was duly classified in order to be analysed. Comparisons were then made following subsequent field studies conducted in Sri Lanka. The final assumptions were made by matching the archaeological facts with the literary sources as well as the theoretical ones. Accordingly, the following study was carried out.

Results and discussion

Ecological and historical relations

The historical connection between Kerala and Sri Lanka should first be understood before focusing on the similarities between Kerala and Sri Lankan non-religious architecture. Sri Lanka is an island in the central part of the Indian Ocean, south of the Indian subcontinent, and Kerala is a state located on the south-western part of the Indian peninsular. Despite their remoteness, the two regions have significant ecological similarities. Geological consideration shows that the creation of this similarity is not accidental. Sri Lanka, Madagascar and the western and south-western parts of the Indian peninsular were once a single region during the pre-Gondwanaland period. Geologists have hypothesized and calculated that the Trivandrum area of the Indian state of Kerala

may have also been a part of this single region that existed during the pre-Gondwanaland period (Dissanayake & Chandrajith 1999: 223) (Map No.01). The distribution of graphite as a mineral in the two regions has primarily influenced this idea (Radhika and Santosh 1995: 143-157).

The Similarity between Kerala and Sri Lanka is well illustrated in its biodiversity. According to global studies, 25 biodiversity hotspots have been identified worldwide; the central highlands of Sri Lanka and the Western Ghats of India are identified as two regions with similar characteristics (Myers, Mittermeier & Kent et al 2000: 853) (Map No.02). Before studying the cultural similarities of the two regions, it is important to understand that there are also physical similarities as mentioned above.

There is almost no source-based historical connection between Kerala and Sri Lanka but, there is evidence that there may be a pint-sized relationship between the two regions. This means that there is no historical source mentioning that a ruler of Kerala has ever made political interference in Sri Lanka. It can be assumed that this may have happened for two reasons. Kerala may not have had as much political dominance as the other dynasties that spread its power in southern India, so they may have had to defend their territory rather than invade a region far from their kingdom. The other reason is that, from time to time the areas of Kerala were conquered by the powerful neighbouring states and there was often no sovereignty over Kerala. Surprisingly, however, Kerala's culture remained independent until the European colonial period, and those independent cultural features became apparent in Sri Lanka as well.

The earliest evidence is that King Gajabāhu of Sri Lanka visited Cera (Kerala) and built a *Pattini Devalaya* there. This is mentioned in the *Silappadikāram*, a South Indian source (Silappathikaram 1991:21). However, other sources report that this was not a direct visit of King Gajabāhu to Kerala and that it happened with his Chola invasion. Furthermore, sources also, mention a relationship with a definite political face in the medieval ages. Many contemporary sources state the invader Kālinga Māgha brought troops from Kerala for his invasion. Sources such as the *Mahāvamsa*, *Pujāvaliya* and *Rājāvaliya* refer to this as 'Malala soldiers' (Mahāvamsa 2010:395/ Pujāvaliya 2015:724/ Rājāvaliya 1976:212). Malala soldiers mean Malayali soldiers or Kerala soldiers. Scholars such as Senarath Paranavitan and Ananda Kulasuriya agree with this view (Kulasuriya 1976; Paranavitana 1960).

The use of Kerala soldiers for warfare took place again during the Dambadeniya period. Rājāvaliya confirms that during the reign of King Parākramabāhu II, Jāvaka Chandrabhānu invaded Sri Lanka twice with Kerala troops (Rājāvaliya 1976:212). Thus, it is clear that the Keralites were a militant people and were recruited as mercenaries during the medieval ages.

Sources say that thousands of Kerala soldiers were brought to Sri Lanka during the aforementioned invasions. It is not clear whether the Kerala people returned to their

homelands. Ananda Kulasuriya is of the opinion that the rest of the group remained in the 'Vanni' region of Sri Lanka and that the leaders of the groups rose up as 'Vanniyār' (Kulasuriya 1976: 139-140). But it is difficult to accept the idea without confirming it from those studies and from multiple sources. However, it is not difficult to imagine that people of Kerala origin may have settled in Sri Lanka after the twelfth century.

Sources do not mention anything about Kerala after the early Dambadeniya period. Back in the Gampola Period a remarkable connection is found in the literary sources. Two major aristocratic families of this era established their administrative dominance, namely the minister 'Senālakādhikāra Senevirath' and the Minister of 'Alagakkonāra'. Sources state that the Minister Senālakādhikāra Senevirath belongs to the 'Menavara' clan. According to Paranavitana the word 'Menavara' comes from the Malayalam word 'Menavan' (Paranavitana 1960: 640-641; Caldwell 1956). This indirectly implies that the roots of this minister are connected to Kerala. With regard to Minister Alagakkonāra, it can be observed that there is also a close relationship with Kerala. According to the '*Kitsiri Mevan Kelani*' and '*Niyamgampāya*' inscriptions, it is stated that Minister Alagakkonāra was a descendant from 'Vānchi' (IC, Vol. VII 2014: 22-24). According to the Sangam literature, Vānchi is referred to as the capital of the Cera kingdom in South India and that this city is identifiable as modern Karāvar in Kerala (Somaratne 1975:50). It should be mentioned that the Vānchi clan is an aristocratic family of Kerala origin. Thus, direct relations with Kerala can be observed in the representation of the Gampola period.

The connection between the sources of Kerala and Sri Lanka can be traced back to the Kotte and Kandy periods. The *Girā Sandesha* written during the Kotte period mentions the Kerala soldiers (Girā Sandeshaya 2009: poem.27). Sources about Bandāras are found in the Kotte and Kandy periods. An aristocratic group called *Pantāram* lived in Kerala and it is a common feature between Dravidian and Sinhala languages that the letter 'Pa' becomes the letter 'Ba' and the letter 'Ta' becomes the letter 'Da'. Lona Devaraja confirms that the *Pantārams* and the *Banḍāras* are one and the same group. It is said that King Parakramabāhu VI brought an aristocratic group called *Pantāram* to this country around 1470-1478 AD (Devaraja 1997:69). *Sinduruvāna kadayimpota* has named Senālakādhikāra Seneviratha as '*Lankā Senevirat Bandāra Mahārāja*' (Codrington 1933:266). Therefore, it proves that the name Banḍāra was used before the Kotte era. Moreover, it confirms our argument by mutually confirming through sources that the Minister Senālakādhikāra has a Kerala origin. The idea makes more sense because Banḍāra is a first-time source for someone with a Kerala origin.

Analysing the historical relations mentioned above, it is clear that there were constant connections between the aristocratic family units in the two regions. It is clear that the centuries-old relations between the two regions may have contributed to the creation of cultural similarities as well as ecological ones.

Architectural similarities

The built environment can be identified as one of the main factors that characterizes the appearance of a culture externally. Architecture is one of the basic disciplines of built environment studies. The main objective of this study is to examine the features of non-religious architecture between Kerala and Sri Lanka and what factors contributed to such similarities. The buildings in Kerala and Sri Lanka on which this study is based belong to the late medieval period and also consider periodic renovations. The features identified in the participatory observations are studied here by comparing them with South Indian architectural texts. The book *Māyāmata* is used as the basis for this study. The *Māyāmata* is a *Vāstuśāstra*, that is to say a ‘treatise on dwelling and as such it deals with all the facets of gods’ temple dwellings, from the choice of a site to the iconography of temple walls. It contains many precise descriptions of villages and towns as of temples, houses, mansions and palaces. It gives indications for the selection of a proper orientation, of right dimension and of appropriate building materials. It intends to be a manual for the architect and a guide book for the layman.

The use of wood or timber architecture can be considered as a prominent feature of late medieval architecture in Kerala and Sri Lanka. According to Senaka Bandaranayake’s studies, woodwork in Kerala, North and South Karnataka, Konkan and Goa is very similar to that in Sri Lanka (Bandaranayake 2012:30). The secular architecture of Kerala and Sri Lanka focuses mainly on the construction of aristocratic houses and the construction of rural houses.

In Kerala as well as in Sri Lanka, the traditional feudal aristocracy of the past represented the superstructure of society. Due to their land ownership, monetary status and official power, they were able to design their residential buildings in a spectacular manner. Elite housing in both regions can be identified in three main forms.

- Traditional Kerala/ Sri Lankan elite houses
- Kerala/ Sri Lankan elite houses with Portuguese and Dutch influences
- Kerala/ Sri Lankan elite houses with mixed features

Kerala and Sri Lankan elite houses built during the pre-colonial period have some common features. These distinctive similarities are evident in the structures, roof, veranda and decorative elements of buildings made of wood and masonry. In terms of model, they are basically single and two-story houses. Architecturally, Kerala’s elite residential buildings are made up of four major forms (Thampuran 2001:23).

- *Ekasālā* (north Kerala model)
- *Ekasālā* (south Kerala model)
- *Kuṭṭikeṭṭu*
- *Nalukeṭṭu*

Focusing on *Ekasālā*, the North Kerala model seems to be the popular model found in both Sri Lanka and Thrissur and Wayanad areas above the Trivandrum district (Figure No.01). *Kuṭṭikeṭṭu* and *Nalukeṭṭu* models bear many similarities with *Walau* (elite houses) in the Sri Lankan upcountry. The *Nalukeṭṭu* model has been used in Kerala by second tier officials to the chief. In Sri Lanka, too, the elite houses of the second *Nilames* to the king are closer to the *Nalukeṭṭu* model (Figure No.02-06). Roofing of high walls with lime mortar is a common feature of all forms but, the basic shapes, appearance and veranda are different (Widiastuti 2013:41-53). According to the field surveys, pre-colonial two-story houses are rare in both regions.

It is important to pay special attention to the roof when focusing on similar features in elite houses. One of its distinctive features is the decoration at the end of the roof, especially when it comes to wooden rafters. According to the *Māyāmata*, these features of the roof rafters are called '*Niwra*' and '*Vishkambha*' (*Māyāmata* 1985: 101/ Widiastuti 2015:6-7). Ananda Coomaraswamy names these features as '*Gonäs*' and '*Hee leeya*' in Sri Lankan architecture (Coomaraswamy 1959:129). The curved ends of the roof rafters are called *Vishkambha* or *Gonäs* and the straight wood that extends from one end of the roof to the other is called the *Niwra* or *Hee leeya*. This feature is prominent in the elite houses of Kerala and Sri Lanka but this is not unique to elite houses (Figure No.7, 8). However, this was a mandatory feature of the religious buildings of the Gampola and Kandy eras in Sri Lanka and Kerala. Perhaps this is an inspiration from religious architecture in the construction of elite houses.

'*Soldara*' was another common feature used in the construction of elite houses in Kerala and Sri Lanka and this feature was used as another (upper) story of these elite houses. Although many researchers consider this to be an inspirational feature of Dutch architecture, it is confirmed that *Soldara* were used in Kerala even before the Dutch spread their dominance. The Nair aristocracy, a popular aristocratic family based in Trivandrum, Kerala in particular, has been built with a *Soldara* which is small in size (Figure No.09). These are designs made of solitary wood (Balakrishna, Padmanaban and et al 1982: 42-51). In appearance, participatory observations revealed that the *Soldara* in the upcountry of Sri Lanka were more similar to the *Soldara* in the houses of the Nair aristocracy mentioned above than with the Dutch influence. Although the features of the houses of these Nair aristocrats in the *Ehelepola Walawwa* near the Kandy Royal Palace are clearly represented, there are differences in terms of height (Ehelepola Nilame held the Maha Adhikāram of King Sri Wickrama Rājasinghe).

The wooden pillars, carvings, veranda, kitchens and *soldara* found in the houses of the Nair aristocracy bear many similarities not only with the secular buildings of Sri Lanka but also with the features of the religious buildings. Here it is important to pay attention to the door locks, key plates and handles of Nair aristocratic houses. Metal key plates, in particular, are square or circular, and come in a variety of designs. Those key plates are no different from Sri Lankan key plates. Ananda Coomaraswamy in his work of

‘Medieval Sinhalese Art’ has mentioned that a number of key plates can be found in many Kerala buildings (Coomaraswamy 1959:196-201).

Not only in aristocratic houses but also in religious buildings, there are commonalities of wooden pillars. According to the Māyāmata text, a pillar consists of a trinity of ‘*Potika*’, ‘*Sthambha*’ and ‘*Sthambhapeetha*’ (Māyāmata 1985: 103). In Sri Lankan architecture, these are known as ‘*Pekaḍa*’, ‘*Kanuwa*’ and ‘*Kanu pādama*’. Ananda Coomaraswamy also identified these wooden pillars as a unique architectural feature (Coomaraswamy 1959:129-132). These same features can be seen in the pillars with front gaps in the veranda of the elite houses but, the same pattern is often seen with regard to pillars not only in Kerala but also in other states of India. The similarity of the wooden pillars of Kerala and Sri Lanka can be felt more strongly due to the material from which they are made.

The similarity of the triangular roof and window sill faces are important as the aristocratic buildings of Sri Lanka are directly inspired by Kerala architecture (Figure No.10). Although some consider this to be a Dutch influence, these features were present in Kerala architecture before the arrival of the Dutch. This feature is distinctive in Sri Lankan upcountry as well as low country aristocratic exteriors. It can be assumed that the low country received this influence from the Dutch. This feature is prominent in many upcountry elite houses such as *Girāgama Walawwa* and *Iriyagama Walawwa* in Kandy as well as low country aristocratic houses up until the last century.

Ṭampiṭa Vihara can be identified as one of the outstanding buildings of late mediaeval religious architecture in Sri Lanka. Not only temples but also *Ṭampiṭa Ambalam* and *Ṭampiṭa Atu* are popular architectural forms of this period. *Ṭampiṭa Gabaḍā* (stores), which is similar to the Sri Lankan *Ṭampiṭa tradition* can be found in local aristocratic houses such as Cochin and Aleppy in the state of Kerala. Since both the Cochin and Aleppy regions are located in a lagoon environment, it is reasonable to assume that these may have been built in terms of utility rather than inspiration.

Similarities can be observed not only in the traditional features but also in the inspiring features of the architectural designs of Kerala and Sri Lanka. In this study, significant similarities were found primarily between the aristocratic houses in the Kottayam and Calicut district and the aristocratic houses in Sri Lanka. These are two-story buildings and it is made of bricks and plastered with lime mortar. These houses have a central courtyard that is not found in traditional Kerala houses and other remnants were found located around these central courtyards. It is clear that these buildings are inspired by Dutch as well as Tamil Nadu architects. This can be identified as a model that later became popular among the aristocracy in Kerala as well as in Sri Lanka.

The aristocratic houses found in the districts of Kottayam and Cochin (Ernakulum) are of totally Dutch influence (Figure No.11-13). The buildings in Galle Fort are completely identical to those found in Cochin Fort. This is not seen as strange, since the Galle Fort

and the Cochin Fort are of similar Dutch design. *Beeraḷu* carvings, large circular columns, lattice, windows and doors are the hallmarks of these buildings.

Similar features were found in aristocratic housing as well as rural housing in Kerala and Sri Lanka. Rural architecture has very different characteristics from those found in religious and secular architecture. It has common features not only in Sri Lanka and Kerala but in the whole of South Asia and beyond. These include simplicity, small size, use of organic materials, and spare exterior decoration. Based on the common features stated above, some similarities can be found in any village house. But some notable similar features can also be observed in rural housing associations in Kerala and Sri Lanka. The village house is discussed here in two main ways.

- Indigenous (Ādivāsi) village houses
- Non-indigenous village houses

Although there are many indigenous people spread all over Kerala, only the *Vādḍa* people stand out in Sri Lanka. This study also focuses on the indigenous people living in the Attappadi forest in Kerala and the *Vāddas* in Sri Lanka. The characteristics of the Attappadi forest are similar to those of the indigenous people of the hilly regions of cold climates such as Wayanad and Munnar in Kerala. Their livelihoods still depend on hunting and traditional industries but somewhat modernized features of the *Vāddas* can be observed as well.

Focusing on the form, the two-story roof of the indigenous village houses is often roofed with thatched roofs. These houses are made of clay and the house is divided into a veranda (*Piḷa*), house and kitchen. Inside the house there is no reservation of walls. Often the kitchen is designed to be separated from the main house but is made in close proximity. Except for the accessible part of the veranda, the rest is covered by a short wall. A special feature of the Attappadi forest is that the tribes form a cluster with their chief's house situated in the middle. The leader's house is designed to be slightly larger than the other houses. Even in the case of *Vāddā* villages like Dambana in Sri Lanka, its basic features are no different from the above-mentioned forms. There are a great deal of similarities in material, structures, and positioning. But these are similarities that are commonly observed among indigenous people, and cannot be thought to have been created on inspirational conditions (Figure No.14). However, in his book "The Prehistory of Sri Lanka", Siran Deraniyagala points out that the *Vāddā* culture in Sri Lanka is similar to that of the Kadar tribe in Kerala (Deraniyagala 1992: chap.6).

Considering the non-indigenous village houses, the traditional rural houses of the countryside can still be found in Kerala as well as in Sri Lanka. The word '*Chala*' is especially used to describe the ancient rural housing model of Kerala. Field explorations have shown that this model exists in one form in the southern part of the state of Kerala, in Trivandrum, and in another form in areas such as Wayanad in the north. Roofs with a high slope can be observed in the rural houses associated with Wayanad which are also

found in Sri Lanka (Panikkar & T.K. Gopal 1995: 32). The walls are commonly made of clay and lime mortar. Characteristics of Wayanad village houses could be seen in villages such as Meemure and Galataraya in Sri Lanka. It is a common feature in Kerala as well as Sri Lanka that later houses with thatched roofs were replaced by tiled roofs.

The kitchen model in Sri Lankan rural houses is very similar to that of the rural houses in Kerala than in other states of south India. The main feature is that the kitchen is designed close to the main house but separately. The ground level design of the fireplace is a feature of rural kitchens in Kerala as well as in Sri Lanka. A chimney (*Dummessa*) is created above the stove to dry meat and fish and to house pots. Creating a small platform and placing a grindstone on it is also a key feature. Spoon holder (*Handi āna*), pot holder (*Waḷan messa*) and mat holder (*Pāduru āna*) can be found inside these kitchens. Although these similarities can be observed in the two regions, it is difficult to say that there are as many similar features in rural architecture as in the aristocratic houses discussed earlier.

Reasons for the emergence of similar features in the elite houses of Kerala and Sri Lanka

There are different definitions of culture. The background to this study, too, is one form of culture. Here we look at the similar cultural characteristics found in two regions. It is important to theoretically examine the factors that contributed to this situation.

Power is a major factor in the origin, spread and breakdown of cultures. Power here is meant more than just political power. According to Machiavelli, power is theoretically defined as one centered (Sullivan 1973:258-270). It is no different from the traditional view of power that we see in history. Machiavelli's philosophical background on power is that, power starts from one place or is considered by a ruler to be an expandable. Given Machiavelli's philosophical background, there is no chance for such strong cultural similarities between Kerala and Sri Lanka. This is because the Keralites have not directed any direct intervention to Sri Lanka as previously discussed. But giving a clearer definition of power, the philosopher Michel Foucault argues that power, which is the opposite of Machiavelli's idea of concentrated power, exists eccentrically everywhere and with every person (Foucault 1978:94). Foucault's view can be cited as the closest theory on how cultural equivalence emerged between Kerala and Sri Lanka.

According to sources, there have been occasional migrations from Kerala to Sri Lanka for various purposes since around 13th century AD. During those migrations, thousands of people representing the culture of Kerala arrived in Sri Lanka. This is not only a cultural diffusion but also a large-scale genetic diffusion. What happened here is that, according to Foucault's theory, the decentralized power of each individual is transferred to another area. This suggests that the culture of Kerala may have slowly mixed with the culture of Sri Lanka.

The question arises as to whether the aforementioned cultural fusion is strong enough to later create (late mediaeval period) architectural similarities. The decisive factor with

regard to the architecture behind the study is Machiavelli's idea rather than Foucault's theory of power. Architectural similarities, especially in the study, can be traced back to the Gampola period. It is from this era that the Kerala-based aristocracy contributed to the main political structure of Sri Lanka. From the Gampola period onwards, aristocrats such as Senālakadhikāra Senevirath and Alagakkonāra, who became central political forces not only in the *Rāja Sabhā* but also in their areas, may have been able to spread their culture more easily and with long lasting effects.

The above can be further understood by comprehending the power of these elite leaders through contemporary sources. Iban Battuta, a pilgrim who arrived in the country in 1344 AD, reports that Alkonār lived like a king with a white elephant (Hussain 1953: 247-251). Minister Alagakkonāra is identified as Battuta Alkonār. It shows that he was a semi-local independent leader in that period. Lankatilaka copper plate named Senālakadhikāra as '*Lanka Senevirath Rāja*' (Paranavitana 1960:24-38). Senālakadhikāra Senevirath was a chief minister, but sources named him as a king. Such sources of information reveal the power of the elite ministers. The power of the ministers of Kerala origin suggests that they acted in accordance with the cultures they were accustomed to rather than adapting to the existing cultures. It is not difficult to imagine that the tendency towards the architectural tradition followed by these ministers, who were attracted to other aristocrats and the masses, may have been popular at the time.

The above led to a reasonable assumption regarding the construction of features parallel to the Kerala features in the construction of elite residential buildings. Although that is the main reason, the question arises as to whether that alone is sufficient to sustain such similarities. This situation which started by the aristocracy of the Gampola period can be further developed due to Minister Senālakadhikāra Senevirath's Kerala relatives who were summoned by King Parakramabāhu VI during the Kotte period. The so-called nobles and their descendants were the leading nobles (*Bandāras*) of the Kandyan period and they too may have preserved the cultural features of their origins.

The human interventions mentioned above may have been more successful due to the ecological similarities between Kerala and Sri Lanka. This is because there is a possibility of the creation of similar cultural characteristics under similar environmental conditions. It is also possible that the wooden architecture of Kerala in particular was well adapted to the upcountry areas of Sri Lanka. In addition, the presence of people who are prepared to accept the changing cultural conditions is an essential factor. There may be people who did not ignore the culture of Kerala through the long-term migrations that had taken place over the centuries. Thus, it is clear that the long-standing conditions in Sri Lanka led to the formation of Kerala culture from an architectural point of view. It could be concluded that, this is a combination of a number of major and residual causes.

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Map No.01: Kerala- Sri Lanka linkage in Gondwanaland (Dissanayake & Chandrajith 1999)

Map No.02: Worldwide Biodiversity hotspot map (Myers, Mittermeier & Kent et al 2000)

Figure No.01: Eka Sālā, Tivandrum

Figure No.02: Nālukettu, Calicut

Figure No.03: Nālukettu, Trissur

Figure No.04: Nālukettu, Calicut

Figure No.05: Nālukettu, Kottayam

Figure No.06: Nālukettu, Kottayam

Figure No.07: Kappetipola Walawwa,
Hulangamuwa

Figure No.08: Ehelepola Walawwa,
Kandy

Figure No.09: Giragama Walawwa, Kandy

Figure No.10: Meedum Walawwa, Rambukkana

Figure No.11: *Niwra'* and *Vishkambha*,
Eka Sālā, Calicut

Figure No.12: *Niwra'* and *Vishkambha*,
Eka Sālā, Tivandrum

Figure No.13: Soldara entrance,
Eka Sālā, Tivandrum

Figure No.14: triangular roof sill face,
Eka Sālā, Tivandrum

Figure No.15: Dutch influenced elite
house, Kottayam

Figure No.16: Dutch influenced
elite house, Kochin fort

Figure No.17: Dutch influenced
elite house, Kochin fort

Figure No.18: Dutch buildings,
Galle fort

Figure No.19: Dutch buildings,
Galle fort

Figure No.20: Tribal house,
Attappadi forest